

UNITED STATES DEPARTMENT OF THE INTERIOR

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE

Fishery Resources

FISHERY AND AQUATIC MANAGEMENT PROGRAM

in

YELLOWSTONE NATIONAL PARK

Technical Report for Calendar Year 1979

JUNE 1980

THE HISTORY OF THE

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

... ..

ANNUAL PROJECT TECHNICAL REPORT FOR 1979

Fishery and Aquatic Management Program

Yellowstone National Park

Ronald D. Jones, Project Leader

June, 1980

Authors (alphabetical):

Robert E. Gresswell, Fishery Management Biologist; Back-country lake surveys, Clear and Cub Creek fish traps, Yellowstone Lake gillnetting, Purse seine operation and Cutthroat trout population estimates.

Daryl E. Jennings, Fishery Management Biologist; Pelican Creek fish trap and Nonconsumptive use of aquatic areas.

Ronald D. Jones, Project Leader; General subjects.

Sandra M. Rubrecht, Biological Technician; Back-country stream surveys, LeHardy's Rapids and Lewis Lake tributary inventory.

John D. Varley, Assistant Project Leader; Fishery management evaluations and general subjects.

Cover Photo: Newly discovered "Yellowstone fine-spotted cutthroat trout" from Bear Creek.

TABLE OF CONTENTS
PART I

	<u>Page</u>
Title page.....	i
Table of Contents.....	ii
Introduction.....	1
Parkwide Fishing in 1979.....	5
Yellowstone Lake.....	8
Yellowstone River.....	15
Madison River.....	19
Firehole River.....	20
Gibbon River.....	21
Lewis Lake.....	22
Shoshone Lake.....	23
Slough Creek.....	24
Lamar River.....	25
Soda Butte Creek.....	26
Gardner River.....	27
Lewis River.....	28
Indian Creek.....	29
Nez Perce Creek.....	29
Heart Lake.....	30
Lewis-Shoshone Channel.....	31
Trout Lake.....	32
Bechler River.....	33
Gallatin River.....	34
Riddle Lake.....	35
Falls River.....	36
Grebe Lake.....	37
Snake River.....	38
Sylvan Lake.....	39
Pelican Creek.....	40
Cache Creek.....	40
Grizzly Lake.....	41
Pebble Creek.....	41
Tower Creek.....	42
Obsidian Creek.....	42
Little Firehole River.....	43
Blacktail Ponds.....	43
Clear Creek.....	44
Lava Creek.....	44
Boundary Creek.....	45
Hellroaring Creek.....	45
Iron Spring Creek.....	46
Cascade Lake.....	47

2. The opening date of waters in the Trout Lake drainage above Soda Butte Creek, including Trout, Buck and Shrimp Lakes, was delayed from May 28th to June 15th.

3. A daily limit of five fish, any size, of which at least three must be brook or brown trout, was established on Cougar Creek (below the Gneiss Creek trail crossing), on Grayling Creek and its tributaries; and the Gallatin River and its tributaries.

4. Regulations were amended to allow fish entrails to be disposed of in back-country waters.

These facts are presented not only to show the widespread importance of the Park's fisheries but also to pinpoint the difficulties faced in the management of those fisheries. Although fishing pressure declined in 1979, the overall trend in the past decade has been upward, similar to the increases in total Park recreational visitation.

The format and content of this year's technical report is different than that presented in recent years. The success of the Volunteer Fisherman Report System (VFR) permits us access to fishery data on a large number of waters. We have annually reported on about 30 lakes and streams that together make up over 96% of the total Park angling use and effort. Periodically, a series of years can be combined to assess the remainder of lakes and streams comprising the other 4%. In this report, fishery statistics for 1977, 1978, and 1979 are combined to estimate use, effort and success statistics for these low sample waters. In order to do this, the management reports on the 30 major waters have been abbreviated. Readers interested in more detailed treatment of the major fisheries are referred to our 1978 report (Jones et al 1978).

The report is divided into two sections. Part I deals with the fishery management of individual waters including any proposed changes in management. Part II includes specialized and technical studies not usually of interest to the general reader. Increasing requests for this report and the expense of producing it have prompted us to distribute it in this manner. To improve the readability and flow of the report, complex technical tables not essential to the discussion in the text have been placed in an appendix. Recipients of Part I only may find references to the appendix but will not have these tables enclosed.

In 1979, the following regulation changes were made:

1. The Park established new catch-and-release regulations on the following waters: The Falls River above the falls at the 7200 foot contour, as posted, including Beula and Hering Lakes; the Bechler River and its tributaries above Colonnade Falls; Cougar Creek above the Gneiss Creek trail crossing; Sportsman Lake, including the inlets and the outlet downstream to Mol Heron Creek; Sedge Creek and its tributaries above Turbid Lake; the entire Cascade Creek drainage (near Canyon). Catch-and-release for cutthroat trout only was established for Blacktail Deer Creek drainage including Blacktail Ponds (regular limit applies to brook trout).

tion is especially important since all maintenance fish stocking for harvest purposes was ended over twenty years ago. Wild stocks must therefore bear the pressure of increasing public interest. Management practices, consisting largely of restrictive regulations, have had to be innovative to keep abreast of increasing trends of parkwide fishing use, explosive increases in back-country visitation and growing interest in specialized fishing (such as fly fishing).

Keeping indigenous fish populations in as near a natural state as possible while continuing to allow sport-fishing would seem to be in direct conflict, and it may be. Tests for compatibility are a continuing objective of our program.

Yellowstone has one species of fish (the Montana grayling) and over a dozen waters restricted to catch-and-release only. A number of other waters, including Yellowstone Lake, are partially catch-and-release as a result of maximum or minimum length limits. These highly restrictive regulations have, by most measures of angling quality, improved populations and provided fishing superior to that found before the restrictions but lack the quality known 100 years ago. Despite improved sport-fishing and fish populations, the question of achieving compatibility with natural area concepts remains unanswered.

In 1979, the National Park Service issued 195,100 free fishing permits to fish Park waters. Permittees comprised a composite group from all 50 states, all Canadian Provinces and numerous foreign countries. The largest single group came from the local states of Montana, Wyoming and Idaho. Although Park anglers fish approximately 120 different lakes and streams, about 30 fisheries comprise most of the fishing pressure. Six fisheries are of such a quality to attract national attention. An average of 3-4 articles are published annually in national magazines concerning various Park waters and are generally complimentary.

The fact that twelve states have fewer total licensed anglers than Yellowstone illustrates the national importance of Park fisheries. The number of Park license-holders equals 83% of the total licenses issued by the state of Wyoming, 74% of the total issued by Montana and 55% of the total issued by Idaho. Using values reported in the 1975 National Survey of Hunting, Fishing and Wildlife Associated Recreation (USDI, Fish and Wildlife Service 1977), Yellowstone hosts about 1.1% of the national cold water anglers. Park fishermen have a substantial economic impact as it is estimated that they spend about 4 million dollars annually in and around the Park.

INTRODUCTION

In its establishment act of March 1, 1872, Yellowstone National Park was "dedicated and set apart as a public park or pleasuring-ground for the benefit and enjoyment of the people" and "for the preservation, from injury or spoilation of all timber, mineral deposits, natural curiosities or wonders . . . and their retention in their natural condition." Since 1872, additional legislation and policies have further defined the purpose of the Park to prohibit hunting of all birds and mammals and to regulate fishing. The Park is managed as a natural area to perpetuate as a functioning natural ecosystem the indigenous fauna, flora, geology and scenic landscape. Because fishing is most often harvest oriented, and thereby causes alterations in energy pathways, its existence is often a significant perturbation to the ecosystem. Fishing has, nonetheless, a historical precedent and has been a major visitor activity for over 100 years. The objectives of fishery management have changed radically during this period. Following very liberal and permissive regulations during the initial 60 years, present regulations serve objectives that have evolved (since the late 1930's) to more closely coincide with the Park's primary purpose. Specifically, the objectives of the fishery program are:

1. Manage the fishery as an integral part of the Park ecosystem.
2. Provide fishermen with a high quality angling experience with wild trout under natural settings.
3. Preserve and restore native species and aquatic habitats.

Regulations that attempt to restore or protect fishes and maintain high quality angling involve manipulating season dates, restricting baits, using creel and size limits, and designating certain species or waters for catch-and-release fishing only. Additionally, certain waters are closed to protect rare or endangered species, nesting birds, or to provide vistas for viewing scenic landscapes and undisturbed wildlife (including fishes).

High-quality angling is defined as having the opportunity to fish for rare native species or wild trout in pristine waters where angling removals do not exceed natural replenishment rates or, on a year-to-year basis, reduce fish numbers, biomass, sizes and age-groups from that which would occur in the absence of fishing. This management approach stipulates a philosophical and literal distinction between catching fishes for sport and removing fishes for consumption. This distinc-

TABLE OF CONTENTS (Continued)
PART II

	<u>Page</u>
Stream Surveys.....	61
Maple Creek.....	61
Cascade Creek.....	67
Lewis River.....	70
Slough Creek.....	77
Lake Survey Program.....	88
Beach Springs Lake.....	96
Dewdrop Lake.....	103
Duck Lake.....	108
Geode Lake.....	111
Glade Lake.....	117
Gooseneck Lake.....	122
Harlequin Lake.....	129
Upper Gooseneck Lake.....	136
Lewis Lake Tributary Inventory.....	139
Nonconsumptive Use of Aquatic Areas.....	141
LeHardy's Rapids.....	143
Pelican Creek Fish Trap.....	148
Clear and Cub Creek Cutthroat Spawning Runs.....	152
Largemesh Gillnetting.....	165
Fall Purse Seine Operation.....	181
Cutthroat Trout Population Estimates.....	185
Literature Cited.....	187
Appendix A.....	193

TABLE OF CONTENTS (Continued)
PART 1

	<u>Page</u>
Blacktail Deer Creek.....	48
Fan Creek.....	48
Beula Lake.....	49
Middle Creek.....	49
Wolf Lake.....	50
Goose Lake.....	50
Ribbon Lake.....	51
Duck Creek.....	51
Native Species Restoration Program.....	52
Other Project Activities.....	56
Acknowledgments.....	59

PARKWIDE FISHING IN 1979

Recreational visitation in Yellowstone Park declined in 1979 to one million visitors (Table 1). The number of free fishing permits issued (195,100) was below the number issued from 1976 through 1978 but higher than those issued in 1973 (the first year they were required) and 1974-75. Because many visitors acquire permits and do not fish, the actual number of anglers afield during the year amounted to 139,100.

The exit gate survey indicated that the average angler spent 1.87 days fishing in the Park and fished an average of 1.12 different waters per day. These data, together with permit totals, yield the information necessary to compute the annual Parkwide total fisherman use (angler-days). During 1979, sportfishermen spent 291,300 angler-days and 656,800 angler-hours in the Park (Table 3).

An estimated 662,700 fish were landed and 96,800 creeled at a rate of 1.01 and 0.15 fish per hour, respectively (Table 2). Of the fish landed, 88% were released and 12% creeled.

The number of fish landed per average angler trip (2.24 hours) was 2.5, and the number creeled was 0.37 (Table 3). Anglers indicating satisfaction with their fishing trip landed 3.9 fish, whereas those that were unsatisfied landed only 1.5 fish. The average length of fish landed was also higher for satisfied anglers (13.8 inches) than unsatisfied fishermen (12.1 inches).

Of 65,405 fish reported landed by Park fishermen, 76.7% were listed as cutthroat trout, followed by rainbow trout (6.7%), brown trout (6.5%), brook trout (5.1%) and lake trout (2.4%). Small numbers of Montana grayling, mountain whitefish, cutthroat x rainbow hybrid and non-game species were also caught.

In 1979, the average size of fish landed was 366 mm (14.4 in) which was slightly higher than in 1975-78 (Table 2). Of 65,726 fish reported, over 70.4% exceeded 305 mm (12 in) in length and 57% exceeded 355 mm (14 in). The average size creeled during the year was 338 mm (13.3 in). Lake trout were the largest and averaged 475 mm (18.7 in) followed by cutthroat trout (381 mm or 13.4 in), cutthroat x rainbow hybrids (331 mm or 13.0 in), rainbow trout (310 mm or 12.2 in), grayling (270 mm or 10.6 in) and brook trout (251 mm or 9.9 in).

The percentage of fishermen that reported satisfaction with their overall fishing experience were 73% in 1979. Satisfaction rates with numbers and sizes of fish landed were 67% and 68%, respectively (Table 2).

On the VFR card, fishermen are asked to judge their own technical expertise level, and expertise is then estimated for each water by an arbitrary value whereby 1.0 is an inexperienced angler, 2.0 is experienced and 3.0 is an expert. In 1979, the mean expertise for 7,634 Park anglers was 1.88: a value indicating that most fishermen fall into the inexperienced to experienced category (Table 2).

Table 1. Estimates of part recreational visitation, fishing permits issued, total parkwide anglers, total parkwide angler-days, Yellowstone National Park, 1972-1979

	1972	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977	1978	1979
Total Park Recreational Visitation:	2,246,927	2,061,537	1,928,915	2,239,483	2,519,224	2,481,933	2,616,359	—
Percent change from previous year:	—	-3.5%	-6.4%	+16.1%	+12.5%	-1.5%	+5.2%	—
Park Fishing Permits Issued:	—	169,103	164,630	191,550	213,250	217,000	218,500	195,160
Percent change from previous year:	—	—	-2.7%	+16.4%	+11.3%	+1.8%	+0.5%	-11.7%
Total Parkwide Anglers:	—	121,238	116,518	138,322	151,730	154,581	155,720	139,150
Percent change from previous year:	—	—	-4.4%	+17.0%	+11.3%	+1.9%	+0.7%	-11.9%
Total Parkwide Angler-days:	—	230,103	720,600	257,300	284,260	311,300	333,500	291,300
Percent change from previous year:	—	—	-4.4%	+17.0%	+10.5%	+8.7%	+6.7%	-14.6%
95% Confidence Limits:	—	225,500-234,700	215,570-724,500	248,100-266,300	278,500-289,950	304,500-311,500	326,200-341,370	274,500-339,700

Table 2. Fisherman use, effort, success, and harvest for Yellowstone National Park, 1973-1979

Year	Angler-days	$\bar{x}$ length angler-day	Total hours fished	Landing rate	Total fish landed	Creel rate	Total fish created	Percentage anglers satisfied with:			Average total length of fish landed (in.)	Mean expertise level
								overall experience	numbers caught	sizes caught		
1979	291,300	2.24	656,800	1.01	661,700	0.15	56,800	73	67	68	14.4	1.58 (1.67-1.90)
1978	333,500	2.23	744,400	0.59	736,900	0.17	126,500	73	66	68	14.2	1.56
1977	311,300	2.33	725,300	0.93	710,800	0.20	145,100	75	68	70	14.3	1.53
1976	284,200	2.36	676,700	1.02	684,100	0.20	134,100	74	69	69	14.1	1.50
1975	257,300	2.31	594,400	1.09	647,500	0.23	136,700	77	74	75	14.2	—
1974	220,050	2.42	531,300	0.86	455,500	0.19	101,000	—	—	—	—	—
1973	230,100	2.45	564,400	0.86	495,400	0.16	96,300	—	—	—	—	—

1) Based on: 1.0 = inexperienced angler, 2.0 = experienced, 3.0 = expert. 95% confidence interval in parenthesis.

Table 3. Characteristics of satisfied and unsatisfied anglers, and the influence of the relative expertise of anglers to sportfishing success in Yellowstone National Park, 1979

	Mean number days fishing	Mean number hours fished/day	Landing rate (fish/hour)	Creel rate (fish/hour)	Fish landed/angler-day	Fish creeled/angler-day	Average length fish landed (in.)	Average expertise	Sample anglers (n)
Satisfied anglers									
Unsatisfied anglers	1.86	3.23	1.20	0.18	3.9	0.58	13.8	1.89	4,533
sum of x		2.97	0.50	0.08	1.5	0.24	12.1	1.87	2,012
		2.49	1.01	0.15	2.5	0.37	13.6	1.88	7,655
Inexperienced anglers	1.70	2.17	0.16	0.17	0.35	0.37	13.5	1.0	1,486
Experienced anglers	1.92	2.52	1.01	0.15	2.55	0.38	13.4	2.0	4,249
Expert anglers	1.91	2.88	1.71	0.14	4.93	0.40	13.8	3.0	810
sum of x	1.86	2.49	1.01	0.15	2.50	0.37	13.6	1.88	7,655

Satisfaction Matrix

	Satisfied anglers			Unsatisfied anglers		
	Overall Satisfaction	Satisfaction with numbers landed	Satisfaction with sizes landed	Overall satisfaction	Satisfaction with numbers landed	Satisfaction with sizes landed
Landing Rate (fish/hr)						
Inexperienced anglers	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.3	0.3	0.4
Experienced anglers	1.2	1.2	1.1	0.4	0.4	0.8
Expert anglers	2.1	2.1	2.0	0.8	0.6	1.1
Creel Rate (fish/hr)						
Inexperienced anglers	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.05	0.08	0.09
Experienced anglers	0.18	0.18	0.17	0.06	0.07	0.10
Expert anglers	0.16	0.17	0.16	0.08	0.08	0.11
fish Size (Inches)						
Inexperienced anglers	13.5	13.6	13.7	13.0	12.7	12.5
Experienced anglers	13.6	13.5	13.9	12.2	13.1	11.9
Expert anglers	14.0	13.6	14.3	12.0	12.1	11.4

1) Based on 1.0 = inexperienced angler; 2.0 experienced; 3.0 expert.

2) The averages are based on all anglers in the sample. Not all anglers marked satisfaction or expertise boxes therefore the sums of the columns do not add up to the total given.

YELLOWSTONE LAKE

Yellowstone Lake has always been the most popular sport fishery in the Park. With a surface area of 35,600 ha (88,000 acres) the lake would appear to be large enough to accommodate enormous angling pressure; however, the lake is deep, cold and has low productivity. In addition, decades of trout harvest plus 50 years cumulative removal of cutthroat spawn, significant alterations in the original age-size structure of the cutthroat population, the possible extinction of discrete spawning populations, introduction and expansion of three nongame species and adverse changes in the lake's basic productivity have each contributed to a decline in the viability of what is the largest and most significant inland cutthroat trout population in North America.

Except for the temporary effects of wars, depressions, some angling regulations and the collapse of the cutthroat population in the 1960's, angler use on Yellowstone Lake has shown an increasing trend since 1872. Use since 1973, and particularly since 1975, has an upward trend although current use and effort is historically equal to that which occurred in the post World War II period (Jones et al 1978). The total annual harvest from the lake has been relatively stable since 1970, although it declined significantly in 1979. Recent harvests correspond historically to the numbers taken during World War II, and before that, about 1920. Recent catch or landing rates are roughly equivalent to those of the late 1940's and have shown an improving trend since 1969.

Past fishing regulations have had less effect on total harvest, use and effort than on the age-size structure of the cutthroat population. Restrictive regulations have generally had the effect of reducing the harvest of trout because of less fisherman use following the change, indicating the change was somewhat unpopular. Reductions in angler use, however, have always been temporary and, overall, have only served to slow the rate of increase.

Regulations in effect in 1979 specified catch-and-release fishing except that two fish may be kept per day if they are under 13 inches in length. This regulation has been in effect since 1975 on the lake, and since 1978 on the lake's tributaries.

During 1979, fisherman use on the lake comprised 49% of the total park-wide angling use. An estimated 58,200 anglers spent 142,700 angler-days and 308,200 angler-hours fishing the lake (Table 4). Fisherman use (angler-days) and effort (angler-hours) declined in 1979.

Table 4. Fishery statistics from Yellowstone Park waters with over 40 angler-days in the sample and which comprise over 90% of the parkwide angler-day use in 1979

Water	% of total parkwide angler-days	Total reported angler-days (1/8)	Anglers	7 length angler-days (hours)	Estimates for the season					Total fish landed	Creel rate	Average size fish landed (inches)	Average size fish creel (inches)	Percent anglers landing 1 or more fish	Average expertise	Overall experience	# anglers satisfied with numbers caught	Fish sizes caught
					Angler-days (trips)	Angler-hours (effort)	Landing rate	Creel rate	Total fish landed									
Parkwide fisheries	100.00	14,700	159,100	7.74	791,350	656,800	1.01	0.15	681,700	96,000	14.4	13.5	67	73	1.82	67	69	
Yellowstone Lake	48.69	6,915	58,700	2.16	142,700	308,700	0.99	0.20	304,000	61,400	15.5	14.1	67	76	1.75	68	74	
Yellowstone River	13.68	1,931	19,900	2.52	39,500	100,500	1.24	0.08	124,500	7,600	15.1	13.1	74	64	1.99	77	63	
Firehole River	5.65	802	6,900	2.50	16,500	28,000	0.53	0.04	20,200	1,400	13.6	16.5	51	51	2.05	36	44	
Gibson River	4.67	288	6,100	2.57	14,700	35,100	0.62	0.02	21,700	400	11.6	13.1	51	60	2.04	57	59	
Lewis Lake	3.74	528	7,100	1.91	10,000	20,500	0.75	0.10	15,700	2,000	9.7	10.9	57	51	1.74	49	53	
Shoshone Lake	3.07	433	4,100	2.46	9,100	22,900	0.56	0.17	12,900	4,000	15.2	16.8	51	75	1.66	63	74	
Slough Creek	2.65	374	2,600	2.43	6,900	21,000	0.57	0.16	12,500	3,400	18.4	19.0	64	72	1.81	64	61	
Levir River	1.79	252	4,100	2.82	7,700	21,700	1.59	0.01	34,600	300	13.7	—	88	87	2.09	83	86	
Scotts Bluff Creek	1.51	199	3,000	2.33	5,700	12,100	2.01	0.05	24,400	600	11.7	10.8	86	87	2.10	85	75	
Carner River	1.30	184	2,000	2.79	4,100	9,400	1.25	0.20	11,800	1,600	10.5	11.4	71	85	1.93	67	67	
Lewis River	0.68	138	1,900	1.99	2,400	6,700	1.33	0.27	6,400	1,700	10.1	11.0	73	64	1.90	63	45	
Hot Forge Creek	0.62	116	1,400	1.70	2,400	5,400	0.88	0.04	4,500	200	10.5	13.7	59	57	2.03	51	36	
Heart Lake	0.55	77	1,200	1.99	1,600	3,200	0.57	0.08	5,400	1,700	9.1	9.1	67	64	1.91	69	23	
Lewis-Strother Cr.	0.50	71	600	2.23	1,500	3,400	1.20	0.23	4,100	300	11.3	12.4	41	39	1.91	37	30	
Front Lake	0.48	67	900	2.67	1,500	3,900	0.52	0.12	2,000	500	12.9	19.6	67	61	1.60	44	63	
Seculer River	0.43	61	700	2.42	1,400	3,500	0.45	0.19	1,600	700	12.8	17.8	67	81	2.03	69	75	
Gallatin River	0.40	57	500	1.88	1,300	3,000	1.09	0.26	3,300	800	15.3	16.1	57	80	1.87	70	65	
Wicche Lake	0.38	54	600	2.07	1,600	2,200	0.69	0.24	1,500	500	11.5	11.9	96	76	2.05	70	60	
Falls River	0.33	47	600	2.31	1,000	2,700	0.70	0.26	1,600	600	14.2	13.4	83	74	1.84	74	74	
Grate Lake	0.32	45	700	2.37	900	2,700	1.25	0.13	3,600	400	10.7	10.7	64	63	1.84	76	88	
Snake River	0.30	42	600	1.65	500	1,400	0.74	0.14	1,700	300	10.1	11.4	78	50	2.06	70	40	
Sylvan Lake	0.28	40	600	1.48	800	1,700	1.37	0.01	1,700	10	10.5	—	69	67	1.84	56	52	

Table 5. Fishery statistics from Yellowstone Park waters with less than 40 angler-days per year represented in the sample*

Water	Total reported angler-days (ifc)	Anglers	Average angler-days (hours)	Angler days (trips)	Angler hours (effort)	Landing rate	Estimates for the Season						% anglers satisfied with:				
							Total fish landed	Creel rate	Total fish created	Average size landed (inches)	Average length created (inches)	Percent of anglers landing one or more fish	Average experience	Overall experience	Numbers	Fish sizes	
Felician Creek	36	620	2.10	700	1,600	1.66	0.05	2,900	80	14.5	17.8	160	2.19	83	50	57	44
Caere Creek	35	310	1.80	700	1,300	2.03	0.42	2,600	500	9.9	9.6	100	1.63	94	54	44	54
Grizzly Lake	34	550	2.75	700	1,600	1.52	0.55	2,500	900	9.5	9.8	68	1.79	80	60	56	56
Pebble Creek	34	510	1.65	700	1,100	1.44	0.38	1,500	400	9.4	10.5	82	1.82	83	83	71	71
Lower Creek	32	440	1.30	650	850	1.74	0.59	1,500	500	9.7	10.0	69	1.68	82	62	56	56
Decision Creek	23	350	1.93	470	960	2.65	0.34	2,500	300	9.0	9.5	67	1.95	71	65	72	71
Blacktail Ponds*	—	67	300	1.55	400	670	0.36	530	220	10.5	10.9	66	1.84	73	64	71	71
Clear Creek*	—	61	300	1.89	400	750	0.24	2,000	180	14.4	13.4	98	1.59	56	56	62	62
Hellroaring Creek*	—	60	200	2.41	380	930	0.24	1,100	270	10.2	11.3	88	2.03	74	77	55	55
Iron Spring Creek*	—	60	220	1.67	390	640	0.16	460	100	10.7	12.2	58	1.93	64	61	67	67
Little Firehole River	55	290	1.62	360	610	1.06	0.21	640	170	9.5	11.0	61	2.04	74	67	58	58
Cascade Creek*	55	400	1.43	540	770	2.27	0.04	1,750	30	10.6	13.5	63	1.92	68	84	65	65
Bummary Creek*	51	200	1.82	340	600	1.19	0.27	730	170	9.0	10.1	100	1.94	77	71	52	52
Lava Creek*	51	260	1.44	320	460	1.23	0.48	570	220	9.2	9.7	85	1.66	83	73	63	63
Blacktail over Creek*	47	240	1.56	300	560	1.50	0.50	900	280	9.3	9.6	82	1.50	70	70	54	54
Fan Creek*	47	70	2.77	250	800	0.66	0.27	530	220	10.1	10.9	100	1.84	94	81	106	106
Beula Lake*	41	160	1.86	260	480	2.35	0.36	1,140	170	10.9	11.6	83	1.63	93	66	61	61
Middle Creek*	40	210	1.51	270	380	1.24	0.37	470	140	10.4	10.4	67	1.95	68	62	62	62
Wolf Lake*	38	150	2.06	240	500	0.95	0.27	500	140	11.3	13.4	50	1.87	61	61	71	71
Goose Lake*	32	140	1.69	200	340	0.37	0.19	130	65	14.1	15.4	33	1.95	50	43	64	64
Pitbon Lake*	32	170	1.78	200	360	0.38	0.21	370	75	10.5	10.5	80	1.42	67	78	33	33
Buck Creek*	30	120	2.47	190	460	0.83	0.17	390	60	11.7	16.7	75	1.86	50	64	64	64

* Figures presented for these fisheries are an average value for 1977, 78, 79, except for reported use which is the sum of those years.

Angler-use continues to be most heavily concentrated in the accessible areas including the northwest portion of the lake, the West Thumb segment, western shoreline and eastern shore. The central and southern areas continue to sustain the lowest proportion of use (Appendix A Table 1). From 1969 through 1974, areas of the lake with easy access accounted for 84 to 88% of the use. Since 1975, annual percentages have ranged from 89 to 94%. These data indicate that the regulation limiting anglers to small trout has shifted more pressure to the northern part of the lake which has smaller fish and also the part that has been historically over-fished.

Yellowstone Lake fishermen landed an estimated 304,000 trout and released 242,000. The total angler-caused mortality was estimated at 84,800 (61,400 creel plus an estimated 23,400 which may have died of hooking wounds following release). Overall landing and creel rates were 0.99 and 0.20 trout/hour, respectively. Landing and creel rates from the boat segment (1.25 and 0.24 trout/hour, respectively) were substantially above those from the shoreline segment (0.74 and 0.16 trout/hour, respectively) (Table 6). Success by area continues to be inversely related to angling pressure, e.g. the more remote areas continue to sustain higher success rates than the more heavily fished accessible areas.

Sixty-seven percent of the lake's fishermen landed one or more trout whereas 34% creel one or more.

In 1979, the lengths of 29,900 trout were reported from Yellowstone Lake; it is apparent that the illegal harvest of trout over 13 inches is a continuing problem (Appendix A Table 2). An estimated 18,700 trout over 13 inches and 4,200 over 14 inches were creel. The average size of trout creel was above the legal maximum at 333 mm (13 in). Although the number of illegal trout in the creel has declined since the first year of the maximum size limit, the violation rate remains a concern. Not only does the public voice its concern over the level of violations, but the 22,900 illegal trout creel remains far above an acceptable level.

Despite the high level of illegal large trout in the creel, the age-size structure of the cutthroat population continues to improve (Table 7). The average size of trout landed in 1979 was 394 mm (15.5 in); this is a 10 mm (0.4 in) increase over 1978. Length frequencies continue to show general improvement indicating survival of proportionately more fish to older and larger size groups (Table 7). The percentage of trout landed exceeding 406 mm (16 in) in total length, at 21.6%, is the highest yet observed. The percentage landed measuring over 457 mm (18 in) and 508 mm (20 in), rose and continues substantially higher than before the regulation change.

Table 6. Fishing statistics from Yellowstone Lake, 1979

Yellowstone lake area:	% of lake total	Total VFR use reported	Anglers	Length angler-day (hours)	Predicted totals for season				% Anglers satisfied with:				
					Angler-days (trips)	Angler-hours	Landing rate	Creel rate	Total fish landed	Total fish created	Overall experience	Fish numbers	Fish sizes
Shore	5.00	346	2,933	2.03	7,136	14,471	0.99	0.25	14,274	3,610	83	81	1.73
Boat	0.94	65	419	3.25	1,336	3,126	1.02	0.24	3,202	736	72	67	1.77
Shore	29.56	2,044	17,636	1.20	42,183	84,182	0.71	0.14	59,439	12,159	69	58	1.76
Boat	15.49	1,071	10,166	2.88	22,100	46,440	0.86	0.25	39,836	11,525	81	72	1.68
Shore	6.12	423	2,860	2.07	8,725	18,082	0.93	0.21	16,895	3,759	82	74	1.69
Boat	0.74	51	291	4.10	1,047	3,030	0.57	0.13	1,725	389	70	80	2.07
Shore	9.72	672	6,030	1.83	13,864	25,352	0.57	0.15	14,522	3,754	65	54	1.74
Boat	10.73	742	5,812	2.33	15,309	34,643	0.94	0.24	32,693	8,177	81	77	1.79
Shore	0.17	12	164	1.81	242	439	1.72	0.25	757	108	100	83	1.67
Boat	3.07	212	2,077	3.80	4,370	11,798	1.59	0.17	18,709	2,011	97	92	1.72
Shore	0.32	22	146	2.98	448	1,335	1.23	0.14	1,643	191	100	100	2.12
Boat	3.04	210	1,239	4.10	4,329	12,532	1.76	0.16	22,116	1,997	90	90	1.84
Shore	0.16	32	164	2.03	655	1,328	1.27	0.25	1,680	335	67	67	2.00
Boat	2.10	145	874	3.27	2,987	7,028	1.96	0.20	13,799	1,301	87	80	1.94
All boat	43.73	3,024	24,686	3.29	62,410	147,948	1.26	0.24	185,673	35,314	83	76	1.74
All shore	56.27	3,891	33,468	2.12	80,305	160,259	0.73	0.16	117,456	25,954	71	61	1.76
Entire lake	100.00	6,915	58,154	2.56	142,720	308,219	0.99	0.20	303,961	61,392	76	68	1.75

Table 7. Average length and length frequencies of cutthroat trout landed and creeled from Yellowstone Lake, 1973-1979

		Number and percentage of trout in length groups (inches):								
		< 10	10-12	12-14	14-16	16-18	18-20	> 20	N	
Number of trout reported landed:										
13"	1979	781	2,463	7,042	13,193	5,308	912	237	29,936	
max.	1978	1,174	3,878	10,322	14,794	4,523	728	188	35,607	
size	1977	645	3,029	10,058	11,778	3,619	613	228	29,980	
	1976	816	3,415	10,160	10,123	2,295	349	94	27,252	
	1975	686	2,634	8,654	8,366	1,571	155	44	22,133	
14"	1974	823	1,861	6,276	8,296	1,097	90	4	18,447	
min.	1973	131	364	1,204	1,521	268	9	0	3,497	
size										
Percentage of trout reported landed:										
13"	1979	2.6	8.2	23.5	44.1	17.7	3.0	0.8	29,936	
max.	1978	3.3	10.9	29.0	41.5	12.7	2.0	0.5	35,607	
size	1977	2.2	10.1	33.6	39.3	12.1	2.0	0.8	29,980	
	1976	3.0	12.5	37.3	37.1	8.4	1.3	0.3	27,252	
	1975	3.1	11.9	39.1	37.8	7.1	0.7	0.2	22,133	
14"	1974	4.5	10.1	34.0	45.0	5.9	0.5	0.02	18,447	
min.	1973	3.7	10.4	34.4	43.5	7.7	0.3	0	3,497	
size										

Percentage of trout landed measuring over:										
		> 12 in	> 14 in	> 16 in	> 18 in	> 20 in	Mean length landed		Mean length creeled	
							in	mm	in	mm
13"	1979	89.2	65.6	21.6	3.8	0.8	15.5	393	13.1	333
max.	1978	85.8	56.8	15.3	2.6	0.5	15.2	386	13.1	333
size	1977	87.8	54.2	14.9	2.8	0.8	15.2	386	13.3	338
	1976	84.8	47.5	14.1	2.0	0.3	14.7	373	13.8	350
	1975	84.9	45.8	8.0	0.9	0.2	14.7	373	13.7	348
14"	1974	85.5	51.4	6.5	0.5	0.02	14.7	373	13.8	350
min.	1973	85.8	51.4	7.9	0.3	0	14.8	376	13.8	350
size										

During 1979, the percentage of fishermen which reported satisfaction with their overall fishing experience was 76%; satisfaction with numbers and sizes landed was 68% and 74%, respectively (Table 4). The average expertise in 1979 was measured at 1.88 on the lake.

Recommendations

The primary goal of recent fishery management on Yellowstone Lake has been to insure compatibility between angler harvests and Park Natural Area management policies (these management guidelines are presented in the introduction of this report). Restrictive regulations since 1968 have attempted to serve these goals, and some progress has been made with each successive restriction. Levels of harvest during four years of the 13 inch maximum size limit suggest that the annual angler-caused mortality on Yellowstone Lake may still be too large to achieve compatibility. Even though the regulation is advancing proportionately more trout into the older age-groups, the total cutthroat trout in the population may not have increased. Increases in use or effort and/or improved catch-per-unit effort will significantly increase total mortality beyond current levels. Other than a complete fishing closure, the remaining regulatory options are few. Because 22,900 oversized trout were creel'd in 1979, intensive law enforcement and public education could theoretically reduce the annual harvest considerably. Beyond this, helpful regulations might include: limiting the number of fishermen that fish the lake, limiting the time they spend fishing, shortening the fishing season or catch-and-release-only fishing. These are the only options we are aware of that limit angling effort over a significant number of years. Limiting the number of anglers (a restricted number of permits) and shortening the season discriminates against large segments of the public (i.e. June visitors or fishermen seeking permits after they are all issued). Catch-and-release fishing discriminates against people who want to consume fish but gives them the choice of whether to fish or not; other options fail to give that choice.

The trout stock must be at a population density well above the maximum sustained yield level to insure sufficient density, competition, and voraciousness to provide for optimum sport. From our experience with other Park low- or no-kill cutthroat fisheries, catch-and-release fishing for Yellowstone Lake seems to be the most acceptable option. In fact, data for cutthroats parkwide suggests that the Yellowstone Lake fishery is far below its potential to provide recreational fishing and is one of the poorest cutthroat trout fisheries in the Park.

YELLOWSTONE RIVER

Approximately 114 km (71 miles) of the Yellowstone River flows through the Park. It is our second most popular fishery sustaining about 39,900 angler-days in 1979 (Table 4). Riverwide, sportfishing is considered excellent by accepted western trout standards. In 1979, an estimated 19,900 fishermen spent 100,500 angler-hours fishing the river. Anglers landed a total of 124,900 fish and creeled 7,600 for overall landing and creel rates of 1.2 and 0.08 fish/hour, respectively (Table 4). The average length for landed fish was 384 mm (15.1 in) and the average size of fish creeled was 340 mm (13.4 in) (Appendix A Table 2). Eighty-four percent of the anglers responding by VFR card were satisfied with their overall fishing experience; this is over 10% above the parkwide average. Anglers satisfied with the numbers and sizes of fish landed (77% and 83%, respectively) were similarly above the parkwide averages (Table 4). Riverwide statistics are strongly influenced by the popular catch-and-release segment which accounts for 73% of the total angling activity.

Because of differences in the amount of use, accessibility, fish barriers and species composition, we consider the river to have at least six identifiable fishery segments. These segments have different regulations concerning creel limits and season lengths.

At the end of 1979, catch-and-release only fishing had been in force on a 14.5 km (9 mile) section of the river downstream from Yellowstone Lake for seven years. A 10.3 km (6.4 mile) reach in Hayden Valley was closed to all fishing in 1965 and divides the catch-and-release portion. The first 1.6 km (1 mile) downstream from Yellowstone Lake outlet is also closed. In 1979, the catch-and-release portion hosted 14,000 anglers who spent 29,000 angler-days and 75,300 hours fishing for cutthroat trout (Table 8). An estimated 82,800 trout were landed at a rate of 1.13 trout/hour, and over 1,500 fish were illegally creeled. The average length of cutthroat landed was 394 mm (15.5 in). Fishermen satisfied with overall fishing experience (85%), numbers of fish caught (78%) and sizes caught (86%) was significantly higher on this segment than most of the other fisheries in the Park. Fishermen were highly successful as 72% landed one or more trout.

In 1979, angler-day use increased and was nearly as high as the highest catch-and-release use level observed in 1976. The landing rate was lower than any measured since the beginning of catch-and-release, though recent landing rates continue to be significantly above pre-catch-and-release rates.

Table B. Creel survey summary, Yellowstone River between Fishing Bridge and Chittenden Bridge, 1951-55, 1967-68, 1970 and 72, and 1973 through 1979.1)

	1951 to 1955 $\bar{x}$	1967 to 1968 $\bar{x}$	1970 and 1972 $\bar{x}$	1973	1974	1975	1976	1977 ⁶⁾	1978	1979
Angler-days (trips) ¹⁾	45,430	44,300	45,120	25,000	23,900	27,900	30,900	26,900	26,300	28,900
$\bar{x}$ Length angler trip (hrs)	1.97	2.00	1.87	2.35	2.31	2.48	2.45	2.44	2.50	2.60
Total hours fished	89,500	88,625	84,400	58,750	55,200	69,200	75,700	65,600	65,700	75,300
Landing rate (trout/hr)	2)	2)	0.74	1.74	2.25	2.04	1.43	1.43	1.23	1.10
Total trout landed	2)	2)	62,550	102,200	124,200	141,100	108,200	93,900	80,800	82,800
Creel rate (trout/hr)	0.41	0.43	0.18	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02
Total trout creeled	36,700	38,100	14,825	590	550	690	980	1,300	1,100	1,500
Angler-days per mile ⁸⁾	2,600	4,600	4,700	2,900	2,700	3,200	3,600	3,100	3,000	3,300
Angler-days per acre ⁸⁾	63	105	107	63	60	70	78	68	66	72
Angler-hours per acre ⁸⁾	123	209	199	147	138	173	189	164	164	188
Mean angler expertise ⁷⁾	-	-	-	-	-	-	2.00	1.98	1.99	2.02
$\bar{x}$ Trout landed and released	2)	2)	76.2	99.4	99.9	99.5	99.8	99.6	99.6	99.3
$\bar{x}$ Length trout creeled ⁵⁾	3)	13.5 ^m	14.7 ^m	3)	3)	3)	3)	14.3 ^m	13.3 ^m	13.2 ^m
$\bar{x}$ Length trout landed	3)	3)	3)	14.3 ^m	14.4 ^m	14.5 ^m	14.7 ^m	14.7 ^m	15.1 ^m	15.3 ^m

1) Statistics for 1951 through 1972 have been converted from summer to season-long estimates.

2) Trout landed and released were not measured during this period.

3) Not measured.

4) Three years of 5 fish creel limit plus two years of 3 fish creel limit.

5) Illegal beginning in 1973.

6) Revised upward 6% from that reported (Jones et al 1978).

7) Based on formula: 1.0 = inexperienced, 2.0 = experienced, 3.0 = expert.

8) Yellowstone River between Fishing Bridge and Chittenden Bridge is 16 mi long and averages 730 acres. Area open to fishing was 9.7 mi and 425 acres between 1965 and 1972. Beginning in 1973, the open area was 8.7 mi and 400 acres.

Data from fishermen indicated the size of the average trout landed increased from 363 mm (14.3 in) in 1973 to 389 mm (15.3 in) in 1979 (Table 8). Significant improvement in the size structure of the population has also occurred since the implementation of catch-and-release rules:

Percentage of Trout Landed Measuring Over:

Year	12 in	14 in	16 in	18 in	20 in
1979	92.5	77.5	35.9	8.7	1.0
1977	89.2	68.7	26.2	5.3	0.9
1976	90.0	67.7	24.3	4.4	0.7
1975	92.7	60.4	15.4	2.6	0.3
1974	89.5	63.3	26.6	6.6	1.2
1973	86.3	62.5	17.3	3.1	0.7

Although estimates for 1973 and 1974 suffer from poor sample sizes, beginning in 1975, a minimum of 10,000 trout are represented in the values presented. Results for 1979 show the highest values ever for trout over 14 and 16 inches.

The second most heavily fished segment of the Yellowstone River was in the Tower Junction area between Quartz and Little Buffalo Creeks. Regulations there allowed two fish of any size to be creel per day. Also, the season opened about 45 days earlier than the catch-and-release section and that portion of the river above Yellowstone Lake. In recent years, fisherman use has grown in this section to 16% of the river's total use. Estimates indicate angler-days were approximately 4,000 in 1976, 6,900 in 1977, 7,300 in 1978 and 6,300 in 1979. In 1979, 14,200 angler-hours resulted in landing and creel rates of 1.8 and 0.3 fish/hr, respectively. Cutthroat trout dominated the catch, but rainbows, hybrids, brooks, browns and mountain whitefish were also reported. The average size of fish landed and creel was 307 mm (12.1 in) and 318 mm (12.5 in), respectively. Satisfaction indices for overall satisfaction, numbers and sizes landed (84%, 75% and 76%, respectively) were about average for the Yellowstone River and above average for the Park.

The section of the Yellowstone River in the Grand Canyon, which now sustains about 3.1% of the river's total use, has few access points and the hike from the river is rigorous. Regulations in effect are the same as those described for the Tower Junction segment. In 1979, 1,300 angler-days and 3,100 angler-hours were expended, landing 8,700 trout. This translated into a landing rate of 2.8 trout/hr, one of the highest in the Park. About 1,100 trout were creel in 1979, yielding a creel rate of 0.4 fish/hr.

The mean size of trout landed and creeled was 297 mm (11.7 in) and 310 mm (12.2 in), respectively. Overall satisfaction was rated at 86%, while satisfaction with numbers and sizes landed was 92% and 72%, respectively.

The upper Black Canyon reach of the Yellowstone between Knowles Falls and Little Buffalo Creek sustained 1,200 angler-days and 3,100 angler-hours in 1979. An estimated 5,100 fish were landed and 500 creeled resulting in landing and creel rates of 1.6 and 0.25 fish/hr, respectively. In recent years, about two-thirds of the catch were cutthroat trout, followed by rainbows (and hybrids) and mountain whitefish. The average sizes of fish landed and creeled were 323 mm (12.7 in) and 338 mm (13.3 in), respectively. Satisfaction indices for overall satisfaction, numbers and sizes landed (78%, 78% and 81%, respectively) were excellent and slightly above the parkwide average. There have been no obvious changes in angler use, effort and success values in recent years on this reach of the river.

In the lower Black Canyon section (between the north Park boundary and Knowles Falls), an estimated 800 angler-days and 1,700 angler-hours were spent fishing. Since this reach is popular with local anglers who do not return VFR cards as commonly as non-locals, these values may be conservative. Although measurements from this segment vary widely from year to year (probably due to small sample sizes), estimated landing and creel rates of 0.6 and 0.1 fish/hr, respectively, are much below average for the Yellowstone River. In recent years, cutthroat, rainbow (and hybrid) trout and mountain whitefish were caught in about equal numbers; a few brown and brook trout were also reported. The average size of fish landed and creeled, at 310 mm (12.2 in) and 325 mm (12.8 in), respectively, has not varied significantly in the past five years. Satisfaction indices (overall 100%, sizes and numbers 88%) were above average for the Yellowstone River and for Park fisheries. Considering the limitations of the sample sizes, it would appear that angler use and success measures for this segment have been relatively stable in recent years.

The Yellowstone River inlet to Yellowstone Lake is remote and is only accessible to fishermen in mid-to late summer and fall. The fishing season opens on July 15th, and the stream has the same restrictions as Yellowstone Lake: catch-and-release only, except that two fish may be kept per day if under 13 inches (330 mm) length. Although we estimate 300 angler-days and 900 angler-hours were expended in 1979, small sample sizes hamper analysis on this portion. Approximately 500 trout were landed and 75 creeled yielding landing and creel rates of 0.6 and 0.1 trout/hr, respectively. Cutthroat trout were the only species caught and averaged 411 mm (16.2 in) landed and 457 mm (18.0 in) creeled. Satisfaction indices were all below average; overall satisfaction was 71%, and satisfaction with both numbers and sizes was 57%.

MADISON RIVER

The Madison River has a notoriety among fishermen shared by few trout streams in America. Historically, the river supported robust populations of Montana westslope cutthroat trout, Montana grayling and mountain whitefish. By 1915, however, Loch Leven trout were reported as being abundant, and by the early 1930's cutthroat trout were believed to be extinct and the grayling dwindling. Between 1929 and 1955, the river was heavily stocked with rainbow trout, brown trout and grayling. Presently, the river is dominated by wild, self-sustaining brown and rainbow (or hybrid) trout and whitefish. Because of species differences, we consider this fishery to have two segments: above and below 7-mile bridge.

Recent angling regulations have changed from a five-fish creel limit, no size restriction in the 1950's to a two-fish limit, 16 inch (406 mm) minimum size limit in 1970. Grayling have been included under catch-and-release only rules since 1969. The Madison has been restricted to fly fishing only since 1950.

A total of 16,500 angler-days were expended on the Madison River in 1979 (Table 4). This use, as well as the other estimates of effort and angling success, are very similar to values observed throughout the 1970's. The pattern of angler use on the river in recent years has been highly variable and was occasionally independent of the trend in parkwide angler-days. From 1969 through 1976, use generally declined, but sharp increases were noted in 1977, 1978, and 1979. Use in the 1970's is about 26% less than that measured in the 1950's (Benson et al 1959) and about 35% less than was estimated for 1969 (Dean and Mills 1970). In terms of angling success (landing rates), present values are approximately one-third higher than measured in prior studies.

Over one-half (54%) of the fishing use occurs between May 28 and August 31 on what we believe to be a resident river population made up largely of brown trout (44%), rainbow trout (17%) and whitefish (39%). In contrast, 46% of the fishing use takes place in September - October and mostly affects spawning migrations of these species from Hebgen Lake. We believe that variation observed in fishery statistics over the years may be largely due to the influence of the fall fishery. The extended Indian summer lasting through September and October largely, though not completely, delayed the spawning runs from Hebgen Lake until after the season had ended.

Efforts to restore the native westslope cutthroat trout were initiated in 1979. The reader is referred to the section on native species restoration for a detailed account.

FIREHOLE RIVER

The Firehole River has received national attention as it is considered by many fishermen to be a premier trout fishery. Since the cessation of stocking activities in 1955, the fishery has survived heavy angler use because of healthy wild trout populations and restrictive angling regulations.

Geothermal influences, waterfalls, fish species composition and angling use combine to suggest the need to divide the stream into three distinct fishery segments. Above Kepler Cascades (14.5 km or 9.0 mi) there is little geothermal water and the Firehole is much like the typical mountain stream common to the region. Brook trout dominate this section, although numbers of brown trout are also present. Below Kepler Cascades, heated water inputs, often exceeding 30° C (86° F), are present throughout the 38.6 km (24 mi) reach downstream to the Firehole Falls. Rainbow trout dominate here, although a substantial brown trout population exists above Midway Geyser Basin. From the Firehole Falls to the confluence of the Gibbon River (2.4 km or 1.5 mi), the stream loses a significant amount of the heat, and the fish population is primarily rainbow and brown trout and mountain whitefish. In all, there are about 62.8 km (39 mi) of fishable water in the mainstream.

Fly fishing only has been in effect since 1950. Since 1970, regulations have stipulated a 16 inch minimum size limit and a two-fish creel limit. Prior to 1970, five fish were allowed with no size limit. Several substantial areas in the vicinity of dangerous or fragile thermal features and a culinary water supply intake are closed to all fishing.

In 1979, the river fishery sustained about 8,100 anglers who fished 14,200 angler-days and 35,100 angler-hours (Table 4). Landing and creel rates, at 0.62 and 0.02 fish/hr, respectively, indicated 21,700 total fish were landed and 800 creeled. Of the total fish landed, 59% were reportedly rainbow trout, 37% brown trout and 4% brook trout; small numbers of grayling and whitefish were also reported. The size of the average fish landed was 295 mm (11.6 in) in 1979.

In the nine years since the present regulation was put into effect, angling use, effort and success have varied little; values reported for 1979 closely reflect the averages.

GIBBON RIVER

The Gibbon River originates in the hills surrounding Grebe Lake. It flows southwest for 60.4 km (37.5 mi) where it joins the Firehole River creating the Madison River. In terms of biomass production, Seamons (1940) considered the Gibbon as one of the least productive streams in the Park; this is probably because it is the only major stream that is acidic. Historically, the river below Gibbon Falls had populations of Montana westslope cutthroat trout, Montana grayling and mountain whitefish; above the falls, the only fish present was the mottled sculpin. Although the species composition varies widely in the stream, in recent years, brown and brook trout have dominated the fishery (43% and 40%, respectively), followed by rainbow trout (16%), grayling (0.5%) and whitefish (0.1%). For fishery purposes, the river is divided into five sections which are separated by barriers to upstream fish movement. The upper section extends from Grebe Lake downstream to Little Gibbon Falls and primarily has rainbow trout and grayling. The next section meanders through Virginia Meadows to Virginia Cascades and sustains principally a brook trout population. The Norris-Elk Park section extends between the Cascades and the Gibbon River Rapids. Here, brook trout dominate, although some rainbow and brown trout are found. The Gibbon Meadows segment flows downstream from the rapids to Gibbon Falls and is primarily a brown trout stream, although brook trout and grayling occur in small numbers. The last segment extends from Gibbon Falls to a junction with the Firehole River. This reach is dominated by brown trout although, brook and rainbow trout, whitefish and grayling are found in small numbers.

Since 1970, regulations for the section below Gibbon Falls have stipulated fly fishing only and a 16 inch minimum size, two-fish bag limit; above the Falls, two fish of any size may be creeled. The few grayling in the stream are protected under catch-and-release only regulations.

In 1979, the river hosted 7,300 anglers who fished 10,900 angler-days and 20,800 angler-hours (Table 4). In recent years, use and effort has been 50% higher than that measured in the 1950's, although all fishery values have been fairly stable throughout the 1970's.

A program to restore the native westslope cutthroat trout was initiated in 1979. For an account of those activities, the reader is referred to the section on native species restoration.

LEWIS LAKE

Lewis Lake is the third largest lake in the Park (1,099 ha or 2,716 acres) and has been popular with fishermen for many years. The lake has roadside access, a boat-launching ramp and an adjacent 100-unit campground. Considering the size and the fish population of the lake, it is surprising that it has generated little research or management interest in the past.

The lake was historically fishless because of several barriers downstream on the Lewis River (Jordan 1891). It was first stocked with brown and lake trout in 1890. As a result, both species have thrived and given the lake a reputation for quality angling. Prior to 1940, grayling and cutthroat trout were also stocked but have apparently failed to survive. Brook trout are captured periodically and probably originate from lake tributaries and the outlet. Redside shiners and Utah chubs are abundant. These two species, which were probably introduced by live-bait fishermen, presently provide a forage base for predacious brown and lake trout.

Prior to 1973, a five-fish creel limit was allowed on the lake. Since 1973, a two-fish bag limit has been in force. Bait fishing has been prohibited on the lake since 1969.

In 1979, 9,300 angler-days were expended and fishermen landed and creeled 12,900 and 4,000 trout, respectively (Table 4). Angler use was the highest measured since the early 1970's. Measures of success and satisfaction, however, were within the range observed in the past decade.

Brown trout made up about 66% of the trout landed and averaged 384 mm (15.1 in) in length. Lake trout made up the majority of the remainder and averaged 439 mm (17.3 in).

Increased use in a year when the total parkwide anglers declined may indicate a major change on this fishery and should be closely monitored in the future.

SHOSHONE LAKE

Shoshone Lake is the second largest lake in the Park (3,258 ha or 8,050 acres) and may be the largest lake without road access in the contiguous United States. For this reason and because of the fine trout fishery it produces, the lake is popular with horsemen, backpackers and canoe enthusiasts. It is the most popular back-country location in Yellowstone Park.

The upper Lewis River, including Shoshone Lake, was originally fishless (Jordan 1891). The Loch Leven brown trout and Great Lakes strain of lake trout were planted in the lake in 1890 and flourished. Although brook trout were planted and are established in the streams in the drainage, Park records do not disclose any further stocking of the lake itself. The Utah chub was reported in the lake by 1965 and is assumed to have been introduced by anglers as live bait. The species is presently thought to provide a prey base for the robust lake-brown trout predator population.

Current regulations for the fishery, which were first implemented in 1973, specify that two fish of any size may be creel per day. In 1961, boats were restricted to hand-propelled craft only, and bait fishing was prohibited in 1969.

During 1979, 2,800 anglers fished 8,900 angler-days on the lake, landed 12,500 trout and creel 3,400 (Table 4). Lake trout averaging 493 mm (19.4 in) dominated the catch (85%), followed by brown trout (8% and 462 mm (18.2 in)) and brook trout (7% and 277 mm (10.9 in)).

Angling use and effort increased in 1979 over 1978. The trend through the 1970's has been one of general increase. This increase is cause for concern and should be monitored closely. Excessive harvests from this quality fishery will significantly degrade the delicate predator-prey balance in the lake.

SLOUGH CREEK

Slough Creek has a reputation among many anglers for being one of the finest cutthroat trout streams in North America. The stream originates in the Beartooth Mountains (Gallatin National Forest), Montana. Approximately one-half of the stream (26 km or 16.2 mi) meanders through the northeast corner of the Park. The stream is believed to have pure cutthroats above the cascades located near Slough Creek campground. Rainbow and rainbow x cutthroat hybrids occur with cutthroat trout below the cascades.

In recent years, a variety of fishing regulations have been in effect. For many years prior to 1970, there was a five trout creel limit. In 1970, the limit was modified to read five fish, of which no more than three could be cutthroats. During 1971-72, a three fish bag and 14 inch minimum size limit was in practice. Since 1973, catch-and-release only regulations have been in effect.

In 1979, an estimated 4,400 fishermen spent 7,700 angler-days and 21,700 angler-hours on the stream (Table 4). Anglers landed a total of 34,600 trout and creeled (illegally) 300 trout, yielding landing and creel rates of 1.6 and 0.01 trout/hour, respectively. The average length of trout landed was 348 mm (13.7 in). Eighty-eight percent of the fishermen reporting landed one or more trout.

Angler use has climbed from a low of 3,500 days in 1974 to the present level of 7,700. Despite these increases, measures of angling success remain high and progress towards restoring a historical age-size structure in the population continues. The effects of increases in angling use, if they continue in the future, will be watched with considerable interest.

LAMAR RIVER

The Lamar River meanders 106 km (66 mi) through a broad, glacially-scoured valley. Substantial lateral movement across the flood plain and considerable sediment discharge differentiate it from most of the other streams in Yellowstone. The stream is one of the largest and longest in the Park but has, in the past, been considered a mediocre to poor fishery (Arnold and Sharpe 1967).

Biologically there are probably three distinct fishery segments. From its confluence with the Yellowstone River upstream to a partial fish barrier in the Lamar Canyon; from Lamar Canyon upstream to a fish barrier near Flint Creek; and above Flint Creek. The lowest segment is dominated by cutthroat trout although rainbow and hybrid trout are also common. The middle reach sustains cutthroat trout almost exclusively, but there are sporadic rainbow and rainbow x cutthroat hybrid trout taken. Above the barrier, near Flint Creek, only native cutthroat trout are believed to exist.

In terms of fishing regulations, the river has two segments. The lower one-third, from its mouth to Cache Creek has good road access and is catch-and-release fishing only; above Cache Creek, the back-country portion, two fish of any size may be creel per day.

During 1979, the river hosted 3,000 anglers who spent 5,200 angler-days and 12,100 angler-hours fishing (Table 4). Fishermen landed approximately 24,400 trout and creel 600 which produced landing and creel rates of 2.0 and 0.05 trout/hr, respectively. Cutthroat trout made up 92% of the fish caught and averaged 297 mm (11.7 in) in length. Eighty-six percent of the anglers fishing the river landed one or more trout.

Unlike other streams placed under catch-and-release in 1973, fisherman use on the Lamar River is greater than the period before the restriction and shows increases almost annually. In spite of these increases, measures of angler success and quality remain high and the river continues to be one of the finest fisheries in the Park.

SODA BUTTE CREEK

Soda Butte Creek is a major tributary to the Lamar River in the north-east portion of the Park. Access is provided by a paved road which parallels the entire length of the stream. It has been a popular fishery for over 100 years. In the late 1800's, the stream had a reputation for fast-fishing and large trout. By 1931, the fishery was reportedly "fair to poor". Since at least 1941, pollution associated with gold mine tailings at the abandoned McLaren Mill site at Cooke City has had deleterious effects at least as far down on the stream as the confluence with Pebble Creek. Arnold and Sharpe (1967) reported finding a sparse trout population. Enriching nutrients from Cooke City and Silver Gate sewage further confuses the biology of the stream. The present trout population is thought to be over 90% cutthroats, 8% rainbows and hybrids, with a few brook trout. Regulations on Soda Butte Creek allow for two fish per day of any size to be creeled.

During 1979, about 2,000 anglers spent 4,100 angler-days and 9,400 angler-hours fishing the stream (Table 4). An estimated 11,800 trout were landed and 1,800 creeled, resulting in landing and creel rates of 1.3 and 0.2 trout/hr, respectively. The average sizes of trout landed and creeled were 267 mm (10.5 in) and 290 mm (11.4 in), respectively. Seventy-one percent of the anglers fishing the stream landed one or more trout.

Angler use on this stream was high in the early 1970's, fell in 1974-75 and has been increasing since that time. Measures of success continue above average for Park waters though the small average size of trout landed is indicative of high angler-caused mortality.

In order to cure a variety of ills (see Jones et al 1979), Soda Butte Creek is slated to fall under catch-and-release regulations in 1980. These restrictions are expected to restore this population to its historic potential and materially improve sport fishing.

GARDNER RIVER

The Gardner River originates in the Gallatin Range in the northwestern section of the Park. The stream flows southeast adding influents from Fawn, Panther, Indian and Obsidian Creeks and then flows north to the Yellowstone River.

The river was historically barren of fishlife above Osprey Falls and had a cutthroat trout - mountain whitefish population below. Presently, only brook trout are believed to exist above the falls, although the fishery below is made up of rainbow, brown and brook trout plus a few cutthroat trout and mountain whitefish. The total fishable water is approximately 50 km (31 mi). There are two distinct fishery segments on the river: a 12.9 km (8 mi) section below Osprey Falls and a 37.1 km (23 mi) reach above the falls. Road access to much of the lower segment and a portion of the upper helps to make this stream very popular. In recent years, regulations have stipulated a daily limit of five fish (three of which must be brook trout) above Osprey Falls and a two-fish bag limit below. Children 12 years and under are allowed to use worms as bait on the Gardner River.

During 1979, an estimated 2,600 anglers spent 3,800 angler-days and 6,500 angler-hours fishing the river (Table 4). Approximately two-thirds of the use and effort occurred on the segment below Osprey Falls. Overall, 86,000 fish were landed and 1,700 creeled representing landing and creel rates of 1.3 and 0.26 fish/hr, respectively. Seventy-three percent of the anglers fishing the Gardner River landed one or more trout. All species combined averaged 256 mm (10.1 in), which is below the mean for Park fisheries.

Angler use in 1979 declined precipitously from that measured in 1977-78, although measures of angling quality and success were within the range observed in recent years. Past years have shown that use and pressure on the river is highly variable. Part of the reason for the decline was undoubtedly the overall parkwide reduction in fishing use; however, the fall brown trout spawning run, which attracts many fishermen, did not materialize in great numbers until after the season ended and may have been a factor.

LEWIS RIVER

The Lewis River begins at Shoshone Lake, flows south through Lewis Lake over Lewis Falls and courses down through Lewis Canyon to join the Snake River near the South Entrance. We recognize five distinct fishery segments on this stream (the channel between Lewis and Shoshone Lakes has fishery characteristics quite unlike the remainder of the Lewis River and is treated as a separate fishery elsewhere in this report); from the outlet of Lewis Lake to Lewis Falls; from the falls to the head of Lewis Canyon; the nearly inaccessible segment through Lewis Canyon and that portion near the mouth of the river near South Entrance.

Fishing regulations in effect since 1973 from Lewis Lake downstream to Lewis Falls have stipulated a two-fish bag of any size. Below Lewis Falls, catch-and-release only rules have been in effect during this same period.

During 1979, 1,900 anglers spent 2,800 angler-days and 5,600 angler-hours fishing the river (Table 4). An estimated 4,900 trout were caught and 200 creeled yielding landing and creel rates of 0.9 and 0.04 trout/hr, respectively. Brown trout were most common in the catch (49%), followed by brook trout (38%), cutthroat trout (10%) and lake trout (0.7%). The average size of all trout landed was 267 mm (10.5 in), although the mean creeled size was 348 mm (13.7 in). Fifty-seven percent of the anglers fishing the river landed one or more trout.

Most of the fishing use occurs on the catch-and-keep segment above Lewis Falls and the catch-and-release portion that parallels the road. Fishery statistics for the entire river and for the catch-and-release segment are very similar to those measured in 1977 and 1978.

INDIAN CREEK

Indian Creek originates in the snowfields of Mt. Holmes and flows north-easterly for 21.6 km (13.4 mi) before joining the Gardner River. A portion of the creek is diverted by canal to Panther Creek to serve the domestic water supply needs of Mammoth Hot Springs. The stream's close proximity to the Mammoth-Norris Road and to a large campground accounts for its fishing popularity. Indian Creek was originally barren of fish because of Osprey Falls on the Gardner River. Plants of brook trout were made as early as 1889, and this species thrives today. Up to five fish may be creeled from Indian Creek if three or more are brook trout.

In 1979, an estimated 1,400 anglers spent 2,400 angler-days and 4,100 angler-hours fishing the creek (Table 4). Fishermen landed 5,400 trout and creeled 1,200 yielding landing and creel rates of 1.3 and 0.3 trout/hr, respectively. There was little difference in the average size of brook trout landed and creeled (230 mm or 9.1 in). Two-thirds (67%) of the anglers fishing the stream caught one or more brook trout.

There has been little change in the characteristics of this fishery in recent years.

NEZ PERCE CREEK

Nez Perce Creek is the largest tributary to the Firehole River. For 24 km (15 mi), the stream meanders through wide, open meadows dotted with acidic, geothermal seeps and springs. Unlike the Firehole River, geothermal activity is concentrated in the upstream section. Consequently, above the confluence with Cowan Creek, 20 km (12.3 mi) from the mouth, the stream does not support fishlife because of acid conditions and high temperatures. Brown, rainbow and brook trout appear to be most abundant in the lower one-half of the creek. This same section, including the mouth, is easily accessible and is the segment of greatest popularity. Current regulations specify that two fish of any size may be creeled per day.

During 1979, an estimated 1,200 anglers spent 1,600 angler-days and 3,200 angler-hours fishing the creek (Table 4). Approximately 1,300 trout were landed and 300 creeled, yielding landing and creel rates of 0.4 and 0.08 trout/hr, respectively. The average size of trout landed and creeled was 287 mm (11.3 in) and 330 mm (13.0 in), respectively. Only forty-one percent of the fishermen on the stream landed one or more trout.

Values of angler use, effort, and success were similar to those measured since 1973. Nez Perce Creek continues to be one of the poorest fisheries in the Park according to the generally accepted measures of quality (Table 4).

HEART LAKE

At 870 ha (2,150 acres), Heart Lake is the fourth largest lake in Yellowstone and contains the most diverse fish population in the Park. Seven of the eight species collected from Heart Lake in recent years were endemic to the drainage; only the lake trout is not native. Cutthroat trout, lake trout and mountain whitefish are common in the catch, and rainbow and brown trout have been reported from the lake but not confirmed. Although the lake is basically oligotrophic, it appears to be the most productive of the four large oligotrophic lakes in the Park.

Heart Lake is accessible only by trail, the shortest being about 12.9 km (8 mi) long. The cutthroat trout has been protected since 1974 under catch-and-release only regulations to help restore their declining numbers. For the remaining species in the lake, the daily creel limit is two fish.

During 1979, an estimated 500 anglers spent 1,500 angler-days and 3,400 angler-hours fishing the lake (Table 4). Approximately 4,100 fish were landed and 800 creeled. Landing and creel rates were 1.2 and 0.2 fish per hour, respectively.

Between 1973 and 1979, lake trout made up 50% of the fish landed followed by cutthroat trout (43%) and mountain whitefish (7%). The majority of trout caught by shore fishermen were cutthroat trout while the majority caught by boat fishermen were lake trout. In 1979, the average sizes of fish landed and creeled were 455 mm (17.9 in) and 498 mm (19.6 in), respectively. Two-thirds (67%) of the anglers fishing Heart Lake landed one or more fish.

Angling use and effort, the number of fish landed and creeled and the rates of success were significantly higher in 1979 than the six previous years. The increase in use is surprising in light of the reduced number of anglers entering the Park in 1979.

LEWIS-SHOSHONE CHANNEL

The channel between Lewis and Shoshone Lake is approximately 6.3 km (3.9 mi) long. Though considered to be the uppermost part of the Lewis River, it has few characteristics in common with the river below Lewis Lake and is separated in this report because of its distinctive fishery. The river has a reputation of excellent trophy fishing, a result of brown trout spawning migrations in the channel during the fall. Prior to 1973, three fish per day were allowed. Current regulations stipulate a two-fish daily creel limit of any size.

The pattern of angler use since 1971 suggests a general increase. The increase appears to be somewhat independent of fluctuations in parkwide angler use data indicating growing popularity of the fishery. Part of the increase would occur as a by-product of the extraordinary rise in the use at Shoshone Lake (see Shoshone Lake this report), but the major share is undoubtedly due to the increasing reputation of the fall fishery.

In 1979, results for the season indicated that about 800 anglers fished 1,500 angler-days and 3,900 angler-hours on the channel (Table 4). Approximately 2,000 trout were landed and 500 creeled at rates of 0.5 and 0.12 fish/hr, respectively. Brown trout made up 91% of the fish landed, followed by lake trout (9%) and a few brook trout. The average size of fish landed and creeled was 452 mm (17.8 in). About two-thirds (67%) of the anglers fishing the channel landed one or more trout.

In 1979, about 75% of the use and effort occurred during September and October. Because of the summer-like weather experienced during those months, the fall brown trout run was somewhat delayed, which probably accounts for the poorer success values observed compared to prior years.

TROUT LAKE

Trout Lake, a small (5.1 ha or 12.5 a) and popular lake located in the northeastern portion of the Park, is especially favored by local anglers. Historically, the lake supported an indigenous cutthroat trout population but efforts in the 1930's to make it a source of rainbow trout eggs resulted in a population of hybrids. This fishery is noted for the frequency of trophy-sized trout in the catch. In recent years, regulations have allowed two fish of any size to be creeled per day.

Angler use since 1973 has shown an increasing trend and appears to have at least doubled in the past 10-15 years. Trout Lake continues to be the most heavily fished lake in the Park, even though estimates are considered to be conservative due to suspected poor VFR returns by local anglers. In recent years, trout harvests have been excessive averaging at least 27 kg/ha (30 lbs/acre). In 1976, we recommended a program to shift the species composition back to cutthroat trout while maintaining normal sport fishing activities (Jones et al 1977). We continue to advocate that program, although progress is restricted by limited money and manpower, and by a lack of significant local support. In 1979, the fishing season was moved from May 28 to June 15, to give the spawning population more protection.

During 1979, an estimated 900 anglers spent 1,400 angler-days and 3,500 angler-hours fishing the lake (Table 4). Expanded estimates indicated approximately 1,600 were landed and 700 creeled. Landing and creel rates were 0.5 and 0.19 trout/hr, respectively. Trout landed averaged 389 mm (15.3 in) and those creeled 409 mm (16.1 in). Approximately 57% of anglers fishing the lake landed one or more trout.

Angler use and effort declined slightly but was still higher than most years in the 1970's. The harvest of trout, however, at 700, was the highest number ever measured reaffirming the potential overfishing problem on the lake.

BECHLER RIVER

Located in the southwest corner of Yellowstone Park, the Bechler River flows approximately 33 km (20 mi) before joining the Falls River. The river is moderately large and especially popular with residents of eastern Idaho; however, little data regarding its fishery have ever been obtained. Although accessible by pack trail only, the river has been the site of increasing use in the past twenty years. For fishery purposes, three distinct segments are recognized: from the river's confluence with the Falls River to Bechler Falls; from Bechler Falls to Colonnade Falls (including Bechler Meadows) and from Colonnade Falls to Three Rivers Junction. Fishing regulations in recent years have allowed two fish of any size to be creel per day, although the waters above Colonnade Falls became catch-and-release only in 1979.

In past years, 80 to 90% of the total angling use on the river occurred below Colonnade Falls, mostly in the Bechler Meadow region. This aspect did not change in 1979 as a result of the catch-and-release regulations.

During 1979, expanded fishery estimates for the river were 700 anglers, 1,300 angler-days and 3,000 angler-hours (Table 4). Approximately 3,300 trout were landed and 800 creel with landing and creel rates of 1.1 and 0.3 trout/hr, respectively. The average size of trout landed and creel was 292 mm (11.5 in).

Angler use and effort declined precipitously in 1979 to one of the lowest levels measured in the 1970's. The new catch-and-release regulation undoubtedly played a role in the decline though the general decrease parkwide probably contributed. The resurgence in the landing and creel rates measured in 1979 was likely the result of the reduced fisherman activity.

GALLATIN RIVER

Located in the northwest corner of Yellowstone, the Gallatin River headwaters in the Bannock-Three Rivers Peak area and flows for 51 km (31.9 mi) before exiting the Park. Approximately one-half of the river parallels U.S. Highway 191, and the other half is "back-country" and accessible by the Bighorn Pass pack trail. Native fishes in the river included the west-slope cutthroat trout, Montana grayling and mountain whitefish, although this assemblage has been severely modified. Current regulations stipulate that no more than five fish can be creeled per day (of any size) of which three must be brown or brook trout; however, the presence of brook trout in the drainage has not been documented.

During 1979, approximately 500 anglers spent 1,200 angler-days and 2,200 angler-hours on the stream (Table 4). In recent years, about 90% of the use occurred along the roadside section. An estimated 1,500 fish were landed and 500 creeled which gave overall landing and creel rates of 0.7 and 0.2 fish/hr, respectively. Fish landed averaged 282 mm (11.1 in) and those creeled 302 mm (11.9 in). Only 53% of the anglers fishing the stream landed one or more fish.

Since 1973, the Gallatin River has experienced a slow but steady increase in angler use and effort. It did not show the decline in 1973-74 or in 1979 observed in parkwide angler-days. Reasons for this are unknown but may reflect new developments in the Gallatin Canyon outside the Park.

The collection of basic aquatic data is desirable from the Gallatin River drainage and should be programmed as soon as possible. Simple hydrographic mapping and species composition information is especially needed.

RIDDLE LAKE

Riddle Lake is a moderately large (111 ha or 274 acres), back-country water located approximately 4 km (2.5 mi) south of the West Thumb of Yellowstone Lake and 3.2 km (2 mi) east of the South Entrance Road. The lake's access is by foot trail only. Historically, cut-throat trout gained entry from Yellowstone Lake via Solution Creek. Non-indigenous longnose suckers and redbreast shiners probably entered Riddle Lake by the same route.

The lake has been included under a 13 inch maximum size, two-fish creel limit since 1974. This is one year longer than the same regulations have been in force on Yellowstone Lake.

During 1979, an estimated 800 anglers spent 1,100 angler-days and 2,200 angler-hours on Riddle Lake (Table 4). Fishermen landed approximately 1,600 trout and creeled 600, yielding landing and creel rates of 0.7 and 0.3 fish per hour, respectively. Trout landed averaged 361 mm (14.2 in) in length and those in the creel 340 mm (13.4 in). Over 83% of the anglers fishing the lake landed one or more trout.

An analysis of fisherman use, effort, harvest and success data from 1973 through 1979 suggests some significant changes since the implementation of the maximum size regulation in 1974. The pattern of increasing angler-day use since the maximum size rule was instituted is interesting as it contrasts sharply with the trend of parkwide angler-days. Overall, the effects of the regulation on the fishery are very similar to that on Yellowstone Lake.

FALLS RIVER

Originating above Beula Lake, the Falls River flows for 49 km (31 mi) paralleling the south boundary of Yellowstone Park. Numerous falls and cascades, for which the river was named, are often barriers to upstream fish movement. Although it is known that the upper Falls River was originally barren of fishlife, little additional information regarding the biology of the stream or its fishery exists. Present fishes are the result of cutthroat plants from Yellowstone Lake in its upper reaches and cutthroat and rainbow trout plants in the lower section. We believe there are three distinct fishery segments: 1. between the Park boundary and Cave Falls, 2. Cave Falls to the unnamed falls at the 2,200 m (7,220 ft) elevation, and 3. between this falls and Beula Lake.

There is a single road access near the mouth; however, much of the stream is accessible from the old Reclamation Road by relatively short hikes. Current regulations stipulate that no more than two fish of any size may be creeled per day below the falls located at elevation 2,200 m (7,200 ft), and catch-and-release only fishing above. The catch-and-release regulation was first implemented in 1979, and included Beula and Hering Lakes.

During 1979, the total number of fishermen on the river was estimated at 600 (Table 4). Angler-days and hours were 1,000 and 2,200, respectively, and diminished with each succeeding upstream segment. Approximately 3,600 trout were landed and 400 creeled, yielding landing and creel rates of 1.6 and 0.2 trout/hr, respectively. The average size of landed and creeled trout in 1979 was 272 mm (10.7 in). Approximately 84% of anglers fishing the stream landed one or more trout.

Angler use fell sharply in 1978 following five years of steady increase. Use in 1979 recovered somewhat over 1978, which was somewhat surprising in light of the first year of catch-and-release fishing on the upper reaches. Measures of fishing quality and success were within the range observed since 1973.

GREBE LAKE

At an elevation of 2,438 m (8,000 ft), Grebe Lake is the uppermost lake in the headwaters of the Gibbon River drainage. This large (63 ha or 156 a) back-country lake is located on the Solfatara Plateau near the center of Yellowstone Park. Since the lake is only 5.6 km (3.5 mi) from the road, it is a popular day-use fishery. Although originally fishless, it was planted early in this century and has long been the most popular Montana grayling fishery in the Park. Additionally, large cutthroat x rainbow trout hybrids exist and are sought after by anglers. Montana grayling have been included under parkwide catch-and-release regulations since 1969. Two trout hybrids of any size can be legally creeled per day.

During 1979, 700 anglers spent 900 angler-days and 2,200 angler-hours fishing the lake (Table 4). Approximately 2,700 fish were landed and 300 creeled yielding landing and creel rates of 1.3 and 0.1 fish/hr, respectively. Grayling made up 88%, and hybrid trout 13%, of the fish landed in 1979. Hybrids landed averaged 343 mm (13.5 in). Landed Montana grayling had a mean length of 246 mm (9.7 in).

Analysis of angling use over the past 30 years suggests use is about double that estimated in the 1950's (Kruse 1957) and in 1969 (Dean and Mills 1970). Contrary to the trend observed for parkwide angler-days (Table 1), use since 1973 has shown a general pattern of decline, although results between individual years is highly variable. Other statistical fishery values are also variable. The 1.3 fish/hr landing rate in 1979 was the highest ever measured, although it has varied between 0.4 and 1.3 fish/hr, without apparent pattern, since 1973. The average length of grayling is also highly unpredictable and has wide fluctuations.

Small sample sizes may induce much of the variability observed in Grebe Lake statistics, although information from the logs from the Grebe Lake Hatchery (Ca. 1930-55) indicates extreme population fluctuations were common in the past. Factors influencing these fluctuations are unknown.

SNAKE RIVER

The Snake River headwaters and traverses for about 68 km (42 mi) in Yellowstone Park. To the Park section, roadside access is limited to a short section near the South Entrance, and over 90% of the angling pressure occurs between there and the Heart River. The remainder of the river in the Park is accessible by foot trails involving considerable distances. For unknown reasons, the Park segment of this river has never maintained the sport fishing reputation that is held by other comparable-sized streams in the area. In recent years regulations have stipulated that two fish of any size may be creeled per day.

During 1979, an estimated 600 anglers spent 900 angler-days and 1,400 angler-hours on the river (Table 4). Fishermen landed an estimated 1,100 fish and creeled 200 which yielded landing and creel rates of 0.7 and 0.1 fish/hr, respectively.

Fishes caught between 1973-78 included mountain whitefish (50%), cutthroat trout (34%), brown trout (15%) and lake trout (1%). A few rainbow and brook trout were also reported. All fish landed during this period averaged 292 mm (11.5 in) with 34% reportedly exceeding 304 mm (12 in) and 11% over 408 mm (16 in).

Unlike the trend in parkwide angler-days, use on the Snake River has shown a steady increase since 1973. Use declined in 1979 but was still nearly double that measured in 1973-74. Perhaps as a result of this, measures of success, particularly the landing rate, have been declining. The landing rate measured in 1979 was the lowest yet recorded. Although sample sizes are small, the average size of fish landed in 1979 was also the smallest measured since 1973.

SYLVAN LAKE

Sylvan Lake is located on the East Entrance Road near Sylvan Pass in the headwaters of the Clear Creek drainage. Because of roadside proximity, automobile pullouts and a picnic area, this small lake (11.4 ha or 28.2 a) has historically sustained greater angler use than most Park lakes its size. Regulations in recent years have allowed two fish of any size to be creeled per day. Because of the Natural Area management philosophy of protection of native species in native habitats, and an unreasonably high rate of angler exploitation, Sylvan Lake became a catch-and-release-only fishery in 1978. During the period from 1974 through 1977, fisherman use, effort, harvest and success measures suggested a rather stable, though mediocre, fishery. The average size of trout in the catch has also varied little. Very few experienced anglers (who have been the strongest supporters of catch-and-release rules) fished the lake. In future years, the lake should provide an interesting study of the effects of the regulation, since it is the Park's first roadside catch-and-release lake.

Before 1978, annual angler effort of 156 hours/ha (63 hrs/a) and the removal of trout (9.6 kg/ha or 8.6 lbs/a) were among the highest rates of exploitation in the Park. The average size of cutthroat trout landed was smaller than other Park lakes with similar productivity.

During 1979, an estimated 600 anglers spent 800 angler-days and 1,200 angler-hours fishing the lake (Table 4). Approximately 1,700 trout were landed and only 10 creeled yielding landing and creel rates of 1.4 and 0.01 trout/hr, respectively. The average size of trout landed was 10.5 in (267 mm). Approximately 77% of the anglers fishing the lake landed one or more trout.

Fishermen reported satisfaction with their overall fishing experience at 64%; satisfaction with the numbers of fish and sizes landed were 63% and 73%, respectively (Table 3). The average level of angler expertise for the lake was 1.73.

A comparison of the second year of catch-and-release fishing (1979) with the average of four prior years (1974-77) suggests the regulation has had the effect of reducing angler use and effort between one-third and one-half, increasing measures of success by two-thirds and boosting the average length of trout landed by 0.5 inches (50 mm).

PELICAN CREEK

Pelican Creek (83.7 km or 52 mi in length) is the second largest tributary to Yellowstone Lake and serves as an important spawning stream for the lake's cutthroat trout. The stream also sustains a resident cutthroat population. In 1978, following many years of two and three fish daily bag limits, the stream became catch-and-release only. The season did not open until July 15th, and the lowermost 3.2 km (2 mi) of stream was closed all season. Most of the fishing is back-country or walk-in day-use that takes place on a 29 km (18 mi) segment between the closed zone and the confluence with Raven Creek.

During 1979, an estimated 600 anglers spent 700 angler-days and 1,600 angler-hours fishing the stream (Table 5). Fishermen landed 2,900 trout and creeled (illegally) 80. Resultant landing and creel rates were 1.9 and 0.05 trout/hr, respectively. All fish caught were cutthroat trout which averaged 368 mm (14.5 in) landed and 452 mm (17.8 in) creeled.

Following the second year of catch-and-release fishing, Pelican Creek continues to sustain reduced effort and higher values for angling success.

CACHE CREEK

Cache Creek arises high in the Absaroka Range and flows southwesterly to a junction with the Lamar River. Although it is 6.4 km (4 mi) from the road, it is a popular day-use and overnight camping area, and as such, has had high levels of angling use. Cutthroat trout are native to this drainage and in recent years, regulations allowing two trout per day to be creeled have been in effect. Cache Creek is slated to become a catch-and-release only stream in 1980.

Since 1975, angler use on this stream has tripled, reaching over 700 angler-days in 1979 (Table 4). Fishermen landed and creeled 2,600 and 500 trout, respectively, in 1,300 hours effort. Landing and creel rates were 2.03 and 0.4 trout per hour. Harvest and success rates are within the range observed in recent years and are considered excellent, although the average size of trout landed was small (252 mm or 9.9 inches).

GRIZZLY LAKE

Grizzly Lake is a moderately large (55 ha or 136 a) back-country lake located in northwest Yellowstone Park. A short (3.2 km or 2 mi) trail to the lake begins north of Roaring Mountain on the Mammoth-Norris Road. The lake was historically fishless due to Osprey Falls on the Gardner River, but a population of small brook trout presently make up a fishery. Regulations in force in recent years provide for a five-fish creel limit if three or more are brook trout.

During 1979, an estimated 550 anglers spent 700 angler-days and 1,600 angler-hours fishing the lake (Table 5). Approximately 2,400 brook trout were landed and 900 creeled. Landing and creel rates of 1.5 and 0.6 trout/hr, respectively, were much above average for Park fisheries. The trout were small, averaging 241 mm (9.5 in) in the catch and 249 mm (9.8 in) in the creel.

Since measurements began in 1974, it appears that angler use has had a general trend upward, reaching new highs in 1977, 1978 and 1979. The increased use does not appear to have negatively influenced fishing as success (landing-creel rates) and satisfaction indices remain excellent. The average size of trout caught and creeled is small and has changed little in the past five years. Only about three trout in one thousand caught reportedly measure over 304 mm (12 in).

PEBBLE CREEK

Pebble Creek, a major tributary to Soda Butte Creek, headwaters in the Absaroka Mountain range and is a high velocity, high gradient subalpine stream. It flows for approximately 29 km (18 mi) and sustains an indigenous, pure population of cutthroat trout above a barrier near its mouth; cutthroat and rainbow x cutthroat hybrids are found below the barrier. The stream's angling popularity is primarily the result of the adjacent campground. Regulations in recent years have specified a daily creel limit of two fish.

During 1979, an estimated 510 anglers spent 700 angler-days and 1,100 angler-hours on the stream (Table 5). About 1,900 trout were landed and 400 creeled which yielded landing and creel rates of 1.6 and 0.4 trout/hr, respectively. Between 1973 and 1979, anglers reported landing 97% cutthroat trout with the remainder rainbow or hybrid trout. The average size landed for this period was 243 mm (9.6 in).

In 1980, Pebble Creek will become a catch-and-release-only stream. Its proximity to Soda Butte Creek may be highly significant; if there is interaction between the two streams, Pebble Creek may be important in helping restoration of Soda Butte Creek's meager fish population.

TOWER CREEK

Tower Creek, which drains an extensive watershed in the Washburn Range, flows for 31 km (19 mi) before meeting the Yellowstone River near Tower Junction. Tower Falls, the Roosevelt Lodge development and Tower Creek Campground account for much of this stream's popularity with visitors. There are actually two fishery segments, one above and one below Tower Falls; however, below the Falls, there are only about 1,000 ft (300 m) of stream before it enters the Yellowstone River. Consequently, both segments are combined for this discussion. Regulations governing fishing in recent years have stipulated a two fish daily creel limit.

During 1979, an estimated 440 anglers spent 650 angler-days and 850 angler-hours on the stream (Table 5). Approximately 1,500 trout were landed and 500 creeled which yielded landing and creel rates of 1.7 and 0.6 trout/hr, respectively. The average size of trout landed and creeled was 246 mm (9.7 in) and 254 mm (10.0 in), respectively.

Since 1973, fishery data from Tower Creek has shown variability due to small sample sizes. The angler use trend on the stream, however, is similar to the generally increasing use shown in the entire Park during the 1970's. Data from 1979 showed a continued high level of use. Measures of angling success and quality also continue to be excellent, although trout landed tend to be small.

OBSIDIAN CREEK

Located in the northwest portion of the Park, Obsidian Creek flows north for 25 km (15.8 mi) before joining Indian Creek, a tributary to the Gardner River. Upper reaches of this stream are significantly influenced by geothermal waters from the Roaring Mountain-Twin Lakes area and render parts of the stream fishless. Brook trout are established in the vicinity of Beaver Lake and become more common downstream. The creek parallels the Mammoth-Norris Road which accounts for its fishing popularity. Most angling activity occurs below the confluence of Straight Creek in the Willow Park area. Five fish of any size per day can be taken from the stream if three or more are brook trout; this is the only species known in the drainage.

During 1979, an estimated 350 anglers spent 470 angler-days and 900 angler-hours fishing the creek (Table 5). A landing rate of 2.7 trout/hr and a creel rate of 0.3 trout/hr produced an estimated 2,400 fish landed and 300 creeled. During 1979, 1,138 brook trout reported averaged 229 mm (9.0 in).

Although the sizes of trout caught are small, the landing rates are consistently above average. High landing rates and small trout are characteristic of Yellowstone's brook trout fisheries, of which Obsidian Creek is an excellent example.

LITTLE FIREHOLE RIVER

The Little Firehole River headwaters high on the Madison Plateau and flows east to join Iron Spring Creek, which in turn empties into the Firehole River near Biscuit Basin. We estimate that the stream has about 16 km (10 mi) of fishable water with populations of cutthroat, brook, rainbow and brown trout. Regulations in recent years have allowed two fish of any size to be creeled per day.

For 1977, 1978 and 1979, an annual average of 290 anglers spent 380 angler-days and 610 angler-hours on this stream (Table 5). An estimated 640 trout were landed and 120 creeled per year at rates of 1.1 and 0.2 trout per hour, respectively. The mean size of trout landed between 1973-79 was 252 mm (9.9 in).

The pattern of angler use on this stream through the 1970's has been upward and similar to the trend of back-country use throughout Yellowstone. Measures of sport fishing success and quality tend to be about average by Park standards.

BLACKTAIL PONDS

Adjacent to the road about 10.6 km (7 mi) east of Mammoth, the Blacktail Ponds have been popular fisheries since the late 1800's. These small ponds (3.56 ha or 8.8 a) originally held an indigenous cutthroat trout population (Jordan 1891), though brook trout stockings and heavy angling pressure have caused the cutthroat to become extinct from the drainage. Because of this, a cutthroat restoration project is planned for the drainage, to begin in 1980. Thus, the regulations in force for the entire Blacktail Deer Creek drainage will place the cutthroat under catch-and-release only rules while allowing five brook trout to be creeled per day.

During 1977, 1978 and 1979, an annual average of 230 anglers spent 400 angler-days and 620 angler-hours fishing the ponds (Table 5). Approximately 530 brook trout were landed and 220 creeled at rates of 0.85 and 0.36 trout/hr, respectively. Landed brook trout between 1973 and 1979 averaged 272 mm (10.7 in).

Angling use during the 1970's has had wide fluctuations possibly due to small sample sizes. Figures are thought to be conservative because the ponds are heavily used by local fishermen who do not return VFR cards at the same rate as visitors. Our conservative estimates, however, indicate that on a per-unit-area basis, these ponds are very heavily fished.

CLEAR CREEK

Clear Creek rises in the heights of the Absaroka Mountains, flows west to the eastern shore of Yellowstone Lake and, throughout its length, is used as an important spawning stream for the lake's cutthroat trout population. The fishery that exists on this stream appears to be wholly dependent on the spawning migration. In recent years, the fishing season has been short, though variable, but has generally been scheduled from late July through October. In 1979, two fish less than 330 mm (13.0 in) could be creeled per day.

In 1973-74, angling use averaged an estimated 4,000 angler-days per year. When Yellowstone Lake went to the 13.0 in (330 mm) maximum size restriction in 1975, use declined significantly and use on Clear Creek declined by a similar proportion. Angling success and the average size of trout landed remain very high (Table 5).

To protect spawning runs, the stream will be closed until August 1st, beginning in 1980. The 13 in (330 mm) maximum size, two fish daily creel will remain unchanged.

LAVA CREEK

Several kilometers southeast of Mammoth Hot Springs, Lava Creek joins the Gardner River. The creek issues from the Washburn Range in the Cook Peak area. Most of the stream is in the backcountry and is relatively inaccessible; however, it passes under the Mammoth-Tower road which, combined with a roadside picnic area, probably accounts for its popularity. Historically, Lava Creek sustained an indigenous cutthroat trout population. Repeated stockings of brook trout in the past established this species and the native cutthroat is presently extinct. Undine Falls, just downstream from the road, is a barrier to upstream fish migration. Above the falls only brook trout are found; below the falls brook, rainbow and brown trout are encountered. Current regulations specify that five fish may be creeled per day if three are brook trout.

Between 1977 and 1979, an average of 260 anglers spent 320 angler-days and 460 angler-hours fishing this stream (Table 5). Success, in terms of trout landed is good (1.23 trout/hr), though the average size of trout is small (less than 254 mm or 10 in). Larger trout, principally rainbow and brown trout, are found below the falls.

Future management should consider a program to restore cutthroat trout to this stream.

BOUNDARY CREEK

Boundary Creek originates on the Madison Plateau near the west boundary of the Park and serves as a major tributary to the Bechler River. A 16.9 km (10.5 mi) segment that meanders through the Bechler Meadows is fishable primarily for rainbow trout, although some cutthroat and hybrid trout are reported. Regulations for this stream in recent years have specified that two fish of any size may be creeled per day.

For 1977, 1978 and 1979, an annual average of 200 anglers spent 340 angler-days and 600 angler-hours on the stream (Table 5). Landing and creel rates of 1.2 and 0.3 fish per hour, respectively, indicated that approximately 730 trout were landed and 170 creeled. The average length of trout landed was 229 mm (9.0 in). Fishing success and quality indices are about average for the Park, although the trout are small.

HELLROARING CREEK

Hellroaring Creek drains an extensive area in the Gallatin National Forest. The lowermost 14.5 km (9 mi), which is located in the Park, enters the Yellowstone River at the head of the Black Canyon of the Yellowstone and is popular with day-use and overnight back-pack fishermen. The stream is thought to contain cutthroat trout, though anglers consistently report catching small numbers of rainbow, hybrid, brook and brown trout. Regulations in the 1970's have allowed two fish of any size to be creeled per day.

For 1977, 1978 and 1979, an annual average of 200 anglers spent 380 angler-days and 930 angler-hours fishing the stream (Table 5). An estimated 1,100 trout were landed and 220 creeled at rates of 1.2 and 0.2 trout per hour, respectively. The average size of trout landed was 260 mm (10.2 in).

During the 1970's, angler use has been fairly steady and similar to the estimates given for 1977-79. Measures of success fluctuate, probably due to small sample sizes, but are average by Park standards.

IRON SPRING CREEK

Iron Spring Creek is the second largest tributary to the Firehole River and, like the Firehole, is significantly influenced by geothermal waters. The mainstem and small unnamed tributaries are moderately heated by springs ranging from 12.8° C (55° F) to 31° C (120° F). The West Fork, which drains part of the Madison Plateau, is a typical cold, subalpine creek that compensates for the heated input and thereby provides suitable trout habitat in the mainstem. Iron Spring Creek is cooler than the Firehole River during midsummer and serves as a refuge for Firehole trout escaping very warm temperatures. There are about 13.2 km (7.8 mi) of stream, including tributary portions, that are inhabited by fishes, and these waters are treated here as a single fishery. Regulations in recent years have allowed a daily creel limit of two fish of any size.

During 1977, 1978, and 1979, an annual average of approximately 220 anglers spent 390 angler-days and 640 angler-hours fishing the creek (Table 5). An estimated 460 trout were landed and 100 creeled giving landing and creel rates of 0.7 and 0.2 trout/hr, respectively. Between 1973 - 1979, the average size of trout landed was 257 mm (10.1 in).

The angler use pattern since 1973 has generally followed the increasing trend of parkwide angler-days, reaching a high in 1978 and declining somewhat in 1979. Considering the small size of the stream and its short length, present use may be excessive, although the statistics for the stream are too variable to make definitive conclusions.

CASCADE LAKE

Cascade Lake is a moderately sized (14.6 ha or 36 acre) back-country lake near Canyon Village. The lake is the origin of Cascade Creek, a tributary to the Yellowstone River below Lower Falls, and is presently the primary culinary water supply for Canyon Village. The lake's close proximity to Canyon Village and Park roads (two trails each 4 km or 2.5 mi long) contributes to its popularity. Cascade Lake supports an introduced population of pure Yellowstone Lake cutthroat trout and a smaller population of Montana grayling. Grayling in the lake have been protected by parkwide catch-and-release-only regulations since 1969, and for many years, a creel limit of two fish of any size had been allowed for cutthroats. Beginning in 1978, the entire lake fishery was included under catch-and-release regulations to reduce one of the highest exploitation rates in the Park.

During 1979, an estimated 400 anglers spent 540 angler-days and 770 angler-hours on the lake (Table 5). Fishermen landed approximately 1,750 fish and creeled (illegally) 30. Landing and creel rates were 2.3 and 0.04 fish/hr., respectively. The average size of cutthroat trout and grayling landed during the year was 269 mm (10.6 in). Cutthroats made up 87% of the fish landed.

Since the lake fishery went totally to catch-and-release fishing in 1978, comparison of the first two years results with prior years is of interest. Contrasting 1978-79 with an average of five prior years (1973-77) suggests that the regulation change caused a significant decline in total use (-45%), total effort (-50%) and total fish creeled (-94%). Conversely, increases were noted with the landing rate (+51%) and total fish landed (+3%). The sizes of fish landed are larger as the percentage of landed fish over 14 in has doubled.

BLACKTAIL DEER CREEK

Headwatering in the Washburn Range in the northcentral portion of Yellowstone Park, Blacktail Deer Creek runs north to join the Yellowstone River in the Black Canyon. Despite a falls near the mouth, the stream historically contained a native cutthroat trout population. Heavy fishing and repeated stockings of brook trout depleted cutthroat stocks so that now only brook trout remain. Regulations in recent years have allowed a daily creel limit of five brook trout.

In 1977, 1978 and 1979, an average of 240 anglers spent approximately 300 angler-days and 560 angler-hours fishing this stream (Table 5). Landing and creel rates, averaging 1.6 and 0.5 trout per hour, respectively, were above average for Yellowstone's fisheries. Brook trout landed are universally small with few caught that are over 229 mm (9.0 in) in length.

A program to restore cutthroat trout to the drainage is scheduled to begin in 1980. Limits for brook trout will remain the same though the reintroduced cutthroat trout will be protected under catch-and-release only regulations.

FAN CREEK

Fan Creek rises in the Gallatin Mountain Range and is one of the principal tributaries to the Gallatin River. The length of the stream, except the mouth, lies in the back-country, although the Fawn Pass Trail parallels the stream for several miles. The stream is believed to have a relatively pure cutthroat trout population and a few mountain whitefish. Recent regulations have specified that five fish may be creeled per day if three or more are brook or brown trout.

Between 1977 and 1979, Fan Creek averaged 70 anglers per year who fished an estimated 300 angler-days and 800 angler-hours (Table 5). At 0.7 trout/hr, the landing rate was below average. Trout sizes are small, averaging 261 mm (10.3 in) in the catch, although larger fish have been reported.

Trout habitat is poor near the mouth of the stream and may explain the poor landing rates. Little is known of the character of the stream in the upper reaches.

BEULA LAKE

Beula Lake is a popular and sizable (43 ha or 107 a) lake located near Yellowstone's south boundary, high in the Falls River drainage. The trailhead to the lake is located on the old Reclamation Road in the Teton National Forest. Distance between the trailhead and the lake is only 4 km (2.5 mi). The lake has been heavily used in the past, and the cutthroat population showed signs of abuse. Consequently, the lake and its tributaries, as well as the Falls River above the falls at the 7,200 ft elevation, were placed under catch-and-release-only regulations in 1979.

Angler use declined about 31% in the first year of the regulation change but effort remained similar to the earlier years. The harvest of cutthroat trout declined from a pre-catch-and-release average of 260 trout per year down to virtually none (Table 5).

Interpretation of the Beula Lake statistics is hampered by small sample size and a suspicion that use on the lake is higher than the VFR system has estimated. The system appears to underestimate waters that have higher than average local use, which may be the case on Beula Lake.

MIDDLE CREEK

Middle Creek flows east from the Park into the North Fork of the Shoshone River. The stream is mostly inaccessible but offers some angling opportunity near the East Entrance. Regulations in recent years have allowed two fish of any size to be creeled per day. Inhabitants of the stream appear to be solely cutthroat trout, although this has not been confirmed in recent years.

For 1977 through 1979, an average of 250 angler-days were spent annually on the stream (Table 5). Landing and creel rates of 1.2 and 0.4 fish per hour, respectively, are above average for Park fisheries. The average size of trout landed, at 264 mm (10.4 in), is relatively good considering the small size and high gradient of the stream.

WOLF LAKE

Wolf Lake is located approximately 1.6 km (1 mi) downstream from Grebe Lake in the headwaters of the Gibbon River. Because of the Gibbon Falls barrier, this portion of the drainage was historically fishless. Montana grayling, Yellowstone cutthroat and rainbow trout have been introduced in past years, and the grayling and hybrids of the cutthroat and rainbow are believed to exist in the lake at present. The grayling has been protected by catch-and-release-only regulations since 1969. Two trout of any size are allowed to be creeled per day.

Between 1977 and 1979, an average of 240 angler-days have been expended per year (Table 5). Success, in terms of landing and creel rates, has been about average for Park fisheries although angler satisfaction is high, and the average size of fish landed (287 mm or 11.3 in) is considered excellent for a small back-country water.

GOOSE LAKE

Goose Lake is the terminus of a short drainage that begins above Gooseneck Lake. The lake contains a population of rainbow and perhaps brook trout, and has been puzzling in the past because the mode of reproduction of these fishes cannot readily be explained. The Fountain Freight Road provides access to the lake, but in the past, the lake sustained low fishing pressure.

Between 1977 and 1979, an average of 200 angler-days per year has resulted in a relatively slow fishing by Park standards (Table 5). A small trout population is thought to be the reason. Individual fish landed and creeled, however, are above average and offer some incentive.

RIBBON LAKE

Ribbon Lake lies near the rim of the Grand Canyon of the Yellowstone about 3.2 km (2 mi) from the Artist's Point parking area. The small (4.5 ha or 11 a) lake is on a popular day-use trail and receives heavy angling use. The lake's fish population is composed solely of relatively small rainbow trout. Regulations governing the fishery in recent years have allowed two fish of any size to be creeled per day.

In the years 1977, 1978 and 1979, an average of 200 angler-days per year were expended fishing the lake (Table 5). Landing rates were below par though creel rates were higher than average for Park fisheries. The average size of trout landed and creeled (267 mm or 10.5 in) is small.

It may be that the poorer than average condition of this fishery is due to the very high (33 angler-hours per acre) annual rates of exploitation.

DUCK CREEK

Duck Creek only flows for about 5.2 km (3.2 mi) within the Park although its progenitors (Campanula, Gneiss and Richards Creeks) drain an extensive area in Yellowstone. Brook trout dominate the stream's fishery followed by rainbow and brown trout. The occurrence of larger sized trout in the fishery may be the result of close proximity and connection with Hebgen Lake. In recent years, regulations governing Duck Creek have allowed a daily limit of five fish, if three or more are brook trout.

For the years 1977, 1978 and 1979, an average of 190 angler-days were spent on the stream resulting in rather slow rates of success (Table 5). Angler satisfaction is high, which is probably a result of the frequency of larger trout in the catch. Brown and rainbow trout tend to make up the majority of larger fish while brook trout tend to be small.

NATIVE SPECIES RESTORATION PROGRAM

Introduction

The native fishes of Yellowstone Park consist of eleven species. The Montana grayling, three or more subspecies or races of cutthroat trout and the mountain whitefish are the best known. In addition, three species of suckers, four species of minnows (Cyprinidae) and the mottled sculpin are also native. The range and densities of these fishes have been altered substantially in the past century.

The restoration of native fish species in natural areas of the National Park system is a matter of policy (U.S. Dept. Interior 1975). Yellowstone has a number of species, subspecies or races of sport fish that are threatened with extinction (Varley et al 1976). At present, an active program of restoration is underway in the Park that seeks to expand the ranges of these threatened fishes. The management strategies developed to attain restoration objectives consist of the enclave concept and the selective exploitation concept (Varley et al 1976).

During 1979, the native species restoration program included the following projects: 1. the Montana grayling restoration project; 2. the Heart Lake cutthroat restoration project; 3. the Sedge Creek cutthroat transplant program; and 4. evaluation of the relative purity of selected cutthroat and rainbow trout stocks.

Montana Grayling Restoration Project

A review of the historical background and rationale of the Montana grayling restoration program has been presented in previous reports (Varley et al 1976 and Jones et al 1978). Canyon Creek, a tributary of the lower Gibbon River, was chemically treated in 1975 to provide a suitable enclave for this species. A barrier-falls was also constructed to prevent upstream recontamination. In June 1976, 2,863 grayling averaging 229 mm (9 in) were transplanted from the Bozeman Fish Cultural Development Center to the Park and airlifted to Canyon Creek. These fish came from eggs taken from Grebe Lake in the spring of 1975. Permission was obtained from the Montana Fish and Game Commission to electrofish the Big Hole River (the last stronghold for fluvial

Montana grayling) and transplant no more than 200 grayling into Canyon Creek. This operation was carried out in late August 1976, and approximately 120 live grayling were airlifted into Canyon Creek. During 1977, an additional plant of Montana grayling was made. The source of eggs was from an outlet spawning population of grayling from Deer Lake, Gallatin National Forest, Montana. In this planting, an unknown number (believed to be 2,000-4,000 eggs) of advanced eyed eggs were set out in Vibert-type boxes in springs tributary to Canyon Creek.

In 1978, 5,000 swimup fry from Red Rock Lakes stock were obtained from Montana Department of Fish and Game and planted in upper Canyon Creek on June 13.

In 1979, several attempts to obtain grayling eggs proved futile and no plants were made.

The objective for the Canyon Creek project continues to be directed toward the behavioral and/or genetic engineering of a wild, self-reproducing population of true fluvial stock, similar to that which once existed in the drainage. We will attempt further plants to accomplish that goal in 1980.

Heart Lake Cutthroat Restoration Project

The Heart Lake cutthroat restoration project sought to provide a second enclave, removed from Heart Lake, for this vulnerable genotype (Dean and Varley 1974, R. Behnke, pers. comm. 1974). Pocket Lake was selected for this purpose because it was the only known potential enclave in the Snake River drainage, and it was also remote and protected. The lake previously sustained an exotic brook trout population which was destroyed by Antimycin in August, 1977.

In September, 1977, 993 cutthroat trout from Beaver Creek, a tributary of Heart Lake were captured and transplanted to Pocket Lake by helicopter. A similar operation took place in September, 1978, when approximately 900 young-of-the-year and age I+ trout were captured and transplanted to the lake. Also in 1978, Pocket Lake was placed under catch-and-release-only regulations to protect the young stock.

If evaluation of these plants proves promising in 1980, no further work on this project is recommended in the immediate future.

Sedge Creek Cutthroat Transplants

The Yellowstone River originates outside the Park boundaries in the Teton Wilderness Area. The branches of the Yellowstone above Woodard Canyon were fishless due to falls preventing upstream fish movement. The Wyoming Game and Fish Department, who have management jurisdiction over fishes in this area, have aspired to establish cutthroat trout in this region for many years. Previous transplants using stocks from Yellowstone Lake have proven fruitless. These fish apparently have strong inherent instincts to drift downstream to the lake. Due to these instincts, a search was made for a suitable and pure Yellowstone cutthroat strain for transplant. Trout from Sedge Creek were ultimately chosen for a variety of reasons. In recent geologic time Sedge Creek was directly connected to Yellowstone Lake but as the depth diminished, upper Sedge Creek was isolated from Yellowstone Lake proper by Turbid Lake, a geothermal body of water. In subsequent years, the population evolved to become a fluvial form adapted to a very harsh, subalpine environment. Some morphological changes in the fish also occurred (Bulkley 1963), but there is no evidence that this population has been altered by fish stocking or fishing pressure; therefore, it is truly a distinctive and pristine strain.

Using this strain for transplant to the upper Yellowstone River area served two purposes: it provided an optimally adapted population of Yellowstone cutthroats for another harsh, subalpine environment, and it provided a second, secure enclave for this unique genotype.

During June, 1977, 457 trout were collected and transplanted by helicopter to suitable habitat on the South Fork of the Yellowstone River. The planted trout varied in size from 51 to 221 mm (2-11.2 in) total length. Ageing suggested the group included yearlings through five year-olds. Numerous prespawning individuals were present in the group although it is not known whether they would spawn in their new environment following transplant. On July 7, 1978, 413 trout were transplanted. Of one hundred measured for length, the average length for these cutthroats was 118 mm, ranging from 58-254 mm.

On July 24, 1979, one days' electrofishing on Sedge Creek yielded 604 cutthroat trout of which approximately 550 were successfully airlifted.

Recent observations made in the area of the South Fork suggests the establishment of cutthroats in these waters appears highly promising.

Cutthroat-Rainbow Trout Genetics

The purity of the subspecies or strains of cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Park has been the subject of extensive studies for more than a decade. Current research has been directed towards isolated populations and those that may have hybridized with rainbow trout. For several years, Dr. Eric Loudenslager, of the University of California at Davis, has been conducting biochemical studies. Populations sampled in 1979 included suspected pure populations of the Yellowstone group from the Yellowstone River in the Grand Canyon, upper and lower Slough Creek, upper Pebble Creek, Yellowstone Lake, Sportsman Lake, Bear Creek and upper Alum Creek. Populations from the upper Snake River group were collected from Heart Lake and Sheridan Lake. Westslope cutthroats were sampled from Grayling Creek, Bacon Rind Creek and the Galatin River. Suspected rainbow-cutthroat hybrids were taken from Rose Creek, Buffalo Fork, upper Gibbon River, Tower Creek and Soda Butte Creek.

Results of the present studies will be prepared in a final report by Dr. Loudenslager in 1980, and will be reported in the future.

OTHER PROJECT ACTIVITIES

Young Adult Conservation Corps

Yellowstone's resident Y.A.C.C. camp provided three enrollees to assist in data analysis during the winter and five enrollees to help collect field data during the summer. In the past year, approximately 50% of our summer field program and 25% of the winter data analysis would not have been possible without them. The Y.A.C.C. program has become an essential part of this project, but they do not totally replace seasonal employees, and certainly not a full-time biologist.

Assistance to Independent Researchers

Project personnel frequently assist independent researchers working on aquatic related studies in the Park. We provide administrative liason and logistical support at the request of either the National Park Service or the Fish and Wildlife Service. During 1979, aid was given to Dr. E. Vyse, Montana State University, who worked on the genetics of Montana grayling; Dr. E. Loudenslager, University of California, who worked on cutthroat trout taxonomy; and Richard D. Swanson, University of Wyoming graduate student, who worked on the possible competitive interaction between cutthroat trout and longnose suckers.

Youth Conservation Corps

The Y.C.C. provided a valuable service to the fisheries program in the Park, and its participants received a a diverse educational experience as a result. A short orientation and training session was presented to the participants prior to each work assignment. The purpose and objectives of each project were explained, and they were trained on methods and equipment to be used. In 1979, they assisted in operation of the Pelican and Clear Creek traps, repaired extensive flood damage to the Cub Creek trap and assisted in marking 48,000 cutthroat trout at Pelican and Clear Creeks.

Trawling

The search for a better method of assessing year-class strengths of cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Lake has been important in recent years. Mid-water trawling was selected as a feasible method. Construction and testing of the mechanical apparatus for utilizing a Tucker trawl was completed in 1978.

In 1979, the mechanical apparatus was installed on the project's 23 foot I.O. boat for testing. A new compass and several lighting modifications were made to aid in the night navigation. Approximately 30 hours were spent perfecting night trawling and navigation on the lake. The trawl was operated between 6-20 meters depth at several locations in the northern part of the lake. No salmonids were captured in the trawl; however, all trawling operations took place with a full moon, which is less than an ideal trawling condition. The echosounder used proved to be inadequate because it will not locate fish in the target range. Shiners were captured at one location in shallow depths near the bottom.

To fully evaluate, the trawl will require further testing under ideal weather conditions, with an improved echo sounder, and at different towing speeds.

Yellowstone Aquatic Library

In 1979, efforts to collect and catalog the substantial written material on aquatic resources in Yellowstone Park continued. The project, which began in 1973, presently has about 630 titles which are cross-referenced by author, species, water (locale) and subject. This achievement was possible largely because of the availability of Y.A.C.C. assistance. Work in 1979 centered on cross-referencing the substantial F.W.S. and N.P.S. correspondence files collected in the past 50 years.

Yellowstone, Lewis, Shoshone, Heart Lakes Limnology

In 1979, limnological sampling was conducted on all four of Yellowstone's large, oligotrophic lakes. This included the fourth year of sampling Yellowstone Lake and the third year on Lewis Lake. As a result of the diligent efforts of the rangers stationed at Shoshone and Heart Lakes, sampling on a regularly scheduled basis, which began for the first time in 1978, continued in 1979.

Data collection began on Yellowstone Lake as a direct result of the 1976 Divide fire; however, the overall objective of the limnology program on all four lakes is to provide long-term baseline limnological data. These data are especially important as a result of the Park's natural fire program. Results from these sampling programs will be reported in the future.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This report was made possible by the collective efforts of numerous individuals who deserve credit for their efforts. We thank the following persons: Mr. Kemper McMaster, as our only seasonal employee, contributed significantly to our field operations; Rick Swanson, although a graduate student working full-time on longnose suckers, was helpful enough to fill the shoes of another seasonal; Y.A.C.C. enrollees Phyllis Vining, Kathy Buff, Mary Micklos, Bob Wolak, Karen Lubold, Pat Bigelow, Ann Mitchell, Dave Susong and Jim Busk worked for us during either the field season, the winter data analyses period or both, and made our operations viable; Mike Morris, a college work-study student, helped during the summer field season; Dennis Kaleta spent the winter working with our aquatic insect collections and is primarily responsible for the insect work found herein; Don C. Despain again freely gave his time and talents identifying aquatic plants; Lee Whittlesey has again helped us with place-names for our remote and nameless waters; the Heart and Shoshone Lake rangers, Tim Stone and Don Yestness, collected limnological data from those lakes in a highly competent manner; Fish and Wildlife Service personnel from the Billings Area Office and stations at Hardin, Jackson, Ennis and Bozeman made the fall gillnetting a pleasure; Roy Whaley and his seining crew from the Wyoming Game and Fish Commission were also a pleasure to work with on Yellowstone Lake.

Our special thanks to all of the above and also to those who contributed, but have been unfortunately forgotten.

This report was submitted by:

Ronald D. Jones, Project Leader

John D. Varley, Asst. Project Leader

Reviewed by:

Jack D. Larmoyeux, Area Supervisor
Fishery Resources, Billings Area Office

PART II

TECHNICAL STUDIES

STREAM SURVEYS

Investigations into the Park's extensive aquatic stream resource were conducted in 1979. A reconnaissance survey was conducted on Maple Creek utilizing those methods described in the Firehole River drainage study (Jones et al 1978). Slough Creek and the Lewis River were surveyed using much the same methods described in 1978 (Jones et al 1979), with the following changes: 1. at least two stations were sampled on each stream, 2. station length was increased to 304 m, and 3. the number of transects per station was increased to 5 (numbered from downstream to upstream) at 69 m intervals. To gain better insight into the 1978 survey on Cascade Creek, two additional stations located in distinctively different habitat types were analyzed (Jones et al 1979).

Maple Creek

Maple Creek is situated in the northwestern part of the Park and drains the Gallatin Range. The reconnaissance survey was conducted on August 28-30, 1979. During the survey, wildlife was sparse along the stream course; however, game trails and beds were abundant throughout. On historical maps, the main southern tributary to Maple Creek (SONYEW #1301) was named Duck Creek. To avoid confusion in this report, #1301 will be referred to as upper Duck Creek while the stream at the mouth of Maple Creek will be noted as lower Duck Creek.

Access to Maple Creek can be accomplished by three routes. The easiest is from Highway 191 where the stream crosses under the road approximately 1.28 km south of the Quake Lake turn-off. Here the creek is under Montana State jurisdiction. The part of Maple Creek in the Park can be easily reached via a dirt road 0.4 km south of the Highway 191 crossing. The stream closely parallels this road east for 1.6 km to the Park boundary where all vehicles must be abandoned; further access must be accomplished by foot. Another access point can be reached by foot travel only over the Gneiss Creek trail, a well-marked and maintained trail, which begins at Highway 191 approximately 1.25 km north of the Quake Lake road turn-off. This trail intercepts the creek 11.1 km from the trailhead. The stream may also be approached by bush-whacking from two trails, the Cougar Creek and the Mount Holmes pack-trails, however, the terrain is rough with dense forests and thick underbrush.

Historic and Fish Stocking Records

Other than station fish stocking records, no other references to Maple Creek could be found in books or articles. Historically, Maple Creek was first stocked in 1923 with cutthroat trout eyed eggs from the Yellowstone Lake hatchery and repeatedly supplied in 1924, 1926 and 1932. The only official rainbow trout plants took place in 1939; however, this species has not been reported or observed in the creek since that time. The last stocking was in 1947 when brown trout were planted there for the first time, and this species appears to have survived through the years. Although there are no records of brook trout plants, they are now the dominant fish species. These fish probably entered the Maple Creek drainage via the Madison River and Hebgen Lake and thrived in the cold, mountain stream environment. Since brook trout easily out-compete cutthroat trout for food and space, it is not surprising that cutthroat can no longer be found in this drainage.

Description of Area

From the headwaters to its junction with the upper Duck Creek (19.1 km downstream), Maple Creek travels westwardly through a dense forest dominated primarily by a subalpine fir/grouse whortleberry habitat type with occasional patches of meadow rue (Figure 1). The mainstem continues for 4.8 km to the Gneiss Creek trail through a thick subalpine fir/pinegrass forest interspersed with wet subalpine fir types and meadow rue. From here to its mouth (21.9 km), the stream meanders through a dense willow cover with upper and lower slopes varying from predominately lodgepole pine/antelope brush to subalpine fir/pinegrass and infrequent stands of big sagebrush and Idaho fescue.

Upper Duck Creek originates south of Mt. Holmes near Christmas Tree Meadows. The north fork of upper Duck Creek (SONYEW #1302) travels 7.2 km from its source to a junction with the mainstem through a subalpine fir/grouse whortleberry forest. From its source to the north fork junction, Duck Creek surges 8.6 km through a Douglas Fir/pinegrass forest and from there continues to Maple Creek (6.5 km) through a subalpine fir/pinegrass forest.

Geologically, Maple Creek and upper Duck Creek are heavily influenced by rhyolitic Lava Creek tuff of the Pleistocene era. Upstream from their junction, however, there is minimal influence from andesitic and basaltic lava flows of the Eocene. The streambed itself

flows over colluvium deposits of predominately scree deposits of rhyolitic rubble from the Pinedale Glaciation.

The Maple Creek drainage (13,721 ha) originates in the western foothills of the White Peaks at an elevation of 2,247 m (Figure 1). It derives its main water supply from small, cold springs and snow-melt. From its source to the junction with upper Duck Creek, Maple Creek descends at a high gradient (25.54/km) through steep cliffs and rocky canyons over a predominately rubble, boulder and sand substrate. Approximately 5.3 km upstream from the junction, the stream tumbles over a series of cascades, each one approximately 0.9-1.5 m in height, and a definite barrier to upstream fish migration. Above this barrier, no fish were observed; however, brook and brown trout were seen below. Upper Duck Creek is also characterized with high gradient (42.54 m/km) and rushes through a steep-walled canyon much as Maple Creek. Permanent barriers in the form of two separate cascade series (each cascade 1.2-2.1 m in height) were observed 4.4 km and 7.2 km upstream from its junction with Maple Creek. In this section, the stream tumbles over a rubble, gravel and sand substrate where aquatic vegetation is scarce (only scattered mosses and algae) and riffles dominate. No fishes were observed upstream from these cascades; however brook trout, sculpins and possibly brown trout were seen a short distance downstream. Downstream from the junction of the two creeks, Maple Creek changes drastically. From here to its mouth, the stream begins to meander at a low gradient (2.7 m/km) over a predominately sand and gravel substrate with deep pools and large deposits of sand and gravel at point bars. Although there is little aquatic vegetation, the riparian zone is dense in willows and sedges and beaver activity is extensive. Brook and brown trout were observed throughout. A remnant of a streambed was found near the alleged junction of Cougar Creek and Maple Creek; however, the bed was only a mere impression and was vegetated with deep rooted grasses, sagebrush and some small lodgepole pines.

Four water samples were taken: two on Maple Creek and two on upper Duck Creek (Table 9). Maple Creek was determined to be a calcium-bicarbonate water with a near neutral pH of 7.3.

Angler Use and Pressure

Due to their remoteness and inaccessibility, the upper reaches of Maple Creek upstream of the Gneiss Creek trail and upper Duck

Table 9. Chemical characteristics of back country streams, Yellowstone National Park, 1979

	Cache Creek	Callfee Creek	Cold Creek	Gallatin River	Grayling Creek	Lamar River	Lewis River
	8/18/79	9/16/79	8/18/79	at Bighorn trailhead 9/11/79	near Park boundary 9/6/79	above Cold Creek 8/18/79	near bridge 7/18/79
Water temp. °C	--	--	--	--	--	--	20
Spec. cond. µmhos	--	--	7.5	8.4	--	7.5	110
pH	7.5	7.8	--	--	--	--	7.2
Dissolved O ₂	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pheno. alk.	76	55	41	142	76	40	27
Total alk.	38	24	12	143	50	14	9.6
Ca hardness	62	42	18	210	70	22	11
Total hardness	135	95	70	282	120	59	75
Total diss. solids	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carbonate alk.	76	56	41	142	76	40	27
Bicarbonate alk.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carbonates	0	68	0	173	93	49	33
Bicarbonates	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hydroxides	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carbon dioxide	20	9.7	17	4.6	10	10	18
Chloride	1.2	4.5	1.5	<1	1	1.2	6.1
Sulfate	11	2	2	75	5	9	3.5
Fluoride	0.13	0.18	0.75	0.23	0.09	0.13	2.6
Phosphate	--	--	--	0.16	<0.06	--	0.19
Potassium	--	--	--	0.5	1.1	--	0.97
Pg hardness	24	18	6	69	20	8	1.4
Calcium	15	9.6	4.8	57	20	5.6	3.8
Magnesium	5.8	4.4	1.5	16	4.9	1.9	0.34
Sodium	9.4	7.9	9.6	5.1	2.3	6.2	14
Iron	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.1	0.16	0.51	0.02
Manganese	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05
Copper	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
Silica	14	6.5	8.8	7	4.2	7.1	32
Color (PCU)	5	0	5	0	0	0	0
Turbidity (NTU)	2.4	0.5	0.76	0.1	0.38	39	0.5
TOC	--	--	--	4.8	18	--	9.5
Ortho-phosphate	--	--	--	0.16	<0.06	--	0.09
Kjeldahl N	--	--	--	0.77	0.03	--	0.16
Nitrate N	--	--	--	0.03	0.02	--	0.03

continued on next page

* field measurements, all others made by commercial laboratory.

Table 9. continued

	Maple Creek		Duck Cr. at confluence w/ Maple Creek		Miller Creek		Slough Creek		Lower Creek		Upper Alum Creek	
	at Oneiss Creek trail crossing 8/30/79	near confluence w/ Duck Creek 8/30/79	Duck Cr. at confluence w/ Maple Creek 8/29/79	Duck Creek near confluence w/ Maple Creek 8/29/79	8/18/79	8/10/79	8/20/79	8/3/79	8/15/79	(#307)		
Water temp. °C.	11	5	7	7	--	16	12	--	--	--	--	--
Spec. cond. µmhos/cm	75	82	75	80	--	151	164	--	--	--	--	--
pH	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.3	7.6	8.2	7.9	7.6	7.6	7-7.2	7-7.2	7-7.2
Dissolved O ₂	--	--	--	0	--	--	--	--	0	0	0	0
Pheno. alk.	0	0	0	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total alk.	36	34	36	26	42	84	78	40	40	78	78	78
Ca hardness	24	28	24	30	14	58	63	16	16	38	38	38
Total hardness	32	32	28	63	24	79	82	28	28	59	59	59
Total diss. solids	56	54	57	0	68	122	125	67	67	128	128	128
Carbonate alk.	0	0	0	36	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bicarbonate alk.	36	34	36	0	42	84	78	40	40	78	78	78
Carbonates	0	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bicarbonates	44	42	44	0	51	102	95	49	49	95	95	95
Hydroxides	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carbon dioxide	15	18	19	19	14	14	63	17	17	40	40	40
Chloride	1.3	1.8	1.1	1.1	2.2	<1	<1	1.4	1.4	<1	<1	<1
Sulfate	1	1	1	1.6	8	1	2	1	1	5	5	5
Fluoride	1	0.39	1.5	--	0.16	0.07	0.06	0.58	0.58	0.4	0.4	0.4
Phosphate	--	--	--	--	--	0.31	0.19	--	--	0.34	0.34	0.34
Potassium	--	--	--	4	--	1.7	1.6	1.6	1.6	3.8	3.8	3.8
Mg hardness	8	4	4	10	10	21	19	12	12	21	21	21
Calcium	9.6	11	9.6	1	56	23	25	6.4	6.4	15	15	15
Magnesium	1.9	1	1	3	2.4	5.1	4.6	2.9	2.9	5.1	5.1	5.1
Sulfates	2.7	2.3	2.7	<0.01	9.6	4.2	3.3	5.3	5.3	7.2	7.2	7.2
Iron	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Manganese	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.1	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05
Copper	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	13	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1
Silica	5.7	5	7.1	0	8.5	18	11	11	11	45	45	45
Color (PCU)	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Turbidity (NTU)	0.26	0.18	0.35	0.25	7	0.37	2.5	0.3	0.3	13	13	13
TGC	--	--	--	--	--	5.8	2.5	--	--	4	4	4
Ortho-phosphate	--	--	--	--	--	0.31	0.12	--	--	0.28	0.28	0.28
Kjeldahl N	--	--	--	--	--	0.08	0.08	--	--	0.17	0.17	0.17
Nitrate N	--	--	--	--	--	0.02	0.04	--	--	0.01	0.01	0.01

* Field measurements, all others made by commercial laboratory.

Creek showed little sign of human visitation. The only evidence observed was an old, partially buried fire ring (probably 20-50 years old) at the junction of #1302 and the mainstem of upper Duck Creek. There is a designated campsite at the Gneiss Creek trail crossing where fishing line and some trash were found. Well-beaten angler paths were observed along the banks near Highway 191 and from the service road to the Park boundary.

VFR data for 1974 through 1979 show an average of 38 angler days/year spent on Maple Creek. Average landing and creel rates were 1.51 and 0.26 trout/hour/year, respectively, which is excellent by Yellowstone standards.

Cascade Creek

In 1978, a comprehensive stream survey was conducted on Cascade Creek; however, at that time only one station was measured (Jones et al 1979). Since the habitat type in that section represented only 29% of the entire creek, the stream was resurveyed in 1979 at two distinctly different habitat types. These additional stations were then compared and included with the 1978 data.

Habitat Inventory

Two stations were surveyed in 1979. Station 2 was located 1.9 km downstream from Cascade Lake and station 3 was 1.2 km upstream from the mouth. The average width, depth and flow of stations 2 and 3 were 1.49 m, 0.12 m and 0.015 m³/sec and 3.35 m, 0.12 m and 0.06 m³/sec, respectively (Table 10).

Station 2 was located in a forested area. The upper slopes were dominated by a spruce and lodgepole pine forest with a twinberry undergrowth. The lower slopes were generally spruce and lodgepole pine while grasses, willows and sedges dominated the riparian zone. Approximately 40% direct sunlight reaches the stream on a clear, summer day.

In the canyon area (station 3), the upper slopes were steep and predominately a spruce and lodgepole pine/pinegrass forest with scattered sub-alpine fir and aspen. The lower slopes were generally spruce and lodgepole pine with mixed areas of Douglas fir, pinegrass, willows and huckleberry. Willows, sedges, twinberry and mixed grasses made-up the riparian zone. In this steep-sloped area only 25% of direct sunlight reaches the creek on a clear summer day.

In 1978, the Optimum Rating for Cascade Creek was determined at a low 15% (Jones et al 1979); however, when stations 2 and 3 are included in estimates, the rating for the entire stream increased to 32.5% (Table 11). This increase is due to the numerous pools and dense riparian cover

Table II. Station means and optimum habitat ratings for the Lewis River, Cascade Creek and Slouch Creek, 1979

	Lewis River			Slouch Creek			Cascade Creek		
	Sta. 1	Sta. 2	Sta. 3	Sta. 1	Sta. 2	Sta. 3	Sta. 1 ¹⁾	Sta. 2	Sta. 3
Pool measure (x)	0.0	0.0	7.1	57.0	35.1	29.4	0.0	34.1	25.3
Pool structure (%)	0.0	0.0	7.1	35.5	17.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Stream bottom (%)	15.6	60.0	69.2	41.0	46.0	65.0	35.0	67.0	55.0
Environment	68.8	32.5	35.0	42.5	90.0	42.5	25.0	67.5	65.0
			weighted avg. survey area			weighted avg. survey area			weighted avg. survey area
			2.4			29.4			37.6
			2.4			0.0			12.7
			42.3			65.0			54.9
			52.1			42.5			52.6
Bottom structure (x)	71.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	45.0	0.0	17.0
Gravel	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	22.0	0.0	1.7	0.0	17.0
Silt	11.6	1.0	5.2	8.0	37.0	36.0	25.6	34.0	41.0
Sand	4.0	59.0	64.0	33.0	5.0	29.0	9.2	33.0	14.0
Other	12.0	30.0	23.0	32.0	25.0	26.0	16.7	18.0	12.0
	1.0	1.0	8.0	21.0	9.0	9.0	1.7	15.0	4.0
	0.0	0.0	0.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mean width (x)	34.9	35.4	35.9	36.2	21.9	24.4	3.2	1.5	3.4
(x) Pool	0.0	0.0	4.6	31.3	46.9	14.7	33.3	27.9	12.6
(x) riffle	107.0	100.0	96.4	56.6	53.1	55.3	66.7	76.8	57.4
Mean center (x)	0.40	0.52	0.43	0.67	0.49	0.49	0.19	0.12	0.09
Mean velocity (x/sec)	0.64	0.71	0.74	0.03	0.69	0.09	—	0.69	0.24
Flow (m ³ /sec)	5.97	3.42	3.36	0.71	0.60	0.67	—	6.02	0.66
Y of the habitat represented by each station	33.3	33.3	33.3	25.0	21.0	53.0	29.0	40.0	31.0
Center Habitat Rating (%)	26.1	23.1	27.0	44.0	47.1	34.2	15.0	42.2	36.3
			26.3			39.4			32.5

1) Station 1, Cascade Creek, survey in 1978 (Jones et al 1979).

found at stations 2 and 3. At both stations, the bottom structure was predominately rubble and gravel which produced a marked increase in the stream bottom rating from station 1 (generally bedrock bottom).

When all three stations were combined, Cascade Creek was rated good (66.6) under the Channel Stability Rating System (U.S. Forest Service 1975) (Table 12); this was poorer than the 1978 rating (49) (Jones et al 1979). The upper and lower banks in station 3 were less stable than stations 1 and 2 causing some mass wasting and jam debris; as a result, pools were shallow and showed evidence of siltation. The stream bottoms in stations 2 and 3 were less stable than station 1 with some bottom sediment shifting and scouring at constrictions. This increased instability found in stations 2 and 3 was the cause of the lower channel stability ratings.

Aquatic vegetation was far more common in stations 2 and 3 than in station 1 (Jones et al 1979). Although aquatic vascular plants were rarely observed in stations 2 and 3, liverworts and mosses were common but lacked species diversity. Mosses were especially abundant in the rubble sections of station 3.

Aquatic Invertebrates

One overnight drift and two surber samples were collected at station 3. No invertebrate sampling was conducted in station 2. A total of 229 invertebrates were collected in the drift and 70 in surber samples (Table 13). As in the 1978 sample, Baetidae mayflies (i.e. Baetis tricaudatis) were the most abundant group in the drift, but the beetle Heterlimnius sp. was most common in the surber.

Mayflies in the drift numbered 0.82 individuals per cubic meter of water. All combined aquatic invertebrates drifted at 1.60/m³ of water. This yielded a ratio of 1: 1.95 (mayflies all combined) per cubic meter of flow. These estimates were slightly lower than those found in the drift at station 1 in 1978.

Lewis River

Lewis River is situated in the south-central portion of the Park. During the survey, moose were abundant along the stream course as well as evidence of current beaver activity. Although the Lewis River drainage (43,988 ha) reaches from Shoshone Lake to the Snake River, only the 6 km catch-and-release section between the Lewis River Bridge and the canyon was sampled. The survey was conducted on July 12, 18 and 19, 1979, at three separate stations (Figure 2). Results of an electro-

LEWIS RIVER

7/31/79

Figure 2 . Lewis River, catch-and-release section, 1979.

Table 12. Stream reach inventory and channel stability evaluation, Lewis River, Cascade Creek, and Slough Creek, 1979.

	STATION 1)				STATION 2				STATION 3			
	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor
<u>LEWIS RIVER</u>												
Upper Banks	5	10	0	0	5	10	0	0	8	4	0	0
Lower Banks	10	2	6	0	0	20	3	8	4	4	15	8
Stream Bottom	8	12	3	0	0	0	39	8	0	2	24	24
TOTALS	23	24	9	0	5	30	42	16	12	10	39	32
Station Stability Score:	93											
Stream Stability Score ²⁾ :	80.7 or fair											
<u>CASCADE CREEK</u>												
Upper Banks	8	0	6	0	8	4	0	0	0	12	12	0
Lower Banks	10	2	0	8	0	14	16	0	2	14	12	0
Stream Bottom	15	0	0	0	2	26	0	0	6	16	0	0
TOTALS	33	2	6	8	10	44	0	0	8	44	24	0
Station Stability Score:	72											
Stream Stability Score ²⁾ :	66.6 or Good											
<u>SLOUGH CREEK</u>												
Upper Banks	2	6	15	0	3	0	21	0	2	10	9	0
Lower Banks	0	6	21	24	2	4	27	0	2	0	27	8
Stream Bottom	0	10	30	0	7	16	0	0	0	4	39	0
TOTALS	2	16	66	24	12	20	48	0	4	14	75	8
Station Stability Score:	80											
Stream Stability Score ²⁾ :	97.3 or Fair											

1) Cascade Creek Station 1 was conducted in 1978 (Jenns et al, 1979).

2) Ratings: Excellent = 0 - 38; Good = 39 - 76; Fair = 77 - 114; Poor = 115+.

Table 13. continued

Taxon (common name)	Number of Invertebrates									
	Cascade Creek		Lewis River				Slough Creek			
	8/2/79 Station 3		Sta. 1	7/12, 18-19/79 Sta. 2 Sta. 3		Sta. 3	8/8-10 & 20-22/79 Sta. 1 Sta. 2 Sta. 3 Sta. 3			
Surber	Drift	Surber	Surber	Surber	Drift	Surber	Surber	Surber	Drift #1	Drift #2
Trichoptera (caddisflies)										
Brachycentridae										
Brachycentrus sp.			1			67				
Micrasema sp.	7	44					1	40	1	
Glossosomatidae										
Glossosoma sp.	10	14								
Hydropsychidae										
Parapsyche sp.	1									
Hydroptilidae										
Hydroctila sp.							1		66	1
Lepidostomatidae										
Lepidostoma sp.			1							
Leptoceridae										
Gecetis sp.			1							
Limnephilidae										
Apatania sp.								1	11	1
Phlebotanidae										
Colophonilodes sp.		2								
Polytropodidae										
Polytropus sp.	6									
Psychomyiidae										
Linodes sp.				1						
Rhyacophilidae										
Rhyacophila sp.	3								4	
Coleoptera (beetles)										
Dytiscidae										
Acabus sp.		1								
Oreocytes sp.							13		1	3
Elmidae										
Cleotelis sp.	9	4	36	6	8	2	1	3	8	2
Heterilimnius sp.	13	5						2	2	1
Halplidae										
Brychius sp.									1	
Peltodytes sp.						1				
Diptera (true flies)										
Chironomidae										
	1	1	8			19	142	72	275	53
Rhaqionidae										
Atherix sp.							1	1		
Simuliidae										
		3				1				13
Tanuloae										
	1	1		1	3		3	2	1	
Amphipoda (scuds)										
Hyalella azteca										
			11	2	5	14				
Pelecypoda (clams)										
Sphaeriidae										
			3							
Hirudinea (leeches)										
					2					
Hydracarina (water mites)										
		16					2			16
Oligochaeta (aquatic earthworms)										
			16	4			3		2	
TOTAL NUMBER INVERTEBRATES	70	229	90	22	20	707	173	194	611	465
NUMBER TAXONOMIC GROUPS	18	19	14	9	6	21	14	15	24	18
TOTAL NUMBER OF GROUPS PER WATER	25		52				36			

shocking survey were reported in 1978 (Jones et al 1979). A basic hydrographic survey was obtained by visual observation on July 31, 1979.

Historic and Fish Stocking Records

In 1889, David Starr Jordan (1891) found the Lewis River above Lewis Falls barren of fishlife. Although there is no mention of the river below the falls prior to initial fish stocking in 1890, it is also believed that the section of river between the Lewis River Bridge and the canyon area was also historically barren. Aster Creek, the major tributary in that section, was historically fishless which suggests the existence of a fish barrier somewhere in the inaccessible reaches of Lewis River Canyon. Although the section of river below the falls was not specifically referred to in stocking records, repeated fish plants in Lewis River above the falls, Lewis, Shoshone, Aster and DeLacy Lakes and Shoshone, DeLacy and Aster Creeks produced a ready supply of fish to the previously barren middle Lewis River. Between 1890 and 1954, numerous plants of grayling and brook, brown, cutthroat, rainbow and lake trout were made in these waters. Today, only brook, brown and lake trout thrive throughout most of these waters.

Since 1973, the section of river between Lewis River Falls and the canyon has been regulated for catch-and-release fishing only. Since then, no regulation changes have been initiated.

Physical and Chemical Characteristics

The Lewis River originates as the outlet to Shoshone Lake at an elevation of 2,377 m. It continues through Lewis Lake, over Lewis River Falls and eventually empties into the Snake River (elevation of 2,097 m) after traveling 45.7 km from its source (Figure 2).

Easy access to the surveyed section can be obtained from the South Entrance road which closely parallels the river. This 6 km section courses through open wet, sedge meadows and subalpine fir forests at a very low gradient (2.04 m/km). Geologically, this area is heavily influenced by the Aster Creek and Pitchstone Plateau rhyolitic flows of the Pleistocene era. The river itself courses through alluvium and glaciofluvial deposits of the Helocene era. Another noted geologic formation, the southwestern fault scarp of the Yellowstone Caldera, closely parallels Aster Creek and approximately 2 km of the river below the falls.

One water sample was collected 150 km downstream from the bridge (Table 9). On the basis of ionic components, the surveyed section was classified

as a sodium-bicarbonate water. This was expected since both Lewis and Shoshone Lakes have a similar chemical makeup. Compared to other Park streams recently surveyed, the river had lower than average or near average concentrations in most properties; however, it was higher than average in chloride, fluoride, sodium and silica.

Habitat Inventory

Three stations were selected and analyzed on the 6 km section below the falls (Figure 2). Station 1 was located 0.4 km upstream from the canyon, station 2 at the large roadside talus slope, and station 3 about 0.4 km downstream from the bridge. The average depth and flow for the surveyed area were 0.46 m and 4.25 m³/sec, respectively. Width varied from 28.8 m to 49.8 m.

The percent of optimum for the 6 km section was 26.3% (Table 11). This relatively low rating is probably due to the near absence of pools at all three stations and high percentage of exposed banks in stations 2 and 3. Stream bottom ratings were high in stations 2 and 3, but environment ratings were high only in station 1. Since the three chosen station sites appeared to be representative of the entire catch-and-release section, the low optimum rating represents the true percentage of prime fish habitat.

The upper slopes were generally forested with lodgepole pine, subalpine fir and occasional patches of whitebark pine and twinberry (Table 10). The lower slopes were densely covered with twinberry, willows, grasses, sedges and infrequent stands of lodgepole pine, whitebark pine and subalpine fir. The riparian zone was lush with twinberry, grasses, sedges and, less frequently, willows. This vegetation created 50% or more stable banks throughout the section. An average of 98% of direct sunlight reaches this area on a clear, summer day.

Under the Channel Stability Rating System (U.S. Forest Service 1975), the surveyed area was rated fair (80.7) (Table 12). The upper banks showed little evidence of past or any potential for future mass wasting into the channel. The lower banks showed evidence of occasional overbank floods. There was some bank erosion and increases in bar formation, mostly of coarse gravels and sands. The stream bottom in stations 2 and 3 was relatively unstable and 30-50% of the bottom was in state of flux. Rocks moved easily underfoot and were rounded and well-sorted. Station 1, however, showed no signs of either scouring or deposition; rocks were tightly packed and wedged in an array of sizes. The high rating of stream bottom at station 1 was due to the high percentage of bedrock found (71.4%) (Tables 11 and 12).

Aquatic vegetation was uncommon throughout the surveyed section. Although there was a high diversity of aquatic vascular plants (Table 14), they were not abundant and were restricted to backwater areas. Few mosses and only two types of algae were observed. The yellow-green stalked diatom, Cymbella sp., was identified for the first time from Park waters. Since sufficient sunlight reaches the stream, minimal plant production is heavily influenced by the general instability of the stream bottom.

Aquatic Invertebrates

Both surber and overnight drift samples were used for quantitative investigations of aquatic invertebrates. Two surber samples were taken at each station and one overnight drift was conducted at station 3. From the surber samples, a total of 132 invertebrates were collected from which 29 taxonomic groups were identified; however, a total of 707 individuals and 21 taxonomic groups were indentified from the one drift sample (Table 13). Baetis mayflies were most common in the drift while the beetle, Elmidae, was most abundant in the surber. Of the three stations, station 1 had the highest density and diversity of invertebrates and taxonomic groups; this is due to the more stable bottom found at that station.

The drift was used to determine the number of mayflies and number of combined aquatic invertebrates per cubic meter of water. Mayflies, which made up 84% of all the invertebrates in the drift, drifted at $3.2/m^3$ of water; all aquatic invertebrates combined were slightly higher at $3.8/m^3$. The ratio of mayflies to all invertebrates combined was 1:1.2.

Angler Use and Pressure

Due to its easy roadside access, the catch-and-release section of the Lewis River drainage receives heavy angling pressure. Deeply entrenched angler trails were observed along the banks of the entire section and fishing line was frequently found tangled among the bushes. This section of the Lewis River has appeared in VFR data annually since 1975 with an average of 1,569 angler days/year. These anglers produced landing and creel rates of 0.99 and 0.05 trout/hour/year.

Slough Creek

Slough Creek originates as the outlet to a small unnamed lake west of Pinnacle Mountain and travels 36.4 km through Gallatin National Forest before reaching the Park boundary. It flows 32.4 km through the north-

Table 14. Terrestrial and aquatic plants, Cascade Creek, Lewis River and Slough Creek, W.P., 1979.

Name	CASCADE CREEK 8/2/79		LEWIS RIVER	SLOUGH CREEK 8/10/20/21/79		
	Sta. #2	Sta. #3	8/12, 18, 19/79	Sta. #1	Sta. #2	Sta. #3
Terrestrial plants:						
<u>Alnus incana</u> (L.) Moench (mountain alder)					X	
<u>Betula glandulosa</u> Michx. (hog birch, scrub birch)					X	X
<u>Carex rostrata</u> Stokes (beaked sedge)						X
<u>Lonicera involucrata</u> (Rich.) Banks (honeysuckle, black twiberry)		X	X			
<u>Mahonia repens</u> (Lindl.) G. Don (creeping or low Oregon grape)					X	
<u>Poa interior</u> Rydb. (inland bluegrass)						X
<u>Potentilla fruticosa</u> L. (scrubby cinquefoil, yellow rose)					X	
<u>Rosa acicularis</u> Lindl. (prickly rose)					X	
<u>Rosa woodsii</u> Lindl. var woodsii (wood's rose)				X		
<u>Shepherdia canadensis</u> (L.) Nutt (carolina buffaloberry, soapberry, rustyberry)					X	
<u>Thalictrum venulosum</u> (valley meadow rue)	X					
<u>Vaccinium occidentale</u> Gray (western huckleberry)			X			
<u>Viburnum edule</u> (Michx.) Raf. (d. Sandi)					X	
Willows:						
<u>Salix bebbiana</u> Sarg. (bebb willow)				X	X	
<u>Salix boothii</u> Dorn (<i>S. novaeangliae</i> Andrews)	X			X		X
<u>Salix drummondiana</u> Barratt (drummond willow)		X				
<u>Salix fluviatilis</u> Nutt. (river willow)				X	X	
<u>Salix glauca</u> L. (glaucous willow)			X			
<u>Salix lasiandra</u> Benth. (pacific or red willow)		X		X		
<u>Salix wolfii</u> Bebb (wolf's willow)	X		X			X
Aquatics:						
Vascular plants:						
<u>Eleocharis</u> sp. (spike rush)			X			
<u>Elodea canadensis</u> Richard (elodea, rocky Mt. waterweed)			X			
<u>Equisetum arvense</u> L. (common or field horsetail)	X	X				
<u>Isaetes colabrieri</u> Engelm (bolander's quillwort)			X			

continued on next page

Table 14-continued

	CASCADE CREEK 8/2/79 Sta. #2 Sta. #3	LEWIS RIVER 8/12, 18, 19/79 Sta. #1 Sta. #2 Sta. #3	SLOUGH CREEK 8/10/20/21/79 Sta. #1 Sta. #2 Sta. #3
Vascular plants cont.:			
<u>Myriophyllum spicatum L.</u> (spiked water-milfoil)		X	
<u>Potamogeton filiformis Pers.</u> (slender-leaved pondweed)		X	X
<u>Potamogeton gramineus L.</u> (grass-leaved pondweed)		X	
<u>Potamogeton pectinatus L.</u> (fennel-leaved pondweed)		X	
<u>Ranunculus aquatilis L.</u> (white water buttercup or water crowfoot)	X	X	X
<u>Sparacanium sp.</u> (bur-reed)		X	
Mosses:			
<u>Calliergen cordifolium (Hedw.) Kindb.</u>			X
<u>Fontinalis antipyretica Hedw.</u>	X		X
<u>Fontinalis neomexicana S & L</u>		X	
<u>Hypolychnus sp.</u>	X	X	
<u>Jungermannia sp.</u>	X	X	
<u>Jungermannia cordifolia Hook.</u>	X		
<u>Leptodictyum riparium (Hedw.) Warnst.</u>			X
<u>Marchantia sp.</u>			X
Algae:			
<u>Chara sp.</u>			X
<u>Cladophora sp.</u>			X
<u>Cyrtella sp.</u>		X	
<u>Preparnadia sp.</u>			X
<u>Nostoc sp.</u>	X		
<u>Rhizogonium sp.</u>			X
<u>Spirogyra sp.</u>		X	X
<u>Ulothrix sp.</u>		X	X
<u>Zygnema sp.</u>			X

eastern corner of the Park, eventually emptying into the Lamar River. A visual hydrographic survey was conducted on the Park portion of the stream during August 7-9, 1979. A more comprehensive survey, including an electroshocking operation, was conducted at station 3 on August 10, 20-21, 1979.

Auto access to the lower 7.2 km of Slough Creek is provided by a dirt road which leaves the Northeast Entrance Road approximately 9.7 km from Tower Junction. The dirt road branches at three points providing access to the campground area (7.2 km upstream from the mouth) and two other areas (1 km and 6.11 km upstream from the mouth). Other access can be obtained over maintained foot and pack trails. The most heavily used trail (32.2 km long) parallels the stream from the dirt road to Frenchy's Meadow located 7 km outside the Park boundary. Three other maintained Park trails lend access to upper Slough Creek: 1. the Warm Creek trail from Pebble Creek to Elk Tongue Creek patrol cabin (16.7 km long), 2. Buffalo Plateau trail from the Hellroaring Creek trail (32.5 km long), and 3. a short (8.7 km) unnamed trail from Lamar Ranger Station to the lower Slough Creek cabin. Also, the stream can be reached from outside the Park over numerous Forest Service pack trails varying in length from 10-65+ km.

Historic and Fish Stocking Records

In 1889, David Starr Jordan (1891) found Slough Creek "well stocked with native cutthroat trout". Since this first report, the cutthroat trout in this creek have received much journalistic comment. An example of this was written by Lanier (1927) who reported that Slough Creek near the Park boundary had "big native trout" that ran up to "one, one and a half and rarely (in August) two pounds or more". He also stated that the rough water area below McBride Lake was the "pink of fishing" for the big trout of Slough Creek, where cutthroats ran "up to four pounds", and averaged two pounds. Over the years, however, as Slough Creek gained notoriety and angling pressure increased, catch rates and average fish lengths began to fall. When Chapman (no date) wrote of his fishing experience in 1952 on upper Slough Creek, he states that the fish were "rather small but about usual for the placed we fished". It wasn't until 1971 that special regulations were initiated on the declining fishery. At that time, a 14 inch size, three bag limit was imposed. In 1973, as a result of the parkwide roadside stream regulations (Dean and Varley 1974), the creek became a catch-and-release only water.

Although Slough Creek above the canyon barrier was historically, and remains yet, an exclusive cutthroat fishery, the stream was repeatedly

stocked with cutthroat from 1920-1953. In 1936 and 1937, however, McBride Lake was stocked with rainbow trout and grayling. Luckily, these plants did not survive. Below the barrier, cutthroat, rainbow and cutthroat x rainbow hybrids can be found. The introduction of rainbows into the lower Slough Creek drainage occurred during the late 1920's to early 1930's when rainbows were planted in Buffalo Creek.

Physical and Chemical Characteristics

Slough Creek originates in Gallatin National Forest at an elevation of 2,972 m at the base of Pinnacle Mountain (Figure 3). Its water supply is from snow, glaciers, springs and cirque lakes.

Slough Creek has a large drainage area of 56,941 ha, of which only 19,953 ha (35%) are within the Park boundaries. The creek outside the Park travels through a densely forested area at a moderate gradient (26 m/km) and enters the Park at an elevation of 2,024 m. Near the boundary, the stream transforms from a generally forest shaded, swift-running mountain creek to a placid stream meandering through meadows at a low gradient (5 m/km). From the boundary to the canyon barrier (21 km downstream), the creek gently meanders through wet sedges and tufted hairgrass. The upper slopes are generally big sagebrush/Idaho fescue and Engelmann spruce/northern twinflower interspersed with aspen and occasional patches of subalpine fir/northern twinflower. In the canyon area, the creek tumbles over a series of cascades, approximately 0.4-0.8 km in length, with some individual cascades up to 2.1 m in height; this was determined to be a barrier to upstream fish migration (Figure 3). In the canyon area (2.9 km long), wet sedges, tufted hairgrass, Engelmann spruce and Douglas fir are found. Below the canyon to the mouth (10.7 km), Slough Creek meanders through wet sedge/tufted hairgrass meadow surrounded by big sagebrush/Idaho fescue and infrequent stands of aspen and Douglas fir/snowberry.

Geologically, the main course of the river meanders through alluvium and glaciofluvial deposits of the Pleistocene and Helocene eras. Below the Slough Creek patrol cabin, the upper slopes are heavily influenced by Precambrian schist and gneiss. Above the cabin, the area is generally glacial till and landslide deposits made up of volcanic conglomerate, sandstone, tuff and well-sorted breccia.

Two water samples were taken on Slough Creek (Table 9). In agreement with past studies (Pickett and Chadwick 1972; Jones et al 1979), the stream was found to be a calcium-bicarbonate water. The pH varied from

SLOUGH CREEK

8/7-9/79

Figure 3 . Slough Creek, surveyed area, 1979.

8.2 near the mouth and 7.9 near Elk Tongue Creek. Most measured chemical parameters were average for Park waters except for higher than average concentrations of magnesium and calcium at both stations, and TOC near the mouth.

Habitat Inventory

Three stations were sampled on Slough Creek within the Park boundaries (Figure 3). Station 1 was located 0.8 km upstream from the mouth where the stream sluggishly meanders through open sagebrush hills and occasional patches of trees. This station was representative of the lower portion of the stream and 25% of the entire in-park system. Station 2 was located in a canyon area near the McBride Lake. Here the stream tumbled through a forested, cliffed area representative of 21% of the surveyed area. The largest habitat type (53%) was represented by station 3 near Elk Tongue Creek. In this area, the stream meanders through open, rolling sagebrush and grass covered hills and meadows.

The average flow and depth for stations 1, 2 and 3 were 0.71 m³/sec and 0.67 m, 0.6 m³/sec and 0.49 m, and 0.67 m³/sec and 0.49 m, respectively. Widths varied from 11.7 m to 48.4 m at the three stations.

The overall percent of optimum for the Park portion of Slough Creek was 39.4 (Table 11). Although this rating is not high, it is greater than any other stream surveyed to date. Station 1 and 2 received the highest individual optimum ratings, probably due to the larger percentage of quality pools found at station 1 and the greater amount of cover found at station 2. Ratings for stations 1 and 2 indicate that trout habitat for Slough Creek above the barrier to the boundary is nearly 50% of optimum.

The upper slopes in station 1 were predominately sagebrush with infrequent stands of aspen, Engelmann spruce and Douglas fir. At stations 2 and 3, the upper slopes were Engelmann spruce, Douglas fir, lodgepole pine and sagebrush with infrequent stands at station 3 of aspen, juniper and subalpine fir. The lower slopes in stations 1 and 3 were similar with sagebrush, aspen and Douglas fir dominating the areas. At station 2, the lower slopes held a variety of vegetation dominated by Engelmann spruce, Douglas fir, lodgepole pine, wildrose and some juniper and sagebrush. The riparian zone was dominated by grasses, willows, sedges and buffaloberry in station 1; alders, Engelmann spruce and buffaloberry in station 2; and grasses, sedges and timothy at station 3. Approximately 90% of direct sunlight reaches the stream in stations 1 and 3 on a clear, summer day but only 40% in station 2.

The Park portion of the stream was rated fair (97.3) under the Channel Stability Rating System (U.S Forest Service 1975) (Table 12). The upper

banks showed a frequency of mass wasting during high water with subsequent undercutting. Only at station 1 was this less evident with infrequent and very small slumps. Vegetative bank protection was greatest in the canyon area of station 2 (70-90%), and almost nonexistent in station 1 (50-70%) where seedling reproduction was nil and serious erosion of upper banks was possible. The lower banks at all stations showed evidence of significant bank cutting and suggested that the channel barely contains peak runoff during average years. Although the pool-riffle relationship in station 3 appeared stable and obstructions firmly embedded in the channel, these features gradually deteriorated progressively downstream. In stations 2 and 3, fresh, coarse sands and gravels were noticed at constrictions, enlarging bars and filling pools. Station 1 had extensive deposition of fresh sand, silt and small gravel moving downstream even during low flow periods. The channel bottom was 80-100% stable in station 2 where more boulders and rubble could be found tightly packed together and difficult to dislodge; cuts were mostly at channel constrictions and sediments tended to move through pools causing only slight changes in depths. In stations 1 and 3, however, the channel bottoms were mostly gravel and sand with some small rubble loosely packed and easily moveable during high water. The bottom of station 1 was 50-80% stable while station 3 was 20-50%; in both, 30-50% of the bottom was in a state of flux causing significant deposition in pools and point bars.

Aquatic vegetation was common throughout the surveyed portion of the stream (Table 14). Mosses and algae were common in the quieter waters of stations 1 and 3 and were observed less frequently in the fast, shaded water of station 2. There appeared to be a definite change in algal species composition between the upper portion of the creek (stations 2 and 3) and the lower section (station 1). Perhaps this change is influenced by the campground pit toilets located directly upstream from station 1. Vascular plants were less frequent at all three stations.

Aquatic Invertebrates

Both surber and drift sampling methods were conducted on Slough Creek. Two surbers were collected from each station, as well as two overnight drifts from station 3 (referred here as drift #1, taken 8-7-79 and drift #2, taken 8-20-79) (Table 13). A total of 978 invertebrates, representing 30 taxonomic groups, were collected in all surber samples combined; 62% (611) were from the station 3 samples. A total of 753 invertebrates were collected in the combined drift samples (representing 22 taxonomic groups). A total of 36 different taxonomic groups were collected in all drift and surber samples combined. At all

three stations, Chironomidae were most common in the surbers. Baetis mayflies were most common in drift #2 while Ephemerella tibialis was most abundant in drift #1. As observed in 1966 (Arnold and Sharpe 1967), relative abundance of invertebrates and diversity of genera increased progressively upstream.

The two drift samples were combined to determine the average numbers of mayflies and all aquatic invertebrates combined per cubic meter of water. Mayflies made up 82% of the two combined samples and drifted at an average rate of 2.4/m³ of water. All aquatic invertebrates combined drifted at an average of 2.9/m³. The ratio of mayflies to all invertebrates was 1:1.22.

Aquatic Vertebrates

Below the cascade barrier, longnose suckers, rainbow trout, cutthroat trout and cutthroat x rainbow hybrids reside in Slough Creek (Mills and Sharpe 1968). Above the barrier and in the sample, only native cutthroat trout were found.

The Slough Creek fish population was sampled at station 3 in a 53.3 m section blocked off by seines. Fish were electroshocked and a population estimate was determined employing the capture-removal method (Zippin 1958). Three passes were made through the area in which only cutthroat trout were found. Since difficulty was encountered in successfully closing-off the shocked area with seines, estimates may be biased.

A total of 69 cutthroats were captured. Their average weight and K factor were 221 g and 0.91, respectively. Of the 69 trout, 7 were determined to be mature males, 15 mature females, 32 immatures (under 304 mm in length) and 13 were mature (sex undetermined). Mature males were slightly larger than females at 367 mm and 358 mm, respectively.

The shocking site had a surface area of 0.13 ha and an average width of 24.35 m. The population for this area was estimated at 85 cutthroat and 18.8 kg. When expanded for the entire surveyed area above the barrier, the total number and biomass of fish per hectare were 654 cutthroat and 144.5 kg, respectively. The expanded linear estimate was calculated at 1,594 trout/km.

Ages were determined on 37 of the 69 captured cutthroat using the scale method (Laasko and Cope 1956). Ages and lengths were then fitted to an age-length key in order to expand ages for the entire sample (Kimura 1977). The average age for fish over 100 mm in length was 3.5 and included individuals from I+ to V+ years. When captured fish less than

100 mm are given an estimated age of 1+ and included in age estimates, the mean age decreases to 2.8.

Angler Use and Pressure

Due to its easy access both by auto and trail, Slough Creek receives moderate to heavy use. In 1966, Arnold and Sharpe (1967) described the creek as "the heaviest fished stream in the northeast section of the Park". Since then its reputation and popularity have increased tremendously. During the survey period, at least nine anglers, with rod in hand, were observed along the banks of the creek above the barrier. From the campground to the mouth, an average of eight to twelve anglers could be observed "beating the water" at any given time. Fisherman trails were evident along the entire surveyed section, especially in the lower area near the campground. Near the boundary, guests of the Silver Tip Ranch fish the upper section of the creek extensively.

From 1968 to 1972, several types of creel surveys, including manned creel census and localized volunteer cards, were conducted on Slough Creek. Between 1968 and 1979, annual use (angler-days) fluctuated from a low of 3,447 in 1973 to a high of 7,714 in 1979. Annual VFR estimates for Slough Creek since 1973 (which was also the start of catch-and-release-only regulations on the creek) have resulted in a landing rate of 1.61 trout/hour.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Maple Creek was found to have a robust population of brook and brown trout up to the cascade barriers near the headwaters. A dry streambed containing young lodgepole pines was observed where Cougar Creek once entered Maple Creek. For most of the stream, little evidence was present of visitation by man. Since there is concern over the possible contamination of the pure Cougar Creek westslope cutthroat (the only such documented population in the Park) by Maple Creek fishes, monitoring of the old channel between the two creeks should be continued.

Further habitat investigation on Cascade Creek in 1979 increased optimum rating and the reliability of the inventory method considerably. This demonstrated the value in selecting a representative number of survey sites in each habitat type along a stream course.

The catch-and-release section of the Lewis River was found to be relatively poor in fish shelter and optimum habitat. Bank cover is inadequate and the stream bottom is unstable allowing minimal aquatic plant and invertebrate reproduction. This situation is rarely found in streams serving as lake outlets.

Due to its easy roadside access, this section of the Lewis River receives heavy angling pressure. Considering the overall poor quality and quantity of fish habitat, it is not surprising that the fish population in this section is relatively low (Jones et al 1979). Continued investigation into this unstable system is desirable to define future management needs.

Slough Creek, on the other hand, was found to have a robust population of cutthroat trout above the barrier. Although bank cover is sparse in most places, aquatic vegetation was common and invertebrate counts were high. The percent of optimum trout habitat was high compared to the other Park streams surveyed using the transect method. Although angler pressure is heavy, Slough Creek has been able to withstand the high use under current restrictive regulations.

LAKE SURVEY PROGRAM

Introduction

In the early 1960's, the National Park Service requested this office to initiate an investigation of all aquatic resources in the Park. The objectives included a basic inventory of the number and types of waters, analysis of angler exploitation and preparation of baseline data to enable future researchers to assess changes in habitats over time. In 1979, complete and abbreviated aquatic surveys were conducted on 8 lakes, bringing the total number of lakes surveyed thus far to 107. Additionally, water samples were collected from 14 previously surveyed lakes for analysis by a commercial laboratory (Table 15); these samples were necessary to increase understanding of the chemical nature of Park lakes.

Surveys were carried out from July through September, and two days were spent on each water. Although various methods have been used over the years to quantify data, overall results are reasonably comparable. Current methods are described in detail by Dean and Mills (1970); plankton enumeration since 1973 follows a method modified from McNabb (1960). Beginning in 1974, one water sample from each lake was given an extensive chemical analysis by a commercial laboratory.

Table 15. Chemical Characteristics of back-country lakes receiving a limited reconnaissance, Yellowstone National Park, 1979

	Basin Creek Lake		Crag Lake		Crescent Lake		Cymet Lake		Fan Creek Fire Pond		Gallatin Lake		Goose Lake		Grebe Lake		Grizzly Lake		High Lake		Fowler Creek Lake		Ripple Lake		Smaw Lake		Wolf Lake	
	5-10-79	6'	5-1-79	6'	9-1-79	6'	7-30-79	6'	9-1-79	6'	9-1-79	6'	10-12-79	6'	10-15-79	6'	10-21-79	6'	9-1-79	6'	10-16-79	6'	8-25-79	6'	10-16-79	6'	Outlet 1-16-79	
Water Temp. °C	14		13		12		—		8		—		17		8		6		17		11		—		11		—	
Spec. Cond. umhos/cm	220		18		22		—		42		—		110		59		119		35		05		—		1250		—	
Dissolved O ₂	—		—		—		—		—		—		—		—		—		—		—		—		—		—	
Total alk.	79		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		6		0		0		0	
Ca hardness	66		8		6		18		14		72		38		24		54		6		32		27		84		16	
Total hardness	85		6		9		16		16		20		74		20		54		8		24		24		30		17	
Total diss. solids	152		16		20		33		29		115		68		49		91		25		48		23		687		14	
Carbonate alk.	0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
Fluoride alk.	79		8		8		18		14		72		38		24		54		6		32		27		84		16	
Chlorides	0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
Bicarbonates	56		9.8		9.8		22		17		88		46		29		66		7.3		39		33		102		27	
Sulfates	51		17		2.7		23		9		7.9		9.7		49		28		6.2		7		60		22		27	
Chloride	<1		0.7		1.1		<1		2		1		2		<1		<1		0.8		0.7		<1		280		<1	
Sulfate	20		2		7		9		<1		5		4.2		8.5		12		6		2		6		26		6	
Fluoride	0.06		0.04		0.04		0.06		0.06		<0.06		0.12		0.34		1.5		0.06		0.14		0.04		6.5		0.02	
Iron	0.66		<0.06		0.66		0.19		0.75		<0.06		0.12		0.12		0.09		0.06		<0.06		0.06		1.7		0.12	
Potassium	0.7		0.6		0.9		1.2		3.6		0.3		2.9		2		1		2		0.3		1.1		8.9		1.5	
Magnesium	15		2		3		7		8		4.6		15.1		8		10		2		8		2		12		2	
Calcium	26		1.6		2.4		3.6		3.2		11		4.8		4.8		14		3.2		9.6		2.4		18		2	
Sulfate	4.6		0.5		0.7		1.7		1.9		11		3.4		1.9		4.4		0.5		1.9		<0.5		12		4.4	
Iron	3.9		<0.01		0.9		5.2		2.3		0.7		16		4.8		17		1.8		0.7		2.4		205		3.0	
Magnesium	0.07		<0.01		<0.01		0.2		<0.01		<0.01		0.08		0.05		<0.01		0.11		<0.01		0.04		0.17		0.14	
Calcium	<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05		<0.05	
Sulfate	<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1	
Silica	2.5		0.2		1.6		3.9		0.1		0.6		57		14		12		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1		<0.1	
Color (FTU)	0		0		0		75		14.0		0		0		0		0		5.8		1.1		0.75		46		1.9	
Transmittance (100)	1.5		0.5		0.75		0.9		1.4		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0		0	
pH	5.6		9.6		5.7		15		76		2.4		8		4.8		3.1		16		11		9.4		6.4		1.5	
Dissolved silica	<0.03		<0.06		<0.06		0.03		0.06		<0.06		0.12		<0.06		0.06		<0.06		<0.06		<0.06		9.7		6.6	
Electrical Conductivity	1.46		0.09		0.44		2.35		1.3		0.55		0.18		1		0.1		0.1		0.14		1.1		1.7		<0.03	
Sulfate	0.03		0.01		0.01		<0.01		0.09		0.01		0.01		0.08		0.02		0.01		0.01		0.01		0.04		0.04	

* Field measurements, all others made by commercial laboratory.

Table 15. Physical characteristics of each-country lakes in Yellowstone Park, 1959.

Lakes	Location 1)	Elevation		Surface area		Surface depth	Maximum depth	Average depth	Circumference	Sediment visibility		Tributaries (2)	Water quality
		meters	feet	hectares	acres					meters	feet		
Alfred	556.0E 493.0W	784	775	157	461	16.3	46	0.7	2.4	116,479	94.0	Yellowstone Lake	Yellowstone Lake
Beaver	510.0E 494.5W	7481	8140	70	19	3.6	9.3	3.0	12.4	142,701	146.8	Big Creek	Yellowstone Lake
Clear	513.7E 4918.4W	2374	7728	62	119	15.0	37	6.7	22.0	1,604,167	814	Yellowstone Lake	Yellowstone Lake
Grass	540.7E 4940.4W	1873	5930	26	64	5.3	13	1.4	4.7	75,174	51.7	AGTB	Yellowstone Lake
Glaze	572.4E 4911.0W	7552	9245	173	319	3.5	6.7	2.7	8.8	94,446	116.6	AGTB	Yellowstone Lake
Grass	512.7E 4945.2W	7337	7350	139	317	3.4	8.3	2.5	8.1	87,916	56.7	AGTB	Yellowstone Lake
Harriet	576.5E 4943.3W	2169	6993	59	124	4.2	10.3	1.3	4.1	52,665	45.1	AGTB	Yellowstone Lake
Lower Clear	512.7E 4933.0W	7249	7350	46	113	0.8	2	2.1	7	5	-	AGTB	Yellowstone Lake

1) Coordinates utilizing Universal Transverse Mercator 3000 meter grid system on USGS map, Yellowstone National Park, 4420-5100N/5948E, 1961.

2) By calculation from pure maps, excepting Yellowstone National Park, 15 min. series, 1:62,500.

3) Estimates from maps and aerial photos for those lakes without floating buoys.

4) Estimates from bathymetric map in Arnold and Sharpe (1957).

5) Not surveyed.

Table 17. Chemical characteristics of back-country lakes surveyed in Yellowstone National Park, 1979

	Beach Springs Lake		Dewdrop Lake		Duck Lake		Goose Lake		Glade Lake		Gooseneck Lake		Harlequin Lake		Upper Gooseneck Lake	
	6' 8/7/79	Inlet 8/7/79	6' 8/29/79	6' 8/29/79	6' 8/15/79	6' 8/15/79	6' 8/30/79	6' 8/30/79	6' 8/29/79	6' 8/29/79	6' 8/11 - 12/79	Inlet 8/11 - 12/79	6' 10/12/79	6' 10/12/79	6' 8/11 - 12/79	Inlet 8/11 - 12/79
Water temp. °C*	25	44	15	19	19	18	18	18	12	19	20	18	11	22	22	33
Spec. Cond. μmhos*	470	760	30	25	25	1750	1750	10	72	130	112	112	70	70	110	110
pH*	6.0	7.0	6.5	6.8	6.8	10.4	10.4	7.2	7.0	7.2	7.8	7.2	5.25-5.5	7.8	7.8	8.0
Dissolved O ₂ *	3.0	—	6.8	7.2	7.2	0	0	0	6.5	6.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
Pheno. alk. %**	0	0	0	0	0	227	227	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total alk**	48	420	4	12	13	1093	1093	30	4	42	60	65	11	45	45	70
Ca hardness**	38	450	4	13	13	30	30	4	4	23	60	55	19	17	17	50
Total hardness**	108	760	10	17	17	174	174	10	10	25	65	60	25	19	19	75
Total diss. solids	290	760	18	20	20	1500	1500	24	24	115	65	60	57	110	110	75
Carbonate alk.	0	0	0	0	0	444	444	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bicarbonate alk.	48	4	4	12	12	649	649	10	0	42	11	45	11	45	45	70
Carbonates	0	0	0	0	0	271	271	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bicarbonates	59	0	4.9	15	15	1333	1333	12	0	51	55	55	14	55	55	70
Hydroxides	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carbon dioxide	39	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Chloride	1	0	519	159	159	1.4	1.4	0	41	54	54	58	2.956	58	58	75
Sulfate	170	0	6	1	1	54	54	9	0.9	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1	<1	75
Fluoride	0.36	0	0.61	0.06	0.06	4.5	4.5	9	0.04	5	5	2	18	2	2	75
Phosphate	0.16	0	<0.06	0.03	0.03	1.2	1.2	0.06	0.06	0.43	0.43	0.19	0.87	0.19	0.19	75
Potassium	9.6	0	0.5	1.3	1.3	21	21	0.6	0.6	2.4	2.4	2.5	3.5	2.5	2.5	75
Hg hardness	70	0	6	4	4	144	144	6	6	2	2	2	6	2	2	75
Calcium	15	0	1.6	5.1	5.1	12	12	1.6	1.6	9.4	9.4	7.6	7.6	6.9	6.9	75
Magnesium	17	0	1.5	1	1	35	35	1.5	1.5	0.5	0.5	1.5	1.5	0.5	0.5	75
Sodium	48	0	1.4	2.1	2.1	460	460	0.7	0.7	14	14	13	13	13	13	75
Iron	0.1	0	0.09	0.03	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.1	0.1	0.01	0.01	0.22	0.22	0.09	0.09	75
Manganese	<0.05	0	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	75
Copper	<0.1	0	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	<0.1	75
Silica	19	0	2.6	3	3	2.5	2.5	3.1	3.1	26	26	29	29	<0.1	<0.1	75
Color (PCU)	0	0	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	75
Turbidity (NTU)	1.3	0	0.37	0.46	0.46	0.64	0.64	9.8	9.8	0.43	0.43	6.8	6.8	0.77	0.77	75
TOC	19	0	14	17	17	21	21	5.3	5.3	3.9	3.9	20	20	5.8	5.8	75
Ortho-phosphate	0.16	0	<0.06	<0.03	<0.03	<0.03	<0.03	0.06	0.06	0.37	0.37	0.62	0.62	0.16	0.16	75
Kjeldahl N	1.03	0	0.56	0.25	0.25	2.5	2.5	0.56	0.56	0.08	0.08	1.1	1.1	0.22	0.22	75
Nitrate N	0.2	0	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.22	0.22	0.04	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	0.04	0.04	75

* Field measurements, all others made by commercial laboratory.

** Field measurements for all inlets, others made by commercial laboratory.

Table 18. Qualitative checklist of aquatic plants collected during lake surveys, Yellowstone National Park, 1979

Species (common name)	Beach Springs Lake	Dewdrop Lake	Geode Lake	Gooseneck Lake	Harlequin Lake
<u>Chara</u> sp. (muskgrass)	X		X	X	
<u>Drepanocladus exannulatus</u> (Guemb.) Warnst. (an aquatic moss)		X			
<u>Hippuris vulgaris</u> L. (common mare's-tail)	X				
<u>Lemna minor</u> L. (water lentil)	X				
<u>Myriophyllum spicatum</u> L. (spiked water-milfoil)	X			X	X
<u>Polygonum amphibium</u> L. (water smartweed)	X				X
<u>Potamogeton alpinus</u> Balbis (northern or reddish pondweed)					X
<u>Potamogeton amplifolius</u> Tuckerman (large-leaved pondweed)				X	
<u>Potamogeton filiformis</u> Pers. (slender-leaved pondweed)			X		
<u>Potamogeton cramineus</u> L. (grass-leaved pondweed)				X	X
<u>Potamogeton pectinatus</u> L. (fennel-leaved pondweed)	X		X		
<u>Potamogeton pusillus</u> L. (small pondweed)					X
<u>Potamogeton richardsonii</u> (Sennet) Rybd. (Richardson's pondweed)	X				
<u>Potamogeton vaginatus</u> Turcz. (sheathing pondweed)			X		
<u>Sagittaria cuneata</u> Sheld. (Arrowleaf arrowhead, wapato)	X				
<u>Sparganium</u> sp. (bur-weed)	X				X
<u>Sparganium emersum</u> Rehn (simplestem bur-weed)	X				
<u>Sparganium minimum</u> Fries (small bur-weed)					X
<u>Utricularia vulgaris</u> L. (common bladderwort)	X			X	X

Table 20. Qualitative checklist of littoral and benthic invertebrates found in six back-country lakes, 1979

Taxon - Common name	Reach Springs Lake	Dewdrop Lake	Geode Lake	Glade Lake	Gooseneck Lake	Harlequin Lake
Mirudinea - Leeches	X	X	X	X		X
Oligochaeta - Aquatic earthworms	X					
Crustacea						
Amphipoda - Scuds						
<u>Hyalella</u> <u>artica</u>	X	X	X		X	X
<u>Gammarus</u> <u>sp.</u>	X				X	
Hydracarina - Watermites	X		X			
Insecta						
Collembola - Springtails	X			X		
Ephemeroptera - Mayflies						
Baetidae						
<u>Callibaetis</u>		X			X	
Caenidae						
<u>Caenis</u>	X					
Leptophlebiidae						
<u>Paralentoophlebia</u>					X	
Odonata						
Anisoptera - Dragonflies						
Aeshnidae						
<u>Aeshna</u>		X	X		X	X
Coruliidae						
<u>Cordulia</u>						X
<u>Soratochlora</u>		X				
Libellulidae						
<u>Sympetrum</u>	X	X	X			X
<u>Leucorrhinia</u>			X			
Zygoptera - Damselflies						
Lestidae						
<u>Lestes</u>			X			
Coenagrionidae						
<u>Ischnura</u>		X	X			
<u>Trallanda</u>					X	
Hemiptera - Truebugs						
Gerridae - Waterstrider						
<u>Gerrinae</u>	X	X			X	
Corixidae - Waterboatmen	X	X	X		X	
Notorectidae - Backswimmers						
<u>Notorecta</u>		X	X		X	X

continued on next page

Table 20. continued

Taxon - Common name	Beach Springs Lake	Dewdrop Lake	Geode Lake	Glade Lake	Gooseneck Lake	Harlequin Lake
Trichoptera - Caddisflies						
Phryganeidae						
Phryganea					X	
Limnephilidae		X		X		
Hesperophylax				X		
Coleoptera - Beetles						
Gyrinidae - Whirligig beetles						
Gyrinus			X			
Halipidae - Crawling water beetle						
Halipus	X					
Dytiscidae - Predaceous diving beetle						
Acilius		X				
Ancus				X		
Colymbetes		X				
Costatus	X	X				
Dytiscus	X					
Graphoderus		X				X
Diptera - Trueflies						
Lipulidae - Craneflies						X
Chironomidae - Midges	X	X	X		X	X
Chaoboridae - Phantom midges		X	X		X	
Gastropoda - Snails						
Helisoma	X					
Lymnaea	X					
Physa					X	
Pelecypoda - Clams						
Sphaeriidae		X			X	X
Number of taxa	16	18	13	5	15	11

BEACH SPRINGS LAKE

Located in the central portion of the Park, Beach Springs Lake lies within sight of the East Entrance Road approximately 7.2 km from Lake Junction. The lake can be easily reached by walking approximately 200 m overland from the road. A survey was conducted at Beach Springs Lake on August 7-8, 1979.

Physical

The geological deposits in the immediate area of Beach Springs Lake are dominated by sandy gravel sediments of beach and lake terraces approximately 3-10 m thick, and the gravel is primarily rhyolite and obsidian. The remainder of the drainage is characterized by hydrothermal explosion deposits which form a ridge around the north and east sides of Mary Bay of Yellowstone Lake. These sediments are often hard when dry but soft and plastic when wet. In the Beach Springs Lake drainage, deposits lie on varved silt or ice-dammed lake sand, and are covered with sandy silt containing volcanic ash (Richmond 1977).

The elevation of Beach Springs Lake (2,361 m) is approximately 4 m above that of Yellowstone Lake which is located several hundred meters to the south. The surface area of the lake was 16.3 ha and shoreline development was fair. Mean depth was only 0.7 m (Table 16). Maximum depth was recorded at 12.5 m, although this measurement may have been influenced by the presence of underwater springs in the deeper areas of the lake. Water temperature (25° C) remained constant from the surface to the bottom and suggested thermal enhancement. Both temperature uniformity and the sulfur odor in the area were assumed to be affects of the subaqueous springs.

Despite a deep green color, the lake was clear, and the secchi disc was visible to 2.7 m on an overcast day. Rooted vegetation was abundant, especially on the west end of the lake. Although rubble and small boulders occurred along the northeast shore, bottom sediments were mostly obsidian sand and gravel covered with various amounts of detritus and decaying plant material. Wind exposure was extreme, but signs of erosion were absent. Fluctuations in lake level appeared to be minimal (0.3 m).

Figure 4. Beach Springs Lake, Yellowstone National Park, 1979.

Groundwater was the primary water source of Beach Springs Lake and there is no outlet. Apparently most of the inflow is subaqueous, but one thermal spring flowed into the northwest corner of the lake (Figure 4). Although velocity was not measured, flow was estimated at less than 5 l/sec. The stream channel was approximately 0.3 m wide and bottom sediments were obsidian sand covered by a layer of silt. Channel banks were almost 0.6 m high and were vegetated by bulrushes (Scripus) and sedges (Carex). The water temperature was 44° C with a pH of 7.0. Neither aquatic insects or fish were observed in this tributary. Aquatic vegetation consisted mainly of muskgrass (Chara), but the water lentil (Lemna minor) was common near the lake.

Chemical

Ionic concentrations of the 1.8 m water sample indicated a sodium-sulfate type of water. Concentration of total dissolved solids (290 ppm) was over twice the mean for the Park back-country lakes, and conductivity (470 μ mhos) was three times the Park mean. Total hardness, magnesium and sodium appeared extremely high. This great concentration of chemical components is undoubtedly caused by the geothermal groundwater in the area. The sulfate content (170 ppm) was the highest yet recorded in Park lakes and further substantiates the geothermal influence. The pH (6.0) was slightly acidic and dissolved oxygen concentration (3.0 ppm) was very low (Table 17). Apparently the lack of dissolved oxygen is linked to the abundance of sulfur dioxide. Total alkalinity, bicarbonates, chloride, fluoride, phosphate and silica were among the few chemical measurements below average.

Aquatic Vegetation

Beach Springs Lake had the most diverse assemblage of aquatic plants yet found in Yellowstone Park. Eleven species of plants were collected from within the lake (Table 18), and at least six additional species were observed (but not collected) in the eulittoral and the supralittoral zones. Most of these plants were hardwater forms which are commonly found in waters with high sulfate concentrations (Hutchinson 1975b).

At least two species of sedges (Carex) were found in the eulittoral zone (0.3 - 0.9 m from the bank) along the southern shore and were common in both supralittoral and eulittoral zones of the northern shore; there was also a small wet meadow comprised of sedges at

the west end of the lake. Bulrushes (Scirpus) occurred in several isolated stands on the southern and western shores, and bordered the inlet. Several thick patches of cattail (Typha) bounded the east shore; young willows (Salix) were found in this area also. Horsetail (Equisetum) appeared sporadically in the eulittoral of the northern shore.

Muskgrass (Chara), spiked-milfoil (Myriophyllum spicatum) and common bladderwort (Utricularia vulgaris) completely covered the bottom with the exception of the less vegetated area at the east end of the lake. Although common maretail (Hippuris vulgaris) was found in some locations, it was less common. Water smartweed (Polygonum amphibium), simplestem burweed (Sparganium emersum) and arumleaf arrowhead (Sagittaria cuneata) were common emergents in the shallow waters around the lake. Terrestrial forms (Hutchinson 1975b) of smartweed and arrowhead were collected from the eulittoral also. Richardsons' pondweed (Potamogeton richardsonii) and funnel-leaved pondweed (Potamogeton pectinatus) were found in the more sparsely vegetated areas characterized by a sand substrate. Water lentil (Lemna minor) was locally common near the inlet.

Limnoplankton

Plankton diversity (12 genera) in the Beach Springs Lake tow sample was above average (9 genera) for Yellowstone back-country lakes ($n = 70$). The number of phytoplankton genera (8) was twice the Park mean, and the number of crustacean genera (2) was average; however, the rotifer diversity (1 genera) was below the Park mean (2 genera). Despite the high plankton diversity and about average densities for crustaceans, the densities for total zooplankton and phytoplankton were both well below average. The dip sample taken in the east end of the lake yielded similar results, although diversity was lower and densities were greater (Table 19).

Green algae and diatoms dominated the phytoplankton, including forms which are associated with more eutrophic waters such as Synedra, and the dinoflagellate Ceratium (Hutchinson 1967). It is quite interesting to note that the only cladoceran sampled (Ceriodaphnia) appears to fare best on a diet of flagellates. The rotifer, Karatella quadrata, is considered a widespread temperate form often associated with eutrophic waters (Hutchinson 1967).

The above average diversity, low densities and the predominance of genera and individuals of small size are all indicative of heavy grazing

on the plankton community by the redbside shiner (Richardsonius balteatus) population. The presence of the cladocerans, Ceriodaphnia, (a pond form) and Chydorus, a macroplanktonic genus, reflect the littoral nature of this shallow lake. The presence of a great deal of organic matter in both tow and dip samples may be due to water mixing by action of subaqueous springs and wind.

Littoral and Benthic Organisms

Macroinvertebrate diversity (16 genera) was far above average for Park lakes (11 genera) (Table 20). Water boatman (Corixidae) and scuds (Gammarus and Hyalella azteca) were the most abundant invertebrates in the littoral sample and were easily observed in the vegetated areas near shore. Larval and adult forms of predaceous diving beetles (Dytiscus and Coptotomus) were also quite numerous, as were water striders (Gerrinae) and snails (Helisoma and Lymnea). Several crawling water beetles (Haliplus) and dragonfly larvae (Sympetrum) were found in the dense vegetation. The mayfly Caenis, a collector-gatherer, was found in detritus and decaying plant materials. Although water mites (Hydracarina) are not generally found in acid lakes or associated with Chara (Pennak 1978), two species were collected from Beach Springs Lake. Springtails (Collembola) were collected in the littoral sample but were most numerous on decaying plant material in the eulittoral. Leeches (Hirudinea), midges (Chironomidae) and aquatic earthworms (Oligochaeta) were common in the benthic samples, and empty caddis fly (Trichoptera) cases were also numerous.

Aquatic Vertebrates

One smallmesh gillnet (overnight set) captured 102 redbside shiners and numerous salamanders (Ambystoma). Average length for 98 of the shiners was 112.8 mm (range 75-150 mm). The total weight was 14.3 g. The condition factor (K) estimated from the respective means was 0.996.

Age was determined for seven of the shiners using the scale method. The back-calculated lengths (calculated by direct proportion) were 38, 82, 104 and 124 mm for ages I-IV, respectively. The resulting age distribution was expanded to 98 shiners using an age-length key (Westerheim and Ricker 1978). The mean age of the sample was 3.0 years; 85% were age III+ or older.

Angler Use

Although litter was common in the vicinity of Beach Springs Lake, it is doubtful that it is associated with anglers. Since VFR cards from

the lake have never been received, it would appear that angling occurs only incidentally if at all. The location of a major road several hundred meters upwind probably accounts for a great deal of the litter.

Discussion

The absence of a flowing outlet from Beach Springs Lake has combined with the influence of the groundwater source to produce the rather concentrated (for Yellowstone Park) chemical character of this shallow lake. This concentration of nutrients and the extent of the littoral zone have undoubtedly influenced the great diversity of aquatic vegetation. The majority of these plant species are adapted to hard water conditions, and many have a tolerance for high sulfate levels.

The acidic (pH 6.0) nature of the lake is evident in the plankton collections. As in most acidic lakes in Yellowstone Park, diversity is high while densities are low. The shallowness of the lake is reflected in the meroplanktonic species which are commonly found in littoral zones. Heavy grazing by the redbreasted sunfish population also greatly affects the densities and size composition of the plankton community.

The redbreasted sunfish population appears to be healthy and thriving. Numbers, mean length and size range were greater than normally found in lakes with sunfish populations (Tanager, Sheridan and Winegar Lakes). Growth was excellent despite high densities indicated by somewhat depressed K factors and high catch per unit effort. Apparently the large amount of shallow water, absence of piscine predators, warm temperature and long growing season have all combined to enhance the existence of this littoral species.

The redbreasted sunfish is not native to Beach Springs Lake or even the greater Yellowstone Lake drainage. These fish were probably introduced by humans. Since this species is well adapted for life in a shallow, littoral environment, it has surely changed the native species composition and structure of this unique aquatic ecosystem. Unfortunately, the cost of removal would be exorbitant, and the chances of successfully eliminating the sunfish are small. Additionally, such a treatment might have negative effects of its own.

Currently the marsh-like qualities of this productive environment combine with its location to provide an excellent wildlife viewing area for visitors traveling along the East Entrance Road. Fish predators such as the western grebe, osprey and great blue heron were observed during the survey. Waterfowl, including

over a dozen mallards, common goldeneye and bluewing teal, were quite obvious even to the casual observer, and shorebirds such as the killdeer and common snipe were also noted. Several muskrat lodges were found in the bulrushes at the west end of the lake. The lake is used annually by trumpeter swans as nesting area and bison utilize the surrounding area for winter range; small herds of bison in late spring and early fall often attract a great number of photographers and spectators.

DEWDROP LAKE

Dewdrop Lake lies at the headwaters of Bog Creek, a tributary to Sour Creek and eventually the Yellowstone River in Hayden Valley. The lake is located 12 km directly north of the Fishing Bridge Campground, but access overland would be quite difficult due to the lack of maintained trails in the area. The most direct approach would be following Sour Creek 4.0 km southeast from the Sour Creek pack trail, and then an additional 4.8 km upstream along Bog Creek to the lake. Dewdrop Lake received an abbreviated survey on August 28, 1979.

Physical

The surficial geology of the Dewdrop Lake drainage is dominated by deposits of glacial till from the Pinedale glaciation. This area is quite typical of surrounding valleys with smooth to hummocky surface deposits and undrained depressions. The fine grained humic alluvium which underlies the small wet meadow areas is comprised of a silt, sand and clay mixture (Richmond 1977). A layer of Lava Creek tuff located directly below the surficial deposits contains 1-5 mm phenocrysts of quartz, sanedine, and sodic plagioclase (Christiansen and Blank 1975).

At an elevation of 2,481 m, Dewdrop Lake has a surface area of 3.8 ha (Table 16). Maximum depth was 7.6 m with an average depth of 3.8 m. On a cloudy day the secchi disc was visible to 2.4 m in tea-brown water. Water temperature varied from 15° C at the surface to 5° C at 7 m. The lake was stratified with a thermocline occurring between 2.8-4.6 m.

The lodgepole pine covered hills around Dewdrop Lake appeared to provide substantial wind protection and there was no sign of bank erosion along the shoreline. Estimated lake level fluctuations were approximately 0.2 m. Shoreline development was good. The shoal substrate was comprised of decaying plant material while the profundal sediments were fine silt and organic detritus.

Since there were no inlets, groundwater appears to be the primary water source for Dewdrop Lake. Although U.S.G.S. maps and aerial photos indicate a possible outlet at the northeast corner of the

Figure 5. Dewdrop Lake, Yellowstone National Park, 1979.

lake, there was no outlet during the survey. The apparent stability of the lake level is indicative of a wet meadow-marsh type system with most water entering through subaqueous springs and some subterranean movement out of the system into the wet meadows at the head of Bog Creek.

Chemical

Dewdrop Lake is an extremely dilute lake (TDS: 18 ppm) (Table 17). Major ionic components were magnesium and sulfate, but only three components, CO₂, total organic carbon (TOC) and color, were above average for Park lakes. The increased values of both color and TOC are related to the concentrations of humic acids, and in conjunction with a slightly acidic pH (6.8), and the great amounts of decaying plant matter, suggest a bog or swamp type (dystrophic) water (Strumm and Morgan 1970). The levels of carbon dioxide (519 ppm) are almost six times greater than the Park average, and it is possible that this value is erroneous. It has been documented, however, that seepage lakes and lakes with organic acids often have excess amounts of carbon dioxide (Hutchinson 1975a, Ruttner 1963).

Aquatic Vegetation

Sedges (Carex) bordered the entire lake, and dominated the wet meadows at the northeast and southwest ends. Water lilies (Nuphar polysepalum) covered the surface of the lake in all areas less than 2 m deep (Figure 18). Aquatic moss (Drepanocladus exannuatus) was abundant over much of the bottom indicating substantial spring activity. The three other plant species collected from Dewdrop Lake could not be positively indentified because of the lack of mature individuals; however, two of these plants appeared to be burweed (Sparganium) and spike-rush (Eleocharis).

Limnoplankton

Although the number of phytoplankton genera (2) was well below average (4 genera) for Park back-country lakes, the number of rotifer genera (3) was one above the mean and crustacean diversity (2 genera) was normal. Overall plankton diversity (8 genera) was somewhat below average (9 genera) and overall densities were greatly reduced. Crustacean numbers were slightly above the norm, but densities of all other plankton were low (Table 19).

The armored dinoflagellate, Ceratium, was the dominant phytoplankton form, but Dinobryon, an oligotrophic yellow-green alga, was found in small numbers. Among the rotifiers, Polyarthra, a predator capable of eating large prey, was the most abundant. The appearance of Holopedium gibberum is significant; this species has rarely been collected in Yellowstone Park and because of its large size, suggests that the lake is barren of fish. The large number of Chaoborus is also indicative of a fishless system.

Littoral Organisms

With 18 taxa represented in the littoral sample alone (Table 20), macro-invertebrate diversity was among the highest yet encountered in the Park lakes. Scuds (Hyalella azteca) and clams (Sphaeriidae) were the two most common forms sampled, although water boatmen (Corixidae) and backswimmers (Notonecta) were extremely abundant. One damselfly (Ischnura) and three dragonflies (Aeshna, Somatochlora, and Sympetrum) were common in decaying plant debris. Densities of a caddisfly grazer (Limnephilidae) were high, but numbers of Callibaetis, a quiet-water mayfly, were low. Water striders (Gerrinae) were locally abundant and the densities of phantom midges (Chaoboridae) and midges (Chironomidae) were surprisingly high for a littoral sample. Phantom midge numbers would suggest that fish do not occur in the lake as does the observance of free-swimming leeches (Hirudinea). The presence of four genera of predaceous diving beetles (Acilius, Colymbetes, Coptotomus and Graphoderus) may represent the greatest diversity of this group yet encountered in Park lakes. One giant (25 mm) Graphoderus was observed with a leech in its mouth. The number of genera of this predaceous form, and especially the presence of Graphoderus, definitely support the contention that Dewdrop Lake is barren of fish life.

Aquatic Vertebrates

Gillnets were not set in Dewdrop Lake, but the presence of fish is doubtful. Stocking records show that they were never introduced and the lack of a water entrance route would preclude their historical occurrence. Even if fish had been introduced, salmonid spawning habitat is totally lacking and overwinter survival might be questionable due to the large amount of decaying organic debris. No salamanders (Ambystoma) were observed and other biological factors suggest they may be absent also.

Angler Use

Difficulty of access would undoubtedly limit angler use even if fish were present. No VFR cards have ever been returned (1973-1979) and signs of human presence were totally absent.

Discussion

Dewdrop Lake has the characteristics of a dystrophic or bog type lake. Chemically, it is one of the most dilute lakes yet surveyed, but levels of color, TOC and pH were indicative of high humic acid content. Carbon dioxide values are usually higher in dystrophic lakes, although levels may have also been influenced by the presence of subaqueous springs.

As in many dystrophic waters, pond lilies covered the surface in shallow waters. Because of its dependence on carbon dioxide as a carbon source in photosynthesis, the presence of aquatic moss is indicative of subaqueous spring activity. The lack of plant life stages advanced enough for positive identification is extremely curious considering that the lake was surveyed in late August. Apparently the combination of dilute water, cold temperatures and insufficient light (forested hills surrounding the lake probably limit the daily illumination to 8 hours even in midsummer) all contribute to the slow development of aquatic plants.

The low plankton diversity and densities are attributable to the nutrient paucity of Dewdrop Lake. The presence of a large plankton forms is indicative of the absence of fish. The great diversity of littoral macro-invertebrates supports this theory, and the great diversity of predaceous diving beetle may additionally suggest the lack of salamanders.

Frogs were the only other animals observed during the survey. Signs of human visitation were totally nonexistent. One submerged log showed signs of ancient beaver activity, but there were no additional cuttings in the surrounding forest. It would appear that this unproductive lake has evolved in the absence of major aquatic vertebrates and has thus developed a distinctive invertebrate community. Other than a lack of forest fires due to fire suppression policies over the past century, man has apparently had little effect on this unique ecosystem.

DUCK LAKE

Duck Lake is situated approximately 0.3 km from the West Thumb of Yellowstone Lake at an elevation of 2,374 m (Table 16). Although historically barren of fish, the lake was stocked with cutthroat trout in 1903, 1905, 1906 and 1912. In 1908, 2,000 landlocked salmon (Salmo sebago) were planted in an attempt to establish this species in Park waters. A final introduction of 35,575 brown trout was made in 1938 (Fromm 1941). When Arnold and Sharpe (1967) surveyed Duck Lake in 1966, they found that brown trout were present and apparently reproducing adequately. Although there was no direct connection between the two lakes, the possibility of introduction of brown trout into Yellowstone Lake remained because of the short distance separating them. Consequently, Duck Lake was treated with rotenone on September 23, 1967, in an attempt to eliminate this exotic species.

In the following year, three 36.6 m experimental gillnets were set overnight, and no trout were captured. The effectiveness of the operation was later reexamined when one 38 m experimental and a 30.5 m smallmesh gillnet were set overnight on September 28-29, 1971. Once again, no fish were captured or observed.

Duck Lake was resurveyed in a greatly abbreviated form on August 16-17, 1979. The objective of this operation was to substantiate extirpation of the brown trout population and to collect additional baseline limnological data on Duck Lake.

Chemical

Duck Lake was classified as a dilute lake on the basis of its low nutrient concentration (TDS = 20), and the predominant ions were calcium and bicarbonate (Table 17). With a pH of 6.8, chemical constituents were well below the Park average for back-country lakes. Only carbon dioxide (159 ppm) and total organic carbon were above average, but carbon equilibrium calculations (Rutner 1963) suggest the possibility of error in the carbon dioxide measurement. This dilute nature is typical of lakes with rhyolitic drainages.

Limnoplankton

The plankton sample reflects the nutrient-poor conditions which prevail (Table 19). Only the number of rotifer genera (3) were above the Park average (2 genera). Although the number of crustacean genera (2)

was average, the extremely low number of phytoplankton genera (2) brought plankton diversity (6 genera) well below the Park mean of 9 genera. It is somewhat curious that the dinoflagellate Ceratium is often associated with more eutrophic environments, but it is indicative of the cosmopolitan nature of the genera collected in Duck Lake.

Plankton densities in this dilute water were extremely low. The number of phytoplankton/liter, zooplankton/liter and total plankton/liter were all well below average and definitely suggest a minimal level of production.

Aquatic Vertebrates

Eight largemesh and two smallmesh gillnets set overnight captured three salamanders (Ambystoma sp) and no fish. Apparently Duck Lake maintains a fishless condition.

Angler Use

Duck Lake is used as the culinary water supply for West Thumb and is closed to angling.

Discussion

Duck Lake is a dilute lake typical of its association with rhyolitic deposits. The effects of the nutrient paucity are definitely reflected in low productivity. The Trophic State Index (TSI) for phosphorus (Carlson 1977) indicates that this lake may be one of the most unproductive lakes in the Park.

Mean depth (6.7 m) also contributes to lowered production. Of the smaller Park lakes (< 20 ha), only Crevice Lake has a greater mean depth (17.8 m). The Morphoedaphic Index (MEI) of Ryder (1965) utilizes TDS (mg/l) and mean depth (m) together as an index to potential fish production. The MEI for Duck Lake (2.953) is the lowest yet obtained for Park lakes, and potential fish yield (Ryder et al 1974) was only 1.65 kg/ha. The small size and poor condition of the brown trout population reported by Arnold and Sharpe (1967) are not surprising in light of these depressed production estimates.

Arnold and Sharpe (1967) did not report the presence of salamanders in 1966, and it is doubtful they could coexist in this environment with the extremely predacious brown trout. Although current densities are extremely low, it is possible that they may populate Duck Lake now that the brown trout have been removed. Salamanders are common in fishless lakes in the Park.

GEODE LAKE

Geode Lake lies in the northern portion of the Park within 0.8 km of the Yellowstone River near the Black Canyon. It is accessible overland by foot or horse, but there is no maintained trail. The lake was reached by traveling approximately 2.4 km down Geode Creek from the point it passes under the Tower-Mammoth road (9.6 km from Tower Junction) and then following the dry outlet drainage (#0876) several hundred meters east from its junction with Geode Creek. The lake was surveyed on August 29-30, 1979.

Physical

Like much of the area in the vicinity of the Black Canyon, the Geode Lake drainage is associated with Precambrian schist and gneiss and the lake apparently lies over this type of substrate. The southern portion of the drainage is comprised of Lost Creek Tuff of trachyte-rhyodacite which contains fragments of Precambrian rocks. A steep basalt cliff rises from the northern shore of the lake (Prostka et al 1975).

The lake lies in a confined basin almost surrounded by steep hills with only two narrow gaps at the east and west ends. Most of the drainage is covered by Douglas fir forest with scattered Engelmann spruce and juniper. Lichen-covered talus from the basalt cliffs along the northern shore are void of higher forms of plant life.

The surrounding hills provide fair wind protection for Geode Lake, and there was no sign of bank erosion along the shore. Lake level appeared to fluctuate almost 0.8 m. Shoreline development of this irregular shaped lake was very good.

The average depth of Geode Lake was only 1.4 m with a maximum depth of 3.4 m (Table 16). The secchi disc was visible in the dark brown-green water to the bottom (3.4 m) on a partly cloudy day. The lake was essentially homothermic (17.8°C) ranging only 0.2°C from the surface to the bottom.

Most of the substrate along the northern shore was rubble and boulder with very little vegetation. The narrow west end of the lake had a moderate layer of decaying plant material and detritus. Most of the remainder of the shallow water substrate was comprised of sand and

Figure 6. Geode Lake, Yellowstone National Park, 1979.

gravel with a thin layer of organic detritus and larger decomposing plants. Deep water sediments were fine silt and organic detrital matter.

The fluctuations in lake level suggest that Geode Lake is dependent on snowmelt as a water source. There was a small grassy gully on the southern shore through which water may be directed to the lake during runoff; however, there was no defined inlet channel. At high lake level some water may apparently depart at the west end of the lake into Geode Creek (Figure 6). The vegetation suggested moist conditions in this area, but there was no defined channel.

Chemistry

The concentration of chemical constituents (TDS: 1400 ppm) for this sodium-bicarbonate type lake is definitely unique among Park waters. Values for conductivity, phenolphthalein alkalinity, total alkalinity, TDS, carbonate alkalinity, bicarbonate alkalinity, carbonates, sodium and dissolved oxygen were all the highest yet reported in the Park. Most other components were far above the mean for back-country lakes. Among the constituents which were below average were sulfates, fluoride, iron, manganese, silica, carbon dioxide and phosphate (Table 17).

Although the extreme nature of these measurements is partially due to the concentrating effect of negligible flow-through, the relationship among the components is related to the solubility of rocks in the watershed. Three nearby lakes (Crevice Lake, Little Trumpeter Lake and Trumpeter Lake), which have drainages heavily influenced by schist and gneiss, displayed similar results. These lakes also had restricted flow-through and high chemical concentrations.

Aquatic Vegetation

The level of solutes in Geode Lake was definitely reflected in the aquatic vegetation. Species diversity was low, with only four species of submerged aquatic plants and two species of marsh plants (helophytes). All of these plants are well adapted for hardwater environments, and the submerged species are capable of using bicarbonates as a carbon source in photosynthesis (Hutchinson 1975b).

Of the helophytes, the bulrush (Scirpus) was by far the most common. This species forms a border around the entire lake except for sections of the northern shore and several isolated portions of the southern shore where the rubble-boulder substrate discouraged plant growth. Bulrushes were especially thick at the west end and sections of the northern shore where they grew in a 3-6 m wide band. Cattails (Typha) occurred near the outlet and in a few other isolated areas around the lake.

Muskgrass (Chara) covered most of the bottom except where the substrate was rocky. Slender-leaved pondweed (Potamogeton filiformis) occurred sporadically throughout the lake with a heavy concentration near the outlet. Fennel-leaved pondweed (Potamogeton pectinatus) and sheathing pondweed (Potamogeton vaginatus) were abundant in the shallow water near shore (Table 18).

Limnoplankton

Plankton diversity (11 genera) was above average for Park lakes (Table 19). The number of rotifer genera (3) was above the Park mean (2 genera) as was the number of crustacean genera (3), and phytoplankton diversity (4 genera) was average.

Although crustacean densities were much above normal, rotifer numbers were low so the number of zooplankton/liter was only average. Phytoplankton densities were well below the norm.

Significant among the phytoplankton was the collection of Spirulina, a blue-green alga which has a hyperhaline form. Geode Lake is the only place Spirulina has been collected in the Park to date. The presence of Ceratium and Mougeotia would also be expected in this eutrophic environment, but the remainder of the plankton are quite cosmopolitan. The appearance of planktonic Chaoborus and increased densities of Diaptomus suggest a fishless condition.

Littoral and Benthic Organisms

The number of taxa collected from Geode Lake (13) was above average for Park waters (11 taxa) (Table 20). Although most of these forms are widely distributed, the appearance of free-swimming leeches (Hirudinea) and large numbers of phantom midges (Chaoborus) is usually limited to lakes barren of fish. Scuds (Hyalella azteca) were probably the most common invertebrate in the littoral sample; however, two species of water mites (one bright orange and the

other black) were very numerous. Waterboatmen (Corixidae) and back swimmers (Notonecta) could be seen darting through submerged vegetation. Three species of dragonflies (Anisoptera) and two species of damselflies (Zygoptera) were collected from organic debris. Phantom midges, midges (Chironomidae), dragonflies and damselflies were abundant in benthic samples.

Aquatic Vertebrates

One largemesh and one smallmesh gillnet set overnight captured 32 salamanders (Ambystoma sp.), but no fish were found. According to stocking records, fish have never been planted in Geode Lake. Even if they had been introduced or gained entry naturally, it is doubtful they would be successful in Geode Lake. Lack of spawning habitat would inhibit salamonid species, and it is unlikely fish could overwinter in this shallow lake.

Angler Use

Both the lack of VFR returns from the lake and the absence of signs of human visitation suggest a total lack of angler use on Geode Lake. Since there are no trails in the vicinity, human presence in the area is probably rare.

Discussion

Geode Lake is the most chemically concentrated lake yet sampled in Yellowstone Park. The dominance of schist and gneiss in the watershed and the lack of flow-through are believed to be the primary factors involved in this nutrient concentration. The aquatic plants and some plankton species found in the lake are especially adapted for life in hardwater environments.

Apparently the salamander is the only vertebrate species. The presence of free-swimming leeches, large numbers of phantom midges and the salamanders definitely indicates a fishless condition. It is doubtful that fish could survive and reproduce in the lake even if they had gained entry historically, either naturally or by man's intervention.

The marshy aspect of this small lake did attract waterfowl. During the survey six common goldeneye, a bluewing teal and a coot were observed on the lake. In the past, the lake has been reported as a common nesting area for trumpeter swans (Dean et al 1975), but none were seen during the survey. Brewer's blackbirds were numerous and probably utilized the bulrushes and cattails for nesting areas. Historical beaver activity was evident in nearby forest areas, but no fresh sign was noted. It would appear that aside from fire suppression activities, man has had little impact on this unique ecosystem.

GLADE LAKE

Glade Lake is situated in a cirque basin at the base of Mt. Shurz in the southeast corner of the Park. There are no maintained trails in the area, and the most likely access would be overland by foot or horse up the Beaverdam Creek drainage. The lake was surveyed in an abbreviated manner on August 27, 1979.

Physical

At an elevation of 2,952 m, Glade Lake is the highest lake in Yellowstone Park. The surficial geology of the drainage is dominated by talus and avalanche debris on the upper slopes. A glacial till of rock fragments in a silty matrix occupies the lower portions of the cirque basin near the lake. The surficial deposits are greatly influenced by the andesitic nature of the bedrock in this area. Rhyodacite plugs have produced many of the peaks in this portion of the Absaroka Range, which forms the eastern boundary of the Park (Richmond and Pierce 1972).

Although most of the upper portions of the surrounding watershed are quite rocky, there are some areas of alpine tundra near the ridges. The vegetation of the lower portion consists of grassy meadows with scattered stands of mixed conifers (Engelmann spruce, subalpine fir and whitebark pine). This sparse vegetation affords virtually no protection from the strong mountain winds.

The lake was quite turbid during the survey giving the water a milky-green color. Apparently recent wind and/or runoff conditions had produced this effect since aerial photos indicate clear, dark green water. Erosion along the northeastern shore suggested substantial wave activity. Secchi disc visibility was 0.9 m on a partly cloudy day, and water temperature (12.2°C) varied only 0.2°C from surface to bottom. Average depth was 2.7 m with a maximum of 4.6 m (Table 16).

The shoreline development was poor for this small (3.5 ha), rather circular lake. Water level appeared to fluctuate approximately 0.3 m. Shoal substrate was primarily sand and gravel with scattered amounts of rubble and boulders along the northeast and west shores. Most of these sediments were covered with a thin layer of fine silt. Although a benthic sample was not taken in the profundal zone, it

Figure 7. Glade Lake, Yellowstone National Park, 1979.

appeared that substrate in the deeper waters was fine silt-clay.

The inlet stream (#0185) was dry during the survey, but it was evident that it was periodically subjected to torrential flows. The channel was approximately 1 m wide and 0.3 m deep, and the substrate was comprised of rubble and gravel. The gradient was very steep except for the lower several hundred meters where the channel formed a small braided delta at its junction with the lake. Several short channels (~30 m), which ended in dry springheads, apparently provide additional water sources during wet periods (Figure 7).

Only a trickle of water was flowing in the outlet stream (#0185). The channel extended about 25 m past the lake before dropping approximately 100 m down a sheer cliff into the valley below. The average depth of this small channel was only 0.1 m and substrate was rubble and boulders in a coarse conglomerate.

Chemical

The water of Glade Lake (TDS: 24 ppm) was extremely nutrient poor. The water was neutral (pH: 7.0) and primary ions were calcium and bicarbonate typical of andesitic watersheds. Although dissolved oxygen was about average and carbon dioxide was slightly above the mean, most constituents were well below the norm for Park lakes. The level of fluoride was the lowest yet found in the Park. The only anomaly to this extreme paucity was the nitrate level, which reached a new maximum for back-country waters.

Aquatic Vegetation

No aquatic vegetation was found in Glade Lake. Apparently the rocky nature of shoal substrates is unfavorable for plant growth. Additional contributing factors may include the lack of wind protection, the extreme winter conditions and associated short growing season. A similar situation was found at Lake #1072 (above Trilobite Lake) which also occurs in a near-alpine lake basin.

Limnoplankton

Plankton diversity (4 genera) was among the lowest reported for Park back-country lakes. Although crustacean diversity was average (2 genera), the number of rotifer genera (1) was below average (2 genera) and the number of phytoplankton genera (1) was far below the mean (4 genera). Densities were all much below average.

One notable aspect of the plankton collection from Glade Lake was the total lack of predators (Table 19). The rotifer (Keratella cochlearis) and the two crustaceans (Daphnia and Diaptomus) are all herbivores. The large size of the individuals of the two crustacean genera is also noteworthy and is indicative of a fishless ecosystem. The presence of Ceratium is curious since it is usually associated with eutrophic situations, but it probably attests to its wide adaptability in Park waters.

Littoral Organisms

Aquatic macroinvertebrate collections were limited to littoral areas in Glade Lake (Table 20). Diversity was quite low (5 genera) and forms commonly associated with aquatic vegetation were totally absent. The presence of free-swimming leeches (Hirudinea) is usually associated with lakes without fish. The predaceous diving beetle (Agabus) may be the top predator in the system. Little is known about springtails (Collembola) but they are apparently omnivorous scavengers. The two caddisflies (Phryganea and Hesperophylax) are grazers which pick-up algae, fungi and some invertebrates at random (Pennak 1978).

Aquatic Vertebrates

Gillnets were not set at Glade Lake, but it is assumed that it would be impossible for fish to survive in this nutrient poor, near-alpine environment. There are no records of fish plants in Glade Lake, and the outlet stream is definitely a barrier to natural fish movement.

Angler Use

No VFR cards have been returned from Glade Lake, and there are no signs of angler activity. In fact, it is doubtful that humans visit this area except

very rarely. There are no maintained trails anywhere in the vicinity and the approaches to the lake are limited and quite rigorous.

Discussion

Glade Lake has the unique distinction of being the highest lake in Yellowstone Park. Additionally, the geological substrates in this area and apparent periodic high flow-through have combined to produce one of the most dilute lakes in the Park. The harsh living conditions associated with life at this altitude and the nutrient-poor condition of the lake are definitely reflected in the biological properties of the system.

Although the lack of aquatic vegetation may be closely linked to unsuitable substrate conditions, the previously mentioned factors must also influence their absence. Diversity and densities of plankton and macroinvertebrates were extremely low. The great size of crustacean plankton, the presence of free-swimming leeches and the lack of fry and fingerlings attest to the fishless condition.

It is likely that few humans have ever seen Glade Lake. The high mountain ridges surrounding this cirque basin are extremely awesome, and the lake definitely represents an extreme in aquatic existence. Bighorn sheep were observed moving around the peaks but there were few signs of other animals in the area. Other than technical rock climbing, access to the area is limited, and has undoubtedly aided in the preservation of this unique, delicately balanced, near-alpine aquatic ecosystem.

GOOSENECK LAKE

Gooseneck Lake occurs in the west-central portion of Yellowstone Park at an elevation of 2,237 m. A preliminary survey conducted in 1969 reported a healthy population of rainbow trout (Dean and Mills 1970). Access is limited to travel by foot or horse for approximately 2 km south from Goose Lake on the Fountain Freight Road and then west on the Fairy Falls trail. From the point where the lake's outlet stream (#1536) crosses this trail (0.5 km west of the road), it is only 0.3 km to the lake along well-used game trails. On August 11-12, 1979, the lake was surveyed in order to gather additional information necessary for more thorough understanding of the ecology of the lake and its exotic fish population.

Physical

Rhyolitic bedrock from the West Yellowstone flow dominates the geology of the Gooseneck Lake drainage. Surficial deposits of glacial till from the Pinedale glaciation are comprised mostly of rhyolite and generally lack morainal form (Christiansen and Blank, Jr. 1974). A small area of alluvial deposits of rhyolite gravel and obsidian sand is located southwest of the lake. Fine grain humic alluvium underlies the wet meadow area along the inlet stream (#1542) from Upper Gooseneck Lake.

The Gooseneck Lake basin lies in a narrow depression opening into a wet meadow near the inlet at the south end. Steep hillsides rise almost directly from the shoreline on the remainder of the lake. The sparse forest which covered these slopes was dominated by lodgepole pine with scattered subalpine fir and Engelmann spruce. Since prevailing winds were from the south, the exposure to wind blowing down the narrow drainage was substantial, but there were no signs of erosion along the lake shore.

This small (3.4 ha) lake had an average depth of 2.5 m and a maximum depth of 3.7 m. The lake was not stratified at the time of survey with water temperature varying from 19.4°C at the surface to 18°C at the bottom (3.7 m). The secchi disc was visible in the olive-green water to 3.2 m on a partly cloudy day (Table 16).

Figure 8. Gooseneck Lake, Yellowstone National Park, 1979.

The elongated shape of Gooseneck Lake provided good shoreline development. The shallow water substrate was primarily obsidian sand and gravel with varying amounts of decaying plant materials and detritus. Silt and detrital ooze were the dominant substrate materials in deeper waters, although decaying organic matter was also prevalent.

The inlet stream (#1542) was heavily influenced by spring activity in the wet meadow through which it descended from Upper Gooseneck Lake. Flow was 18 l/sec and appeared to be quite stable. The substrate of this small, low gradient stream was comprised of fine sand with occasional accumulations of silt. Decaying plant materials were common in the marsh near the lake. Additional ground water from subaqueous springs was indicated by the presence of bubbles in various parts of the lake.

A well established beaverdam at the outlet was covered with terrestrial grasses (Figure 8). The presence of dead trees standing in the water near the outlet suggested a gradual buildup near the outlet as a result of beaver activity through the years. The gradient of the outlet stream (#1536) is low and the substrate is comprised of obsidian sand and gravel. An eventual tributary to Goose Lake, stream #1536 has numerous undercut banks, and productivity appears to be high despite shade from the forest canopy. Flow was only 8 l/sec at the time of survey.

Chemical

Chemical analysis of a 1.8 m water sample indicated that Gooseneck Lake was a sodium-bicarbonate type lake. The concentration of dissolved solutes (TDS: 115) was slightly below normal for Park back-country lakes. Although most constituents were just below the mean, values for chloride, sulfate, magnesium hardness and magnesium appeared extremely low (Table 17). Only fluoride, silica, carbon dioxide and ortho-phosphate were above average. The value of fluoride (5 ppm) was one of the greatest yet recorded for Park lakes.

Aquatic Vegetation

Of the emergent vegetation, sedges (*Carex*) and bulrushes (*Scirpus*) were most common (Table 20). Sedges formed a 1-2 m border along the east shore

but were only scattered on the drier western side of the lake. Along with bulrushes, they dominated the marsh-wet meadow at the south end of the lake. Bulrushes lined the shore of the inlet stream (#1542) for approximately 0.2 km above the lake in the vicinity of an active springhead. Cattails (Typha) occurred in scattered patches on the eastern shoreline of the lake, but only one group was found on the west shore.

Pond lilies (Nuphar polysepalum) and large-leaved pondweed (Potamogeton amplifolius) were scattered along the eastern shoreline with concentrations near the outlet and inlet marsh. Muskgrass (Chara), common bladderwort (Utricularia vulgaris) and spiked water-milfoil (Myriophyllum spicatum) were common in areas with accumulations of organic debris. Another unidentified plant was collected from the southern portions of the lake only. Muskgrass and grass-leaved pondweed (Potamogeton gramineus) were both common in the inlet stream (#1542).

Limnoplankton

Plankton diversity (10 genera) was slightly above the Park mean of 9 genera (Table 19). Both phytoplankton (5 genera) and crustaceans (3 genera) were one genus above their respective means, while the number of rotifer genera (2) equaled the Park average.

Plankton densities were below average, although the number of rotifers per liter was normal and helped to raise zooplankton densities close to the Park mean. Phytoplankton densities, however, were much below normal.

Of the three crustacean zooplankters, the presence of Ceriodaphnia is most often indicative of fish predation. The low densities and small individual sizes of zooplankton forms are commonly associated with the presence of fish. The occurrence of the diatom, Tabellaria, is probably associated with the high levels of silica. Although the filamentous green algae, Mougeotia and Tetraspora, are commonly eutrophic forms, they are also found in more nutrient poor environments with high flow-through such as beaver ponds.

Littoral and Benthic Organisms

Diversity of macroinvertebrates (15 taxa) was well above the Park mean (10 taxa) (Table 20). Scuds (Hyalella azteca and Gammarus) were quite numerous and distributed through the littoral portions of the lake

as were water boatmen (Corixidae) and backswimmers (Buenoa).

At least three different forms of water striders (Gerrinae) were scurrying across the water surface among the bulrushes. Damselfly larvae (Enallagma) were common, and along with two forms of dragonfly larva (Aeshna and Libellulidae), were collected from decaying plant debris. The occurrence of quiet water larvae such as the mayfly, Callibaetis, and the other caddisfly, Phryganea, was expected, but another mayfly, Paraleptophlebia, a free-ranging species of running water, would not normally be found in a lentic environment. Although phantom midges (Chaoboridae) were not collected in the plankton sample, they were present in small numbers in the littoral zone. The benthic sample was comprised mostly of clams (Sphaeriidae), midges (Chironomidae) and snails (Physa), although scuds also occurred in these collections.

Aquatic Vertebrates

A total of 34 rainbow trout were captured in a single smallmesh gillnet set overnight. Sizes ranged from 99-380 mm, with a mean length of 178 mm. Mean weight was 90 g and average condition factor (K) was 1.18.

Back-calculated lengths of 17 trout indicated rather slow growth with 43, 126, 222 and 353 mm for ages I-IV, respectively. An age-length key (Westerheim and Ricker 1978) was used to expand age estimates for 29 fish. About 76% of the sample were age II+, 20% age III+, and only 3% age IV+. No young-of-the-year or yearlings were captured, but they were observed in the inlet stream.

Angler Use

There is no maintained trail to Gooseneck Lake; however, the presence of fish has been documented for almost 40 years and some fishing is known to occur. Since no VFR cards have been received between 1973-1979, angling use is probably minimal and restricted to "local" anglers who are employed in or near the Park. Litter and other signs of human visitation were minimal, but the remnants of an old foot bridge or wooden raft were found near the outlet.

Discussion

The Gooseneck Lake basin may have been formed prior to habitation by beaver, but the occurrence of dead lodgepole pine still standing in shallow waters suggests that the lake level has risen in the past

century. Grass growing on the dam and the presence of old beaver cuttings on the forested hillsides are evidence of long-term beaver occupation. Only one beaver was observed during the survey, but there are abundant signs of current activity.

Although the nutrient levels of the lake are only slightly below average for Park back-country waters, the chemical constituents definitely reflect the rhyolitic nature of the drainage substrate. The above average value of carbon dioxide is probably linked to the influence of groundwater, in the form of both surface and subaqueous springs. The high level of fluoride is also common from groundwater and is most often associated with igneous rocks such as obsidian (Hem 1970).

The physical and chemical characteristics of Gooseneck Lake have interacted with the biological factors to influence various aspects of the flora and fauna. Although the aquatic macrophytes were all common species, their distribution within the lake appeared to be associated with substrate differences. High silica concentrations undoubtedly benefit the planktonic diatom. The lack of phytoplankton development and the occurrence of filamentous green algae is probably linked to the high flow-through character of the lake.

The exotic rainbow trout population has had a significant effect on the plankton of Gooseneck Lake. Both low densities and small individual size indicate intensive grazing. Although the cladoceran, Ceriodaphnia, may have been present prior to the introduction of trout, it is often commonly found cohabitating with fish species. The absence of the phantom midge (Chaoborus) from the plankton sample is also linked to the presence of fish.

Since the Firehole Falls prevented all upstream movement of native fishes, Gooseneck Lake was historically barren of fish. According to stocking records, 5,975 rainbow trout fingerlings from the hatchery at Ennis, Montana, were introduced to the lake in 1940. Because there are no barriers on the outlet stream (#1536), it is possible that trout also ascended from Goose Lake which was first stocked in 1939.

Current results confirm most of the preliminary conclusions concerning the exotic trout population (Dean and Mills 1970). The average condition factor (K: 1.18) is high and indicates a robust population with ample food. The distribution of sizes and the age structure of the gillnet sample in conjunction with the observations of the fingerling trout in the inlet stream (#1542) suggest that reproduction is adequate.

Although growth, as indicated by back-calculated lengths, appears to be reduced for ages I+ and II+ since 1969, these differences are more likely due to differences in sampling and aging technique.

The fish population in Gooseneck Lake appears to be quite stable and capable of sustaining continued low levels of exploitation. Because of the lake's small size, however, it is doubtful the population could support a significant increase in angler use without deterioration of the stock. The lack of older and larger trout may indicate that anglers are already having a substantial impact, but may also suggest downstream migration of larger individuals to Goose Lake. Sharpe and Arnold (1967) reported two distinguishable growth patterns in Goose Lake rainbow trout, thus lending support to the latter supposition. Although the rainbow trout are exotic to the system, removal of this population by chemical rehabilitation does not seem to be practical.

HARLEQUIN LAKE

Harlequin Lake is located in the west-central portion of Yellowstone Park at an elevation of 2,100 m. The lake can be easily reached by traveling 0.8 km from the trailhead which lies about 2.4 km west of Madison Junction on the West Entrance Road. The lake was surveyed on August 8-9, 1979.

Physical

Geologically, the Harlequin Lake drainage is dominated by Lava Creek tuff at higher elevations and Mount Jackson rhyolite closer to the lake. Surficial deposits include large amounts of rhyolitic talus rubble along the steep slopes on the north side of the lake with rubble veneer and rhyolitic scree deposits further uphill. Small areas of glacial till and stream fan gravel are almost exclusively rhyolite. A fine grain humic alluvium underlies the wet meadow areas around most of the lake.

Low forested hills almost surround the lake although the talus slopes along the north shore are primarily bare. The forest was comprised of lodgepole pine with a whortleberry (Vaccinium scoparium) understory. Wind protection was moderate, and there were no signs of erosion around the shore.

The surface area was 4.2 ha, and the average depth was only 1.3 m (Table 16). The maximum depth was 3.4 m and water level fluctuation was approximately 0.3 m. Secchi disc visibility was 1.2 m in tea-brown water on a partly cloudy day. Temperature varied from 21.1° C at the surface to 15.5° C at the bottom (3.4 m). Temperature change was the greatest between the surface and 0.6 m, but there was no indication of stable stratification.

Despite a somewhat circular shape, shoreline development of this small lake was good. Shoal substrates were obsidian sand and gravel with varying (100-600 mm) amounts of decaying plants and detritus. Deep water substrate was a silt-detritus muck with decaying plant matter.

Ground water from both surface and subaqueous springs provided the primary water source for Harlequin Lake. About half of the west shore and all of the northern and eastern shores were bounded by wet meadows from which many short channels enter the lake. Several longer channels with active springheads were located at the base

Figure 9. Harlequin Lake, Yellowstone National Park, 1979.

of the talus slope on the north side of the lake (Figure 9). The occurrence of subaqueous springs was indicated by the presence of an unidentified aquatic moss covering much of the bottom in deeper areas; bubbles were also seen rising to the surface in some portions of the lake.

There was no flowing outlet at the time of survey, but several channels joined in a desiccated pond in the wet meadow at the east end of the lake. A single channel continued through the meadow which gradually disappeared about 100 m below the lake. From there the ground rose and vegetation changed to terrestrial species. This grassy area became very narrow with forest on both sides and then descended gradually into a small, dry snowmelt channel which extended under the West Entrance Road. The outlet does not join this channel as indicated by the USGS 15 minute quadrangle map.

Chemical

Harlequin Lake was classified as a sodium-sulfate water (TDS: 57 ppm) (Table 17). This type of water is uncommon in Yellowstone Park, and other lakes of this type (Beach Springs Lake and Turbid Lake) are much more concentrated chemically. All of these lakes, however, are characterized by abundant spring activity.

The brown color and low pH (5.25-5.5) indicate a dystrophic condition with associated accumulation of humic acids. With few exceptions, chemical components were far below average for Park waters. Depressed values with a high concentration of total organic carbon (TOC: 20 ppm) are common in dystrophic lakes. The above normal concentration of potassium and fluoride are undoubtedly due to the rhyolitic influence in the lake drainage. Although phosphate levels were about average, extremely high values for ortho-phosphate suggests that most phosphorus is tied up in humic acids (Carlson 1977).

Aquatic Vegetation

As in many dystrophic lakes, aquatic vegetation was abundant (Table 18). Sedges (Carex) were plentiful in the west meadow and bordered the entire lake. Bulrushes (Scirpus) were clustered at several points along the west shore and near the outlet. Cattails (Typha) were also numerous at the outlet, and one small area at the west end of the lake.

Pond lilies (Nuphar polysepalum) dominated the water surface, and only deeper waters toward the center of the lake were open. The most abundant plants of the littoral area were the common bladderwort (Utricularia vulgaris) and burweed (Sparganium). Water smartweed (Polygonum amphibium), northern pondweed (Potamogeton alpinus), grass-leaved pondweed (Potamogeton gramineus) and small pondweed (Potamogeton pusillus) were also common throughout the littoral. An unidentified aquatic moss (Musci) was collected in benthic samples from the deeper portions of the lake. Spiked watermilfoil (Myriophyllum spicatum) was uncommon, and small burweed (Sparganium minimum) was limited to the area near the outlet. All of these plants are quite eurytopic, with tolerance for acidic conditions.

Limnoplankton

Although many acidic lakes display a higher than normal plankton diversity, the number of genera (8) was one below average for Park lakes. The number of crustacean genera (1) was also one below normal, but phytoplankton and rotifer diversity were average (Table 19). Another anomaly was the high plankton density. Although the number of crustaceans was very low, rotifer densities brought the number of zooplankton/liter far above the mean. Phytoplankton numbers were about average for Park lakes.

The armored dinoflagellate, Ceratium, dominated the phytoplankton but filamentous green algae (Spirogyra and Zygnema), and a planktonic green alga (Closterium), also appeared in the sample. Zooplankton samples were dominated by rotifers (Filinia and Keratella cochlearis).

The occurrence of a large number of phantom midges (Chaoborus) in the plankton sample suggests the absence of fish. This large dipteran is usually not found when fish are abundant, but often occurs as the top predator when they are not.

According to Hutchinson (1967), a plankton community dominated by Ceratium is classed as a eutrophic dinoflagellate community; however, he also states that it is sometimes indistinguishable from an oligotrophic dinoflagellate community. Rotifers are quite eurytopic, and their dominance in the zooplankton may attest to their ability to survive in habitats which limit other plankters. This may also explain the occurrence of usually eutrophic forms of filamentous green algae.

Littoral and Benthic Organisms

The number of macroinvertebrate forms (11) was just above the Park mean (10 taxa) (Table 20). Scuds (Hyalella azteca and Gammarus) were the most abundant littoral organisms, but backswimmers (Notonecta) were also quite common. Although the appearance of clams (Spaeriidae) in such acidic water may seem strange (because shell structure materials are sparse), they are common in many acidic waters in the Park. Pennak (1978) states that the Spaeriidae are well adapted for acidic conditions. Of the three dragonflies collected, one (Aeshna) was a climber often associated with dense vegetation, one (Cordulia) was among those most often associated with sand-silt substrates and the third (Sympetrum) was a sprawler which occurs on many bottom types (Pennak 1978). The occurrence of the crane fly (Tipulidae) is probably associated with the large amount of decaying plant material which it shreds during feeding. Benthic invertebrates were extremely sparse, and only midges (Chironomidae) and dragonflies were collected.

Free-swimming leeches (Hirudinea) were observed and easily collected throughout the littoral zone. Although leeches are ubiquitous in Yellowstone lakes, free-swimming forms are usually limited to fishless waters. It has been noted also that the extremely large (25 mm) predacious diving beetle, Graphoderus, is apparently limited to fishless waters also. This beetle performs a top littoral predator role in the absence of fish.

Aquatic Vertebrates

One smallmesh gillnet set overnight yielded 84 salamanders (Ambystoma) but no fish were captured. The lack of a connection to the Madison River prevented the natural occurrence of fish in Harlequin Lake.

Angler Use

Although no VFR cards have been returned from Harlequin Lake (1973-1979), an occasional angler may visit the area. According to the trail register, between 66-69 people have visited the lake annually in the past two years. Although none of these people stated fishing as an objective, undoubtedly some adventurous individuals have tested their skills on this fishless water.

Discussion

Harlequin Lake is a classic example of a dystrophic lake. Its brown color and acidic nature are due to the great concentration of humic acids. The large amounts of organic detritus and decaying plant materials are closely associated with these key factors.

Chemically, the lake displays the typical characteristics of dystrophic lakes. Concentration of most chemical properties was far below the Park mean. High levels of TOC and ortho-phosphate are commonly found in lakes which are strongly influenced by humic acids. The association of ground water with the volcanic substrate probably accounts for above average values for fluoride and potassium and the dominance of sulfate among the anions.

The biological characteristics of the lake are also typical of dystrophic lakes. Aquatic vegetation was abundant. Most of the lake surface was covered by floating leaves of pond lilies, and six other plant species covered the entire littoral zone. Because of its dependence on free carbon dioxide as a carbon source for photosynthesis, the collection of an aquatic moss in the benthic sample suggested the presence of subaqueous springs.

Planktonic diversity was low, and the sample was dominated by common Park forms. The above average densities and presence of some forms usually associated with more eutrophic environments may be due to a "stagnation" effect associated with the lack of outflow.

Macroinvertebrates from the littoral samples were all widely distributed forms. The collection of three types of dragonfly larvae reflects the presence of great amounts of organic debris. Occurrence of free-swimming leeches, phantom midges and Graphoderus, a large predacious diving beetle, confirm that the lake is barren of fish.

It appears that salamanders are the only aquatic vertebrates in Harlequin Lake. The lack of a viable connection with the Madison River precluded the historical entry of fish, and although planting records indicate 11,500 grayling were introduced in 1937, the lake remains fishless. Although some fish species might be able to use the spring areas for spawning, overwinter survival in this shallow, vegetation-choked lake is questionable.

The marshy habitat of the wet meadow, which is often associated with dystrophic lakes, supports a community of non-aquatic wildlife

forms. The occurrence of an active beaver colony at Harlequin Lake is significant and interesting. Several different beaver were observed moving about the three beaver lodges on the lake. Although beaver have been observed in many back-country lakes in the Park, this represents one of the largest concentrations reported to date. Other animals observed during the survey included a trumpeter swan (it has been a frequent nesting area in the past), a common snipe, two broods of bluewing teal, frogs, toads and muskrats. For the casual visitor who hikes the short distance into Harlequin Lake, the lake offers the opportunity to observe and photograph these wildlife forms in a pristine environment.

UPPER GOOSENECK LAKE

At an elevation of 2,240 m, Upper Gooseneck Lake is located in the west-central portion of the Park. The outlet stream (#1536) flows northward for approximately 0.8 km before emptying into Gooseneck Lake. Access was gained by following this stream from Gooseneck Lake. A brief survey was made on Upper Gooseneck Lake on August 12, 1979.

Physical

The geological characteristics of the Upper Gooseneck Lake are similar to those of Gooseneck Lake. Rhyolitic bedrock is exposed on much of the lower portions of the drainage, and glacial till at higher elevations is primarily rhyolitic debris. Alluvial deposits of rhyolitic gravel and obsidian sand border the west side of the lake. Fine grain humic alluvium underlies wet meadow areas (Christiansen and Blank 1974).

The lake basin is surrounded by low hills with a sparse lodgepole pine forest; trees were especially scant on slopes on the west side of the lake. A small wet meadow lies at the southwest corner of the lake. Despite generally poor wind protection, signs of erosion were absent.

This 0.8 ha lake had the appearance of a large spring. The water was extremely clear with a light blue-green color, and the bottom was visible from all points along the shore on a cloudy afternoon. Although depth was not measured, the maximum appeared to be approximately 1.8-2.4 m. Surface temperature was 22° C.

Shoreline development was fair. Bottom sediments were primarily a gray-green, clay-silt muck with fine organic detritus. Although the substrate appeared generally uniform throughout the lake, sediments were a reddish-beige near the outlet and along the south end. It is unknown whether this color was due to precipitates from sub-aqueous springs or accumulations of algae, either alive or decaying.

One small tributary flowed from a hot spring for approximately 100 m in a 0.6 m wide channel. Flow of this shallow (25 mm) stream was estimated at less than 7 l/sec, and the substrate was fine gravel and sand. Water temperature was 33° C, and the pH was 8.0 (Table 17).

Additional ground water entered from springs and seeps all along the southern shore. Subaqueous springs were also observed at the south end of the lake. Temperatures varied among the springs, but steam was rising from the area around the southeast shore.

The outlet stream (#1542) was flowing through a sand-gravel channel approximately 0.6 m wide. Gradient was low and the pool:riffle ratio was about 1:1. Average depth was approximately 125 mm. There were no barriers to fish movement from Gooseneck Lake. Despite a moderate outflow (estimated 10 l/sec), water level of the lake appeared to be quite stable.

Chemical

The chemical composition of this sodium-bicarbonate lake was almost identical to that of Gooseneck Lake (Table 17). Dissolved solutes (TDS: 110 ppm) were slightly below the Park mean for back-country lakes, and chloride, sulfate, magnesium hardness and magnesium values were extremely low. Fluoride, silica and carbon dioxide were much above average.

Aquatic Vegetation

Sedges (Carex) formed a border around all but the west shore of the lake. Buirushes (Scirpus) were scattered near the outlet and in the meadow at the south end of the lake. No other aquatic plants were observed, but some filamentous green algae was noted.

Littoral Organisms

Although macroinvertebrates were not collected, observations of the more common forms were recorded. Backswimmers (Notonectidae), caddisflies (Trichoptera) and snails (Pelecypoda) were the most abundant littoral invertebrates and water mites (Hydracarina) and waterstriders (Gerridae) were also present.

Aquatic Vertebrates

Although gillnets were not set, several fish were observed darting about in shallow water, and fingerlings were found in the outlet stream. Presumably these were rainbow trout which may have been residents or migrants from Gooseneck Lake.

Angler Use

Despite the presence of fish and the easy access from Gooseneck Lake, it is doubtful this small lake receives much angler use. The clear water and lack of cover probably severely limits the number of trout in the lake, but it probably doesn't winterkill. Signs of human presence were absent and VFR cards have never been returned from Upper Gooseneck Lake.

Discussion

Upper Gooseneck Lake and Gooseneck Lake are alike in several ways, but there are also sharp contrasts. The geology of the drainages are almost identical and the physical characteristics of the respective basins are also quite similar. Because Upper Gooseneck is a major water source for the lower lake, chemical resemblance was expected. Ground water for both lakes flows through similar rock types and may come from the same sources.

Production is much higher in the lower lake, and it supports a healthy rainbow trout population. The bluish cast and lack of aquatic vegetation suggest a low level of production in the upper lake. The lack of cover undoubtedly affects its potential fish production. Although several species of macroinvertebrates were observed, both diversity and densities appeared low.

The reasons for these differences are open to speculation. Perhaps periodic high temperatures due to geothermal influents and solar radiation on this small, shallow lake prevent the establishment of a stable plant community. Since chemical parameters are almost identical, it is doubtful that this factor affects production. Winterkill is not likely because of the spring influence, and even if it did freeze completely, many organisms are capable of enduring such conditions in a dormant form.

Reasons for the contrast in productivity of these two lakes remains a mystery. This anomaly does lend a uniqueness to Upper Gooseneck Lake, however, and provides a challenge for future research.

LEWIS LAKE TRIBUTARY INVENTORY

Lewis Lake is situated in the south-central portion of the Park at an elevation of 2,371 m. At its northwest end, the Lewis-Shoshone Channel (i.e. Lewis River) serves as the lake's major inlet. In late July, 1979, a cursory visual survey was conducted on the tributaries to the channel and along the lakeshore.

Lakeshore Tributaries

Although several small spring-fed streams were observed around the lake shore, only stream No. 1924 and a small unmapped stream on the west shore of the lake were flowing (Figure 10). Stream No. 1924 originates as a thermal spring (temp = 48.9° C+) located approximately 6.4 km upstream from the lakeshore. It travels at a moderate to low gradient over a rubble, boulder and bedrock substrate. Near the mouth, the stream moves sluggishly over a muck and gravel bottom, aquatic vascular plants and algae are abundant and the temperature is a cool 13.3° C. A few small brook trout were observed in the lowermost 3.2 km.

The other flowing stream, No. 1932, originated from a small spring only 274 m from the lakeshore. Even though the bottom was mostly muck, unidentified trout fry were numerous throughout.

The remaining tributaries around the lakeshore were either thermal (No. 1929 at 36.7° C) or stagnant and cut-off from the lake by extensive sandbars (Dogshead Creek, which is No. 1935, and No. 1940). Since a school of redbreast shiners were observed in No. 1940 and several adult trout were seen in Dogshead Creek, these creeks must connect with Lewis Lake during spring runoff.

Channel Tributaries

Three small streams were observed emptying into the channel: Nos. 1944, 1946 and Summit Creek (No. 1948). No fish were seen in 1944, but brook trout adults and fry were noted in 1946, and brown trout and redbreast shiners were observed throughout Summit creek. Stream 1944 had a muck bottom, low flow and marshy appearance with an average width of 0.3 m. Stream 1946 flowed over a bedrock, gravel and boulder substrate for only 91 m before abruptly ending in a spring. Above the spring, a dry streambed suggested that the stream serves as a larger tributary during spring runoff. During the survey, Summit Creek ended approximately 0.4 km from the mouth. Since a sandbar enclosed the stream 274 m upstream from the lakeshore, the creek was generally stagnant and much of the gravel substrate was covered with algae.

Figure 10 . Lewis Lake tributaries, 1979.

- STREAMS:**
- Annual
 - Perennial
- PAVED ROAD**
- DIRT ROAD**
- TRAIL**
- HOT SPRING**

0 1 2 3 4
KILOMETERS

NONCONSUMPTIVE USE OF AQUATIC AREAS

Levels of human use at the Fishing Bridge and LeHardy's Rapids areas were determined from April 22 to October 18, 1979. An estimated 167,400 and 13,000 individuals visited the bridge and the rapids, respectively. These individuals spent approximately 30,200 and 2,345 man-hours, respectively.

Estimated use of the Fishing Bridge area in 1978 must be corrected from 134,710 visitors and 24,303 man-hours to 137,640 visitors and 24,830 man-hours, due to refinements in methodology. The 21.6% increase in use in 1979 is partially due to increased effort in measuring use, but undoubtedly also represents a real increase. Although total Park visitation was down 28% in 1979 from 1978, summer weather was warmer and more pleasant. Pleasant weather is undoubtedly the most significant factor determining levels of use of these areas.

No estimate of use at the rapids was made for 1978 due to insufficient data. The estimate for 1979 is considered to be a minimum. The problem with data from the rapids is that it is extremely variable. Use is partially from tour bus stops and naturalist guided trips originating from Fishing Bridge Visitor Center. Levels of use other than these two are low but fairly constant. The reasons for this are that there are no signs indicating the location of the rapids, and the white water cannot be seen very well from the road. Some visitors are directed to the rapids from various visitor centers, but large numbers of visitors occur only as a result of tour buses or naturalist trips. Because of the highly variable nature of the data, the estimate was made from only those days when counts were made (no extrapolation was done).

Two terms can be used to describe this type of human use: "Visit" - one person spending time at one of the sites which is comparable to "trip" in angler census terminology and "visitor" - one person participating in one or more visits which is comparable to "angler" in angler census terminology. Examples of how these terms are used in this instance: If two folks visit the bridge, then also visit the rapids, we have 4 visits and 2 visitors; if two folks visit the bridge and two different folks visit the rapids, we have 4 visits and 4 visitors; or if one person visits the bridge once and the rapids 3 times, we have 4 visits and 1 visitor. The difference here is the number of visits per visitor. Those numbers in the 3 examples above are 2, 1 and 4, respectively. In creel census data, the number of trips per angler is usually greater than 2, and its extremely important to know when making estimates and expansions.

The way in which this applies to the bridge and the rapids is that if one assumes one visit per visitor then the figures for the bridge and rapids can be added for an estimate of 180,400 visitors and visits. If we assume that everyone who visited the rapids also visited the bridge then we have 167,400 visitors, 180,400 visits and 1.08 visits per visitor. The latter case is probably very close to reality. The rapids are hard to find and a special effort must be made on part of the visitor to see the area, and a person making such an effort would likely stop at the bridge also. Two sources of error would tend to balance themselves, i.e. rapids visitors who didn't visit the bridge and folks who visit the bridge or rapids more than once.

We consider the levels of nonconsumptive use of aquatic areas to be highly significant and extremely important. In terms of numbers of persons Fishing Bridge alone received, more nonconsumptive use was sustained than the entire Park received in numbers of anglers. An estimated 8.8% of all Park visitors stopped at Fishing Bridge in 1979.

LEHARDY'S RAPIDS

Monitoring of the cutthroat trout spawning run in the catch-and-release section of the Yellowstone River continued in 1979. Weekly sampling was conducted between May 21 - August 6, 1979. Procedures remained unchanged from previous years (Varley et al 1976 and Jones et al 1978).

Results and Discussion

A total of 576 cutthroat trout were captured including 5 subadults. The mean total lengths and weights for 334 adult males and 237 adult females were 394 mm and 514 g, and 371 mm and 431 g, respectively (Table 21). Differences between sexes in mean total length and weight were significant again in 1979. No other fish species were observed.

In 1979, the mean lengths of adult males and females, and all adults increased sharply over all previous years (Figure 11). Since 1974, there has been an increasing trend in the mean lengths of trout sampled (Figure 11). This increase coincided with a notable increase in the percentage of trout over 406 mm in length (Figure 12). and appears to be a direct result of the catch-and-release regulation implemented in 1973.

The mean weights of both adult males and females in 1979 were the highest recorded since sampling began (Table 21). The mean weight of adult males increased 56 g over the previous year while females had an increase in mean K factor from all previous years; the mean K factor for females remained the same as in 1978.

In 1979, the sex ratio of adult males to adult females was 1.4:1. This is a change in the ratio from 1978 and represents the greatest proportion of males yet recorded at LeHardy's Rapids. Male: female ratios greater than 1:1 have been common in the LeHardy's sample since 1974. This is quite different from other tributaries to Yellowstone Lake, such as Clear, Cub and Pelican Creeks, where ratios since 1945 have been comparatively lower (between 0.59:1 - 0.74:1) (Jones et al 1979, Jones et al 1978 and Ball and Cope 1961). On Yellowstone Lake, several different size and creel limits have been implemented and discarded since 1945, but none of these changes have notably affected the M:F ratio. It would appear then, that the change in sex ratio now observed at LeHardy's Rapids is linked to the cessation of harvest under the current restrictions.

Figure 11. Average lengths for the entire season for adult males, adult females and all adults, LeHardy's Rapids, 1974-79.

Figure 12. Percentage of trout greater than 406 mm, LeHardy's Rapids, 1974-79.

Figure 13. Average age of all adults captured at LeHardy's Rapids, 1974-79.

Table 21. Total number and average length, weight, and condition factor of cutthroat trout for each year sampled at Lehardy's Rapids, Yellowstone River, 1974-77.

Year	Adult Males			Adult Females			All Adults			Immatures & Subadults			
	Number captured	Avg length (mm)	Avg weight (g)	Number captured	Avg length (mm)	Avg weight (g)	Number captured	Avg length (mm)	Avg weight (g)	Number captured	Avg length (mm)	Avg weight (g)	Avg k factor
1974 ¹⁾	177	375	394	244	352	339	463	362	363	43	177	60	0.939
1975	338	385	451	426	359	363	775	370	401	40	205	118	1.041
1976 ²⁾	531	384	431	423	362	360	964	375	359	29	173	71	1.643
1977 ³⁾	133	382	429	111	362	370	245	373	402	7	250	139	0.665
1978	399	386	458	358	364	413	759	375	437	68	169	62	0.956
1979	341	371	501	237	371	431	574	385	480	8	225	122	0.913

¹⁾ Due to erroneous measurements, fish were deleted from average weight and k factor calculations only as follows: 6 males and 2 females from 1974, 1 male and 2 females from 1976, and 1 male and 1 female from 1977.

Ages were determined on 136 of the cutthroats using the scale method (Laakso and Cope 1956) and were then fitted to an age-length key to expand ages for the entire sample (Kimura 1977). The average ages for adult males, adult females and all adults were 5.0, 4.5 and 4.8, respectively. These results represent sharp increases in mean age over previous years (Figure 13) and seem to be correlated with the sharp increases in mean length and the percentage of trout larger than 406 mm (Figures 11 and 12). This year, we also recorded age VII+ trout for the first time during the current sampling program. Although we have no historical age data on the Yellowstone River fishery, age VII+ fish have not been observed in the Yellowstone Lake fishery since the 1950's.

Conclusions

The following results found at LeHardy's Rapids appear to be linked to, or are consequences of, the catch-and-release regulation currently in effect on the Yellowstone River:

1. Since 1974, there has been an increasing trend in the mean length of trout sampled.
2. In 1979, we observed the highest lengths yet recorded for both adult males and adult females.
3. The proportion of adult males to adult females (1.4:1) has increased at LeHardy's Rapids since sampling began in 1974.
4. This year we observed the highest mean age yet determined as well as the reappearance of age VII+ fish.
5. The high mean age seems to be associated with the notable increases in mean length and the percentage of trout larger than 406 mm observed in 1979.

Recommendations

We recommend that regular weekly sampling be continued in 1980 to help verify the VFR average lengths and document continuing changes in the catch-and-release section. At this time, it is imperative to continue monitoring trends observed for mean length and age, and to positively document the reappearance of age VII+ fish in the population.

Figure 14. Length frequency of all adult cutthroat, Lellardy's Rapids, 1974-79.

PELICAN CREEK FISH TRAP

Pelican Creek is the second largest tributary to Yellowstone Lake and serves as a major spawning stream. Since 1976 the trap has been operated for the routine purpose of enumerating the trout spawning run, and for the experimental removal of the non-native longnose sucker population.

Fishing pressure in Yellowstone Lake is intense in the northern part of the lake. It has been found that "fish from all streams are caught in greatest numbers in their own arms of the lake. . . ." (Cope 1957). Pelican Creek is second only to the Yellowstone River at Fishing Bridge in importance to the northern stock for spawning habitat (Ball and Cope 1961, Benson and Bulkley 1963). Because of its large size and the presence of river stocks, the Fishing Bridge area is not presently being studied in terms of trout spawning runs or recruitment. Pelican Creek spawning runs are being interpreted as a reflection of the status of the northern stock of cutthroat trout. In 1979, the trap was operated for the additional purpose of studying the growth characteristics of suckers.

Method

Following initial installation of the trap in May, 1979, a large hole eroded under the floor. No attempt was made to enumerate the upstream run because of high water and trap damage.

On June 25, a temporary weir was placed across the stream just upstream of the permanent weir. The hole under the floor prevented use of the permanent weir for the entire season. Frequent washouts reduced the efficiency of the temporary weir.

The downstream run of longnose suckers and cutthroat trout was incompletely enumerated. Length measurements were taken from the samples of both species. A sample of trout was tagged with numbered tags, opercle clipped and released. Another sample was mandible clipped and released. All trout that were tagged, were held overnight to reduce handling and tagging mortality.

Most suckers were destroyed including those with tags from 1974. Most of the male suckers which were tagged with numbered tags in 1977, and recaptured in 1979, were released. A small number were killed in order to check growth of the opercle bone since 1977.

The area of the fish trap was checked daily for bear tracks and none were found. Cleanliness procedures were observed as outlined previously (Jones et al 1977).

Results

Longnose Suckers

During the 37 days of operation, 6,992 suckers were handled. Most of the fish were removed from the population (6,789); a few males with numbered tags were allowed to survive to provide information on ageing and longevity in future years.

Downstream running males averaged 388 mm (n = 195). Downstream running females averaged 441 mm (n = 184) (Table 24). Average length for sexes combined was 417 mm. Suckers tagged in 1974 averaged 446 mm in 1979 (n = 221). Those male suckers which were tagged in 1977 and recaptured in 1979 grew from an average of 387 mm to an average of 410 mm (n = 123).

Number of suckers removed has reached a total of 38,391 since the program began in 1976 (Table 22).

Table 22. Number of suckers removed from Pelican Creek trap, 1976-1979

<u>Year</u>	<u>Number Removed</u>
1976	22,123
1977	1,745
1978	7,725
1979	6,789
Total	39,391

Cutthroat Trout

During the period of trap operation, 15,114 trout were counted through the downstream trap. The distal end of the mandible was clipped on 5,312 fish averaging 372 mm. This provided a marked sample to be used in a Yellowstone Lake trout population estimate (this report). Numbered tags were placed on 302 trout, averaging 378 mm (Table 24); scales were collected and the edge of the left opercle was clipped with a circular punch leaving a semicircular indentation, similar to the method used previously on longnose suckers (Jones et al 1978). Tagged trout were held overnight to minimize the effects of tagging mortality. Following overnight holding, six fish were determined to be suffering the ill effects of tagging; these were removed from the study, leaving 296 trout tagged, for immediate tagging and handling mortality rate of 1.99%.

One trout which was tagged on July 25 was found by an angler on Yellowstone Lake, August 4, near Plover Point. The fish was reported to have been dead for some time.

Numbers of spawners have fluctuated in recent years, but due to inefficient trap operation caused by high runoff problems and trap damage, conclusions are not forthcoming (Table 23).

Table 23. Numbers of cutthroat trout in upstream and downstream migrations in Pelican Creek in recent years

<u>Year</u>	<u>Upstream</u>	<u>Downstream</u>
1976	7,245*	10,022
1977	14,131	27,183
1978	11,291*	19,901
1979	-----	15,114

(* partial counts)

Discussion

The population of longnose suckers which was trapped at Pelican Creek is interpreted as "stray"; i.e., large adult fish which spawned elsewhere in previous years. This interpretation is indicated by the large average size of spawners. The situation, if the straying rate were extremely low, would be a drastically reduced average size of spawners the year following removal of the original spawning stock. Average size should remain low under conditions of continuing removal of all spawners. If spawners were removed only one year, average size would be expected to be greatly reduced the next year then slowly return to precontrol size in one life span or less.

At Pelican Creek, we see no difference in average size of sucker spawners in 1979 (Table 24), following three years of almost total removal of spawners. This indicates that straying rate is fairly high and recruitment rate is extremely low.

Various population estimates indicate a population of 200,000 in Yellowstone Lake prior to 1976. Although almost 20% of that population has been removed, no differences in density have been detected from gillnet studies. Schooling habit of suckers causes gillnet catches to be highly variable, and slight differences in density cannot be expected to be detectable.

Age and longevity studies will require one or more season of data. Preliminary results from studies of competition between young trout and young suckers indicated that there is little or none. The original reason for removal of suckers at Pelican Creek (i. e., to enhance trout spawning) appears to be obsolete in view of present knowledge. The possibility of slightly reducing the Yellowstone Lake population of suckers exists, but the worth and/or desirability of such an undertaking is questionable.

Table 24. Average lengths of fishes from Pelican Creek trap in recent years

<u>Year</u>	<u>Longnose Sucker</u>				<u>Cutthroat Trout</u>			
	<u>All</u>	<u>Female</u>	<u>Male</u>	<u>Tagged In</u>		<u>Upstream</u>	<u>Dowstream</u>	<u>Tagged</u>
				<u>1974</u>	<u>1977</u>			
1960						377		
1961						367		
1964						364		
1965						349		
1966						360		
1968						361		
1970	420	427	393					
1972	404	432	373					
1974	412	432	391	407				
1976	410	432	388	422		367		
1977	413	436	386	424		380		
1978	401	424	377	439	406		374	
1979	417	441	388	446	410		371	378

In 1979, work was accomplished preliminary to investigating age and growth characteristics of cutthroat trout as is being done with longnose suckers since 1977. Growth characteristics of cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Lake and Yellowstone River, as indicated by scales, have become suspect in recent years. Data from studies conducted at LeHardy's Rapids and Yellowstone Lake gillnetting can be interpreted as possibly indicating a more rapid rate of growth in males than females.

Recommendations

1. To continue studies of sucker age and longevity for one or more years.
2. To continue studies of trout age, longevity and spawner enumeration and continuing to collect data on sucker age and longevity when the opportunity exists.
3. To discontinue sucker removal.

CLEAR AND CUB CREEK CUTTHROAT SPAWNING RUNS

Clear Creek and Cub Creek both flow westward from the Absaroka Mountains and empty into Yellowstone Lake along the east shore approximately 1.6 km apart. Fish traps at the mouths of these streams have been operated annually since 1977.

The information currently collected at these traps is diverse. Spawner counts and length measurements, some of which date back to 1945, provide an excellent data base for analyzing long-term changes in the cutthroat trout population. Additional information has been collected concerning run duration, instream mortality and age composition of the runs. Investigation of the effects of density independent factors, such as water temperature and stream flow, also continues.

Methods

The upstream trap was installed at Clear Creek on May 22 and remained in operation until August 3. The trap box was open daily from 0800-2000 hrs. Ascending trout were tallied as they passed through a counting chute (Jones et al 1979) mounted on the upstream side of the trap box.

From May 22 - May 30, downstream migrants were passed over the weir with dipnets. Trout were captured from 1300-2400 hrs daily as they congregated above the weir. On May 31 a portable wooden trap was installed in the overflow channel and was operated daily from 0800-2400. In order to facilitate the handling of increased numbers of migrants, a second downstream trap was installed on the main weir on July 13. Beginning on July 2, downstream migrants were marked by the removal of the adipose fin. The downstream traps at Clear Creek were dismantled on August 3.

The upstream trap at Cub Creek was installed on June 8 and operated through July 19 from approximately 1300-1900 hrs daily. Trout were passed upstream with dipnets; lakeward migrants descended through a downstream release uncounted. After assembly of a downstream trap on July 20, both traps were attended from 0900-1700 hrs daily. Trout captured in the downstream trap were marked with a right mandible clip. On July 27, both traps were removed for the season.

During peak runoff, it was again necessary to remove grates from both weirs. At Clear Creek the weir was out for one 24 hr period (May 28) and three additional overnight periods (May 25-27). At Cub Creek there were two 24 hr periods (June 15-16) and two additional overnight periods when grates were removed.

Fish sampling procedures were identical for the upstream and downstream traps at Clear Creek. Weekly samples of 100 spawners were collected from each trap for length and weight measurements. Scales from a subsample of 20 trout from these collections were used for age determination. Additional scale samples were taken as needed to provide data for the population extremes. Length frequency data (5 mm intervals) were collected from 75 trout daily.

Sampling was limited to the upstream run at Cub Creek. Daily samples of 25 trout were utilized for length and weight measurements. Scales were collected from five of these fish for age determination. Daily length frequency samples of 75 spawners were also collected at Cub Creek.

A maximum-minimum thermometer was used to obtain daily water temperatures at Clear Creek. On May 31, a staff gauge was installed approximately 400 m upstream from the weir. Gauge readings were taken several times daily throughout the season to monitor the pattern of stream discharge. A total of 41 flow measurements were taken at a transect near the gauge and these data were fitted into a level-flow prediction equation.

Bear activities were monitored daily at each trap. Campsites near both streams were closed to minimize the chance of visitor encounters with bears. Cleanliness procedures were strictly followed (Jones et al 1978).

Results

Clear Creek

A total of 58,244 cutthroat trout were counted through the upstream trap at Clear Creek. The number of migrants fluctuated greatly during the first 30 days (May 22 - June 21) varying from 1,194 (May 23) to 3 (June 19) (Figure 15). Over 81% of the run (47,360) ascended from June 22 - July 9. After July 9, the run gradually dwindled to an average of 5 fish per day during the final 7 days (July 27 - August 2).

Figure 15. Pattern of daily temperature (air and water), cutthroat spawning migration, and flow, Clear Creek, 1979.

Mean daily water temperature generally increased through the season and ranged from 1.7° C (May 29) to 14.7° C (July 26). Stream discharge fluctuated greatly during the early weeks of the run, but generally declined after reaching peak flow (6.7 m³/sec) on June 13. Rapid increases in the number in the upstream migration coincided with increasing temperatures and decreasing flows (Figure 15).

Mean total length and weight of upstream cutthroat trout were 393 mm and 533 g, respectively, and the average condition factor (K) was 0.87. The male:female ratio was 0.52:1. Average total length and weight for males (402 mm and 560 g, respectively) were significantly greater than females (388 mm and 519 g, respectively). The weekly average of length, weight and K decreased significantly as the spawning migration progressed (Table 25).

Fingerling trout (presumed yearlings) were first observed near the weir on May 31, but young-of-the-year cutthroat were not seen until July 18. Somewhat larger trout (presumed age II) were also found occasionally after July 1.

Despite the occurrence of spawning longnose suckers near the mouth of Clear Creek and directly below the weir, only two were observed in the traps; both of these were migrating downstream. Several young suckers (75-100 mm) were observed below the weir on July 18.

Downstream migration. A total of 52,763 cutthroat trout were passed downstream at Clear Creek. Of these, 42,229 were marked by the adipose fin clip. During the first 42 days of operation, the lakeward migration varied from 1 (May 29) to 490 (June 12) (Figure 15).

Table 25. Weekly mean, length, weight, and condition factor of cutthroat trout spawners in the upstream trap in Clear Creek, May 23 - July 24, 1979¹⁾

Date	Males			Females			Totals			M:F ratio			
	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor	Number		Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor
May 23 - 24	45	426	711	0.92	54	393	604	0.99	100	408	651	0.96	0.83:1
May 30 - June 5	38	414	644	0.90	62	398	596	0.94	100	404	614	0.92	0.61:1
June 6 - 12	36	401	544	0.83	64	391	545	0.91	100	395	544	0.88	0.56:1
June 13 - 19	30	396	557	0.89	70	385	517	0.90	100	388	529	0.89	0.73:1
June 20 - 26	35	390	506	0.85	65	387	506	0.87	100	388	506	0.86	0.54:1
June 27 - July 3	29	394	507	0.82	71	390	522	0.86	100	391	510	0.86	0.41:1
July 4 - 10	30	394	514	0.83	70	382	492	0.88	100	386	499	0.86	0.43:1
July 11 - 17	33	394	504	0.82	67	382	476	0.85	100	386	486	0.84	0.49:1
July 18 - 24	32	400	480	0.74	68	383	438	0.78	100	388	452	0.77	0.47:1
Composite	308	402	560	0.85	591	388	519	0.88	900	393	553	0.87	0.52:1

1) Based on daily samples of cutthroat trout which were both measured and weighed.

Approximately 80% of the postspawners were counted from July 4-22 (Figure 15). During the last six days of operation, an average of 15 trout were captured per day.

Prior to July 4, the majority of the downstream migration occurred between 2000-2400 hrs. As the downstream migration increased, most movement occurred from 1300-2000 hrs. This pattern continued for the duration of the study.

Average total length and weight for the downstream migrants were 396 mm and 489 g, respectively (Table 26). The average K factor was 0.75, and the male:female ratio was 0.62:1. Males had a significantly greater mean total length (405 mm) and weight (537 g) than females (391 mm and 461 g, respectively).

Mean length of downstream migrants did not differ significantly from upstream migrants. Both males and females in the downstream run displayed significantly lower weights and K factors. As in the upstream migration, there were significant decreases in weekly averages of length, weight and K factors during the study (Table 26).

One particularly interesting occurrence was the collection of a hermaphrodite cutthroat trout (410 mm, 540 g) in the downstream trap. Although this individual had the appearance of an adult male, both eggs and milt were extruded upon light pressure to the abdomen. Only two other documented cases of hermaphroditism have been reported for Yellowstone Lake cutthroat trout (Cope 1958).

Bear tracks and partially eaten fish were observed along the stream on June 4, 5, 6 and 9. Other wildlife observed feeding in or near Clear Creek during the spawning season included family groups of mink, common loons, common mergansers, California gulls, as well as several ospreys, golden and bald eagles, great blue herons and white pelicans (as many as 24 at one time). An otter was seen in the lake near Elk Point and a beaver frequented the weir several times in early June.

Cub Creek

A total of 12,019 cutthroat were passed upstream at Cub Creek. Very few trout migrated from June 8-25 (mean = 17 per day). After June 25, the run increased steadily with approximately 80% (9,640) moving from July 1-12. An average of 28 trout per day were captured during the final nine days (Figure 16).

Table 26. Weekly mean, length, weight and condition factor of cutthroat trout postsmomers in the downstream trap at Clear Creek, May 30 - July 31, 1979¹⁾

Date	Males			Females			Totals						
	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average X factor	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor	M:f ratio
May 30 - June 5	20	394	514	0.83	90	398	510	0.80	100	397	510	0.81	0.25:1
June 6 - 12	33	414	590	0.82	67	395	479	0.77	100	401	516	0.79	0.49:1
June 13 - 19	36	414	598	0.83	63	399	493	0.77	100	404	531	0.79	0.57:1
June 20 - 26	38	417	597	0.81	62	392	480	0.79	100	402	524	0.80	0.61:1
June 27 - July 3	45	415	599	0.82	55	399	462	0.78	100	401	523	0.80	0.82:1
July 4 - 10	17	400	521	0.81	83	388	460	0.78	100	390	470	0.79	0.20:1
July 11 - 17	43	399	506	0.79	57	384	439	0.77	100	391	468	0.78	0.75:1
July 18 - 24	45	395	448	0.72	55	383	393	0.70	100	397	418	0.71	0.82:1
July 25 - 31	58	398	487	0.77	45	381	388	0.70	103	391	444	0.74	1.29:1
Composite	353	405	537	0.79	567	391	461	0.77	903	396	489	0.78	0.62:1

1) Based on daily samples of cutthroat trout which were both measured and weighed.

Figure 16. Pattern of cutthroat spawning migration, Cub Creek, June 8 to July 27, 1979.

Average total length was 386 mm and average weight was 495 g for upstream migrants. The male:female ratio was 0.59:1 (Table 27). Sexual dimorphism was similar to Clear Creek; males exhibited a significantly greater average total length than females (393 mm and 382 mm, respectively). Mean weight was also significantly greater for males, but females had a significantly greater K factor.

Discussion

Both similarities and differences were evident when the cutthroat spawning migrations at Clear Creek and Cub Creek were compared. The most obvious difference between the spawning migrations in the two streams was the much greater number of spawners in Clear Creek. The run began several days later at Cub Creek again in 1979. These observations may reflect general dissimilarities in physical characteristics of the two streams including size, discharge, available spawning habitat and stream temperature.

Mean total length, weight and K factor were significantly greater for cutthroat trout in the Clear Creek spawning run. When each run was partitioned by sex, Clear Creek trout were significantly higher in these parameters with one exception; there was no significant difference between K factors in males. Since in past years mean length was usually greater at Cub Creek, this year's results are quite interesting and deserve continued scrutiny in future years.

Other previously reported relationships were observed at both streams in 1979. The spawning migrations in Clear Creek and Cub Creek began later than Pelican Creek and Hatchery Creek. Larger trout entered the streams first; mean length, weight and K factors gradually decreased during the season. Most males were ripe when they entered the streams, but females apparently ripened during the upstream migration.

The number of spawners entering the streams throughout the season was strongly influenced by stream flows and water temperatures (Figure 15). Since these factors are interrelated, it is difficult to separate their effects; however, numbers increased in June as flow decreased from its peak and water temperature rose above 10° C.

The daily pattern of upstream migration at Clear Creek also appeared to be related to flow and water temperature. The number of trout increased from 1300-1700 hrs as water temperature was rising and flow was decreasing. As flow increased and temperature dropped (1700-2100 hrs), the number of spawners declined. Relatively few upstream migrants were seen after dark. This pattern resembles observations

Table 27. Weekly mean, length, weight, and condition factor of cutthroat trout spawners in the upstream trap in Cub Creek, June 8 - July 26, 1971¹⁾

Date	Males				Females				Totals				
	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor	Number	Average length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average K factor	M:f ratio
June 8 - 14	24	397	566	0.90	22	386	532	0.92	46	391	550	0.91	1.09:1
June 15 - 21	18	383	492	0.87	33	388	521	0.89	51	386	511	0.88	0.55:1
June 22 - 28	67	393	530	0.87	65	389	536	0.91	132	391	533	0.89	1.03:1
June 29 - July 5	66	395	532	0.86	109	384	510	0.90	175	388	518	0.88	0.61:1
July 6 - 12	45	394	526	0.85	130	380	491	0.89	175	384	506	0.88	0.35:1
July 13 - 19	42	369	487	0.82	133	379	454	0.83	175	381	462	0.83	0.32:1
July 20 - 26	64	392	450	0.74	61	382	415	0.74	125	387	433	0.74	1.05:1
Composite	326	393	509	0.84	553	382	466	0.87	879	386	495	0.85	0.59:1

1) Based on daily samples of cutthroat trout which were both measured and weighed.

at Cub Creek and Pelican Creek in recent years. Reports of nocturnal upstream migrations in these streams (Bulkley, pers. com. 1978) indicates a need for further investigation of the daily migration pattern.

Downstream migration during the early weeks of the spawning run was mostly nocturnal and appeared to follow increases in stream flow between 1900-2400 hrs. This observation suggests that many post-spawners moved downstream during periods of heavy runoff. As stream discharge decreased later in the spawning run, the majority of downstream migration occurred between 1300-2000 hrs.

Since all spawners leave Clear Creek after spawning, and there are no residents other than a small number of yearlings and age II+ cutthroat, the difference between the upstream and downstream counts provide an unbiased estimate of instream spawning mortality. The removal of grates during periods of high runoff in 1979 probably allowed some undetected downstream movement; therefore, the mortality estimate of 9.4% is a maximum.

Since 1977, instream mortality has ranged from 6.7% in 1977 to 18.5% in 1978. The mean estimate of 11.5% is much lower than the instream mortality estimate of 48.1% for five tributaries from 1949-1953 (Ball and Cope 1961). Only one estimate of 41.2% was made for Clear Creek during this period. These figures were primarily calculated from tag return data; however, in 1953, one estimate from Arnica Creek of 45.6% was based on total upstream and downstream counts. Although these earlier findings may be biased by tagging mortality and the use of artificially spawned trout in the estimates, significant changes in the population structure may have occurred due to intensive exploitation in the 1950's.

Comparison of eight years of length frequency data collected since 1969 (Figures 17 and 18) has provided a means of monitoring the influence of angling during this period (Jones et al 1978). The continued shift towards larger trout in recent years has been interpreted as a positive response to increasingly restrictive regulations since 1969.

The current spawning migration at Clear Creek underscores the disastrous effects of low spawner escapement, due both to egg-taking operations and overharvest, during the 1940's, 50's and 60's. Although the current structure of the cutthroat trout population may still be far removed from historic levels, spawning migrations at Clear Creek in recent years indicate the potential of a native cutthroat trout population under protective regulations. The large variety of piscivorous birds

Figure 17. Length frequency of cutthroat trout in the upstream spawning migration in Clear Creek in recent years.

Figure 18. Length frequency of cutthroat trout in the upstream spawning migration in Cub Creek in recent years.

and mammals currently associated with the spawning migration illustrates the importance of the cutthroat trout to the Yellowstone Lake ecosystem.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Although the spawning runs in Clear Creek and Cub Creek differ in magnitude and timing, the seasonal pattern of the migration appears to be influenced by decreasing stream flows and increasing water temperature. In both streams larger spawners enter earlier; average length, weight and condition factors decrease throughout the season. Recent increases in average size of cutthroat spawners and shifts in length frequency curves appear to be positive effects of the 330 mm maximum size limit.

At Clear Creek, studies on the dynamics of the cutthroat spawning run revealed that daily upstream migration increased from 1300-1700 hrs with increasing water temperature and decreasing flows. The number of upstream migrants declined with decreased temperature and rising flows from 1900-2400 hrs; very few fish moved upstream after dark. Downstream migration was primarily nocturnal (1900-2400 hrs) during peak runoff, but migrations occurred between 1500-2000 hrs as flow decreased.

Instream spawning mortality calculations utilized counts of upstream and downstream spawners. The 1979 estimate of 9.4% was well within extremes observed since 1977. The three year average instream spawning mortality (11.5%) is substantially lower than the average estimate of 48.1% for five tributaries from 1949-1953.

We recommend that studies on Clear Creek and Cub Creek continue in order to gain further understanding of the dynamics of these two important spawning populations. Such studies should include emphasis on the frequency of repeat spawning and the occurrence of alternate and consecutive spawners in the Clear Creek stock. Efforts to describe the daily migration pattern (both upstream and downstream) should also continue in 1980.

LARGEMESH GILLNETTING

The objective of the largemesh gillnetting program has been to monitor relative abundance and distribution of cutthroat trout and longnose suckers in Yellowstone Lake. In order to reduce variability and enhance the interpretation of data, the experimental design has been altered since the program was initiated in 1969. Despite changes, data has remained comparable for the eight years in which studies have been conducted. Jones et al (1977, 1978 and 1979) provide summaries of previous results.

In 1979, gillnets were set September 17-21 (Figure 19). All sampling procedures, including terms used to describe stage of maturity (Jones et al 1979), remained the same as 1978. Additionally, gonad weights were recorded for 50 of the trout sampled.

Results

Cutthroat Trout - 1979

A total of 748 cutthroat trout (13.6 trout per net) were captured. Average length and weight were 303 mm and 301 g, respectively (Table 28). Average condition factor (K) was 0.92.

Comparison of length and stage of maturity indicated that most trout less than 300 mm were nonspawners (Table 29). The percentage of nonspawners was greater than 40% up to 330 mm. Male prespawners were larger than female prespawners and dominated all size-groups above 381 mm.

The number of trout captured differed significantly between the 11 netting sites. Sites 3a, 4b and 1b had the greatest catch per net (18.6; 18.2 and 18.0, respectively) and sites 2b, 2a and 7c had the lowest (range: 9.0-10.4) (Table 30).

When net catches were combined into four lake zones (North 1a, 1b, 1c, 2a, 2b; Central 3a, 3b; West Thumb 4a, 4b; and South 6c, 7c), West Thumb had a significantly greater mean number per net than either the North or South zones (17.2; 12.4 and 11.4, respectively) (Table 31).

Average total length of trout differed significantly between the 11 netting sites. Trout from site 6c were significantly larger than all

*Yellowstone
before 7/15*

Figure 19. Creel survey, gillnetting, plankton sampling (*), purseseining (o), and spawning trap sites, Yellowstone Lake, 1979.

Table 28. Comparative gillnetting results, cutthroat trout, 1.52-4.57 m depth interval, Yellowstone Lake, 1969, 1970, 1971, 1972, 1974, 1976, 1977, 1978, and 1979

Category	1969	1970	1971	1972	1974	1976	1977	1978	1979
Number of gillnets set ¹⁾	9	11	5	11	11	11	44	55	55
Average number of trout caught per net	12.22	12.27	14.4	13.63	15.45	15.0	15.55	13.93	13.60
95% confidence interval of number of trout caught per net	±6.71	±5.90	±9.76	±3.57	±4.75	±3.06	±1.98	±1.06	±1.27
Percentage of trout over 356 mm (11)	29.1	26.7	37.5	32.7	34.7	37.6	33.0	37.5	32.3
Percentage of trout over 466 mm (11)	1.8	3.0	1.4	3.3	0.6	2.4	4.7	5.4	7.4
Percentage of trout over 457 mm (11)	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.3	0.1
Percentage of prespawning trout ²⁾	53.6	46.6	54.3	39.8	56.4	48.6	75.6	65.7	59.0
Ratio of prespawning males to females	1.06	1.73	1.50	0.52	1.00	1.43	0.98	1.06	0.91
Average length (mm) of prespawning males	353	359	360	358	349	370	376	383	357
Average length (mm) of prespawning females	346	351	368	369	359	365	362	372	374
Condition factor K	0.974	0.917	0.853	0.937	0.859	0.877	0.892	0.923	0.915

1) Number of sets has been limited to the 1.52-4.57 m depth interval to ensure comparability.

2) Percentage of cutthroat trout over 304 mm (11) which were judged to have sufficient gonadal development to spawn the following spring.

Table 29. Length frequency distribution, average lengths and weights, and condition factors of prespawning and nonspawning cutthroat trout and longnose suckers captured in largeesh quillnets, 1.5 - 4.6 m depth interval, Yellowstone Lake, 1979

Species	Maturity category	Size-group (total length - mm)											Average total length (mm)	Average weight (g)	Average condition factor (K)					
		152	178	204	229	254	279	305	330	356	381	406				432	457	483	508	
Cutthroat trout	Nonspawners	31	82	34	76	90	63	42	38	31	30	7	1				211	0.91		
	Prespawning males				1		3	3	13	19	36	23	7	1			542	0.92		
	Prespawning females						3	7	20	36	35	14	2				487	0.92		
TOTALS and AVERAGES		31	82	34	77	90	69	52	71	86	101	44	10	1			301	0.92		
Longnose suckers	Nonspawners			14	15	36	38	13	34	47	17	7	1				256	1.18		
	Prespawning males						1	1	11	24	23	59	74	32	6	4	819	1.26		
	Prespawning females								9	11	21	44	74	58	17	4	593	1.15		
TOTALS and AVERAGES				14	15	36	38	14	35	58	50	41	81	118	106	64	21	4	699	1.20

1) Prespawning fish defined as those judged to have sufficient gonadal development to spawn in 1980; nonspawners include immature, and mature fish which were judged to lack sufficient gonadal development to spawn in 1980.

Table 31. Gillnet catches of cutthroat trout by general area, Yellowstone Lake, 1969, 1970, 1971, 1972, 1974, 1976, 1977, 1978, and 1979.1)

Year	Number/net				Average total length (mm)				Percentage under 210 mm				
	North	Central	W. Thumb	South	North	Central	W. Thumb	South	North	Central	W. Thumb	South	Total
1969	10	--	16	15	316	--	256	319	12.2	--	9.7	10.0	10.9
1970	15	14	17	4	311	352	285	346	7.8	0.0	17.6	0.0	8.1
1971	14	--	--	--	321	--	--	--	1.4	--	--	--	1.4
1972	15	10	14	12	297	307	342	336	11.7	0.0	0.0	4.0	6.7
1974	19	9	16	13	289	302	294	329	14.7	16.7	25.8	0.0	14.7
1976	16	17	13	13	310	311	328	333	11.0	5.9	4.3	7.7	8.5
1977	17	15	11	17	284	293	273	309	28.2	23.1	30.3	13.3	24.6
1978	13	15	17	13	238	305	294	353	13.2	8.6	5.4	0.8	8.5
1979	12	15	17	11	297	290	291	356	18.1	21.0	14.5	6.1	16.0
Totals	145	525	574	494					16.9	14.9	13.8	6.5	14.2
Averages	15	15	14	13	297	301	293	337					

1) Net locations combined as follows: North - 1A, 1B, 1C, 2A, 2B; Central - 3A, 3B; W. Thumb - 4A, 4B; South - 6C, 7C.

other sites. The smallest trout were captured at sites 1a, 3a and 1b (Table 30).

Differences between sites in the length of prespawners were also significant. The relationships between site and the average length of prespawners and the average length of all trout captured differed; however, site 6c had the largest trout in both cases (Table 30).

When length comparisons of all trout were made by zone, cutthroat in the South were significantly larger than those from other zones. Prespawners were also compared by zone, and significantly larger trout were again found in the South. The effect of smaller trout on average lengths is illustrated by the length-frequency histogram (Figure 20).

A gonadal-somatic index (GSI) (LeCren 1951) was calculated for 50 cutthroat trout. Nonspawning cutthroat greater than 304 mm (TL) had significantly lower GSI values (0.10 and 0.44 for males and females, respectively) than cutthroat prespawners (3.09 and 4.25 for males and females, respectively). As expected, females had greater GSI in both maturity categories.

Longnose Suckers - 1979

The average length was 371 mm and average weight was 698 g for the 695 longnose suckers captured (Table 32). The average K factor was 1.19.

Approximately 94% of suckers over 305 mm were categorized as prespawners (Table 29). Males were judged prespawners at a smaller size, and females dominated size classes over 432 mm. These results are consistent with previous studies (Jones et al 1978 and 1979).

Discussion

Cutthroat Trout 1969-1979

Average number per net. Although a trend of increased number of cutthroat trout per net was reported through most of the 1970's (Jones et al 1978), decreases have occurred in the past two years (Table 28). Differences in the number captured between years, however, were not statistically significant. This lack of significance is related to the high degree of variability inherent with the gillnetting results (Jones et al 1978) and suggests that these decreases are not linked to substantial declines in the total lake population.

Figure 20. Length frequencies of cutthroat trout captured in largemesh gillnets at the 1.5-4.6 m depth interval, Yellowstone Lake, 1969-1979.

Table 32. Comparative longnose gillnetting results, longnose suckers, 1.5-4.6 m depth interval, Yellowstone Lake, 1969, 1970, 1971, 1972, 1974, 1976, 1977, 1978, and 1979

Category	1969	1970	1971	1972	1974	1976	1977	1978	1979
Number of gillnets set ¹⁾	9	11	5	11	11	11	44	55	55
Average number of suckers caught per net	16.33	6.45	37.0	2.54	15.91	14.55	7.25	7.52	17.64
55% confidence interval of number of suckers caught per net	±10.65	±5.01	±42.17	±1.29	±5.92	±5.36	±1.83	±1.99	±2.07
Percentage of suckers over 356 mm (11)	66.0	83.1	34.0	42.9	69.7	80.6	60.9	58.3	62.6
Percentage of suckers over 406 mm (11)	29.2	59.2	17.8	28.6	29.1	44.4	55.5	38.9	45.2
Percentage of suckers over 457 mm (11)	6.1	12.7	2.7	7.1	5.7	7.5	14.7	11.1	13.0
Percentage of prespawning suckers ²⁾	92.1	100.0	100.0	88.2	100.0	95.2	100.0	92.5	87.8
Ratio of prespawning males to females	1.23	0.80	2.00	2.00	1.28	1.07	1.48	1.13	0.99
Average length (cm) of prespawning males	382	386	357	378	372	387	390	385	399
Average length (cm) of prespawning females	415	440	417	428	415	425	441	435	440
Condition factor K	1.207	1.235	1.207	1.255	1.215	1.277	1.229	1.187	1.197

1) Number of sets has been limited to the 1.5-4.6 m depth interval to ensure comparability.

2) Percentage of longnose suckers over 310 mm (11) which were judged to have sufficient gonadal development to spawn the following spring.

Other measures of population strength support such a conclusion. Data from VFR indicated that changes in harvest were well within extremes of the past five years and would not suggest a decrease in population size. The number of spawners ascending Clear Creek has remained high, and despite difficulties in obtaining total counts of spawners at Pelican and Cub Creeks, significant decreases have not been observed.

When data from the nine years of gillnetting were combined, differences in the number of trout between sites were significant. The relationship between site and number of trout captured has changed since 1977. Sites 4a, 6c, 3b and 1a, however, continued to have the lowest catch, and site 4b had the highest.

Although the relationships between lake zone and the number of trout has varied annually, there was little difference between zones when data from nine years were combined (Table 31). Catch varied from 15.1 per net in West Thumb to 13.0 in the South.

Average size. The mean total length of cutthroat trout captured in gillnets has varied significantly since 1969. Similar results were observed when data was combined over years and compared by zone and site (Tables 30 and 31). Biological interpretation of these results is confounded by the high degree of variation and absence of observable trends.

It has been suggested that differences in the length of trout captured since 1969 are due mostly to fluctuations in the proportion of smaller fish in the sample (Jones et al 1978). The yearly fluctuations in the portion of smaller trout, and thus the mean length of the entire sample, may be caused by differences in population distribution or may reflect year-class fluctuations of the smaller trout prior to entry into the fishery. Since the mean length of prespawners is not affected by changes in the proportion of smaller trout, comparisons of prespawners may provide an effective means of detecting changes in mature trout.

Differences in the length of prespawning trout between sample years were significant. The previously reported annual trend of increasing length (Jones et al 1979) continued in 1979, and the length of prespawners (380 mm) was the largest reported since the survey began in 1969. This increase is interpreted as a positive response of the cutthroat population to the 330 mm maximum size limit imposed in 1975.

When prespawners were separated by sex, both males and females displayed significant differences in mean length between years. The response of prespawners to harvest changes has been most pronounced in prespawning males (Figure 21). Since most large cutthroat are males, such a response could be expected.

During the years (1970-1974) when a minimum size limit restricted harvest, mean lengths of male prespawners declined rapidly. Although female prespawners followed a similar pattern, reaction was slower. When larger trout became protected by the 330 mm maximum size limit (1975), the males responded rapidly; females again followed a similar pattern but at a slower rate.

Differences in length of prespawning trout from the four lake zones were also significant. Prespawners from the South (386 mm) were the largest and West Thumb prespawners (359 mm) were smallest. Although prespawners from the North and Central (370 mm and 369 mm, respectively) zones differed from the other two zones, there was little difference between the two.

Length frequency. A comparison of length frequency data from eight survey years illustrates several interesting trends (Figure 22). Since the 330 mm maximum size limit was imposed in 1975, there has been a shift towards larger fish in both the 330-400 mm and 400-500 mm groups. In 1979, the proportion of large cutthroat trout (>406 mm) was greater than any other year sampled (Table 28). An increase in the total range of lengths sampled was also apparent (Figure 22).

In 1977, a large pulse of trout less than 210 mm suggested that the 1975 year-class was very strong (Jones et al 1978). In 1978, the increased frequency of trout in the 200-270 mm group was interpreted as growth of this year-class between years (Figure 22). When the majority of this year-class entered the fishery during 1979, the previously reported depression between 270-340 mm (Jones et al 1979) was dampened considerably. Additionally, the proportion of trout less than 210 mm in the 1979 data indicates that the 1977 year-class may also be quite strong.

Comparison of GSI values between the current study and those calculated from trout collected in April 1978 (Jones et al 1979), show little change in nonspawners greater than 304 mm (TL). Prespawning females revealed an anticipated decline from spring (15.24) to fall (4.25); however, the increased GSI value for prespawning males (1.90 and 3.05 for spring and fall, respectively) was unexpected. Since it has been assumed that most spawning is completed by mid-

Figure 21. Mean total lengths of prespawning cutthroat trout captured in largemesh gillnets, Yellowstone lake, 1969 - 1979.

Figure 22. Length frequencies of cutthroat trout captured in largemesh gillnets at the 1.5-4.6 m depth interval, Yellowstone Lake, 1969-79.

July, it was believed that GSI's in the spring, just prior to spawning, would be higher than those in the fall, several months after spawning had ceased. Although the data necessary to explain this result are insufficient, a high proportion of late spawning males in the fall sample is suggested.

Longnose Suckers 1969-1979

Average number per net. Although differences between years in the number of suckers captured are significant, reasons for these changes remain unidentified. It is doubtful these differences are due to population fluctuations since the longnose sucker is believed to be longlived in Yellowstone Lake (Jones et al 1977). These fluctuations may be partially due to schooling behavior; such behavior would intensify variation in gillnet catch. Although it was speculated that the sucker eradication project at Pelican Creek had contributed to the lower sucker catches in 1977 and 1978, the sharp increase in the number per net in 1979 suggests that variability continues to confound comparisons.

Average size. Comparisons between years (Table 33) yield significant differences in mean length. Mean length of suckers was inversely correlated to the male:female ratio ($r = 0.78$) and directly correlated to the percentage of suckers over 310 mm (TL) ($r = 0.94$). Since the latter two factors are probably related to distribution, annual variations affecting numbers captured may also affect variation in mean length.

The largemesh gillnetting program has provided only minimal information concerning the longnose sucker. If methods of ageing this species can be verified, they may provide a means of evaluating yearly fluctuations. Future changes in experimental design intended to reduce variation in cutthroat trout data may also improve interpretation of the longnose sucker data.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Analysis of data from nine years of largemesh gillnetting on Yellowstone Lake has provided insight into both the dynamics of the trout population and the limitations of this sampling method. Yearly variation in the number captured and mean length of longnose suckers continues to confound logical interpretation. Annual fluctuations in

the mean length of cutthroat, however, appear to be related to the proportion of smaller trout (prior to entry into the fishery) in the sample. Significant increases in the mean length of prespawning male and female cutthroat trout and significant shifts toward larger trout in length frequency data since 1974 are believed to be positive effects of the 330 mm maximum size limit. High GSI values of fall captured prespawning male cutthroat trout suggest a high proportion of late spawning males in the fall sample.

We recommend that the largemesh gillnetting program be continued in order to provide an annual monitoring of the cutthroat population in Yellowstone Lake. Additional collection of gonad samples is necessary to provide information concerning the annual sexual cycle of the cutthroat trout.

FALL PURSE SEINE OPERATION

The vast size of Yellowstone Lake (35,630 ha) has historically hindered efforts to sample the pelagic areas. Vertical gillnets were set in 1974 (Dean et al 1975) and 1975 (Varley et al 1975), but low catch/effort limited the effectiveness of this program. In 1979, a purse seining operation was conducted by personnel from Wyoming Game and Fish in an effort to investigate this method of pelagic sampling.

Methods

The purse seine was 236 m long and 18.3 m deep with 15.2 m tapered leads. The net was comprised of 10 mm bar mesh nylon except for the bottom 0.9 m, which was 32 mm bar mesh. An area of approximately 0.4 ha (18.3 m deep) was sampled with each haul.

A total of 19 hauls were made at various sites around Yellowstone Lake from September 17-20, 1979 (Figure 19). These hauls were divided by area of the lake as follows: eight from the vicinity of Bridge Bay (North) including Sand Point (1) and Stevenson Island (1); four from West Thumb; five from the South Arm; and two hauls in the vicinity of Frank Island.

Results

A total of 426 cutthroat trout and one longnose sucker was captured during the study (Table 34). The mean catch was 22.4 trout/haul, but variation was extremely high with catches ranging from 1-99. Frank Island and South Arm had the greatest number/haul (49.0 and 32.2, respectively) while North and West Thumb had the lowest (14.1 and 13.5, respectively); however, these differences were not statistically significant.

The mean lengths and weight for 414 cutthroat trout were 343 mm and 379 g, respectively (Table 34). Trout from South Arm and North (357 and 361 mm, respectively) were significantly larger than those from West Thumb or Frank Island hauls (316 and 314 mm, respectively). When depth of water was considered, trout from hauls in water over 60 m deep were significantly smaller (310 mm) than those from depths

Table 34. Number and size of cutthroat trout captured in purse seine hauls, Yellowstone Lake, September 17 - 20, 1979.

	AREA				Depth		
	North	South	West Thumb	Frank Island	18 - 24 m	33 - 37 m	60 m
Number of hauls	8	5	4	2	11	4	3
Number/haul	14.1	32.2	13.5	49	22.8	18.7	16.7
Mean length (mm)	361	357	316	314	342	352	310
Mean weight (g)	425	412	313	309	375	350	296
Condition factor K	0.856	0.888	0.943	0.943	0.904	0.883	0.949

less than 37 m (346 mm).

Discussion

The purse seine utilized in this study proved to be a relatively efficient method for the collection of cutthroat trout from pelagic areas of Yellowstone Lake. A distinct advantage of this method is that none of the fish are injured and all can be returned to the lake after capture.

The extreme variation between hauls greatly confounded area comparisons and attempts at population estimation (see cutthroat population estimates, this report). Sample size would have to be increased greatly to reduce variability. The minimum detectable difference in catch per unit between samples of current size (19 hauls) is 131% of the mean ($t_{\alpha} = 95\%$, $t_{\beta} = 20\%$), and approximately 779 hauls/sample would be necessary to detect differences as low as 20% of the mean (Snedecor and Cochran 1967).

Although differences were not statistically significant, catches were much lower in the North and West Thumb. It is important to note that these areas also bear the brunt of angler exploitation on Yellowstone Lake.

Trout collected in seine hauls were larger than those captured in gillnets during the same week. Length frequency analysis indicates about 20% more trout over 350 mm in the purse seine samples. Since gillnets were sampling the littoral zone and purse seine hauls were limited to pelagic areas, these size differences are not surprising. Gear selectivity may also influence size discrepancies.

Decreases in trout length with increasing water depth agreed with previous gillnetting data (both experimental and vertical) from Yellowstone Lake; however, length comparisons by area differed somewhat between the methods. Continued investigations are necessary to separate the effects due to habitat differences and gear selectivity.

Conclusion and Recommendations

It appears that catch per unit effort for the purse seine is almost twice as great as gillnet sets during the same time periods. Although the numbers sampled are sufficient for length comparisons between areas of the lake, comparisons of catch per unit effort are hampered by extreme variation. This variation would necessitate a great increase in the number of hauls in future studies. Distinct differences between

the results of purse seine and gillnet catches in similar areas of the lake have limited habitat comparisons using these two methods.

We recommend that studies utilizing the purse seine be continued on Yellowstone Lake in order to further evaluate this sampling method. The number of hauls should be increased greatly to facilitate analysis of catch per unit effort data. The use of a 9 m seine in future studies would enhance investigations concerning trout distributions in the lake by allowing the sampling of shallower waters, and might increase comparability with gillnet data.

CUTTHROAT TROUT POPULATION ESTIMATES

The immense size of Yellowstone Lake (35,391 ha) has consistently inhibited the efficiency of trout sampling programs. These problems have in turn confounded attempts at numerical estimation of what is the largest inland population of cutthroat trout in the world. During September, 1979, the purse seining crew from Wyoming Game and Fish offered to support the first attempt to estimate the cutthroat trout population in Yellowstone Lake.

Methods

In July, 1979, 49,058 cutthroat trout were marked during their post-spawning migration as follows: the adipose fin was removed from 42,229 at Clear Creek; the right mandible was clipped on 1,517 trout at Cub Creek; and the left mandible was clipped on 5,312 trout at Pelican Creek. Between September 17-21, 1979, all trout captured in 55 largemesh gillnets and 19 purse seine hauls were inspected for marks. A population estimate was calculated using an adjusted Petersen estimate (Ricker 1975). Confidence limits were computed after Ricker (1975) and statistical bias was evaluated utilizing the method of Robson and Regier (1964). In order to compensate for growth (recruitment) since time of marking, only trout over 350 mm from the fall catches were utilized in the estimates. Mean catch data from the purse seine were used to provide a secondary evaluation of the estimate.

Results

Only six marked trout were captured during the fall sampling operations. Of 236 cutthroat (> 350 mm) in the purse seine collection, one trout was captured in Bridge Bay and one was captured south of Frank Island (Figure 19); both of these individuals were originally marked at Clear Creek. Four marked fish were among the 266 trout (> 350 mm) captured in the gillnets. Of these, two Pelican Creek trout were captured near Bridge Bay (site 2a) and one individual from Clear Creek was captured in West Thumb (site 4a).

The resulting population estimate was 3.5 million cutthroat trout over 350 mm length in the Yellowstone Lake population. The confidence limits for this estimate range from 1.9 million to 11.2 million. According to the criteria of Robson and Regier (1964), the estimate is statistically unbiased.

The second estimate utilizing the average catch in the purse seine was 987,474 cutthroat trout over 350 mm (TL). The confidence limits ranged from 536,394 to 1,438,544 (Cochran 1963).

Discussion

Although the adjusted Petersen estimate was statistically unbiased, there are six major conditions which should be met for this method to be valid (Ricker 1975). Most of these conditions were met in the present study; however, two major problems were encountered.

The first problem was that all marks must be recognized on recovery. Although adipose fins may display regenerative growth, new growth was imperfect and easily recognized. The greatest difficulty with mark identification was with the mandible clips. Prior mutilation of mandibular bones either by hooking or natural causes was prevalent in these samples. Questionable trout were not counted as marked but were retained in the number checked for marks. This practice may have caused an overestimate and those individuals should have been deleted from the study.

The second condition causing error was that marked fish must become randomly mixed, or that subsequent sampling effort must be proportional to the population distribution. The marking of trout was limited to the three tributaries in the northern portion of the lake, and although the post-spawning distribution of these trout is not completely understood, previous workers (Ball and Cope 1961, Benson 1961) have indicated that distribution is not random. Due to the size of Yellowstone Lake and limited sampling effort, our subsequent sample was not completely random, nor was it conducted in proportion to the distribution of trout.

The purse seine estimates are undoubtedly affected by the great variation in catch/haul and by distributional differences between the littoral and pelagic zones. Since larger trout are most often associated with the littoral zone in Yellowstone Lake, an estimate based solely on pelagic samples probably underestimates the true population in the number. The estimate, however, does provide a minimal figure of the catchable trout population in the lake.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Future attempts at population estimation on Yellowstone Lake should avoid the use of marks which may be difficult to identify during subsequent sampling. In addition, effort should be made to ensure random distribution of marks and/or subsequent sampling effort. Although present estimates are not extremely accurate, they provide a preliminary figure for the catchable trout population. It is felt that the true number probably falls between 1-4 million.

LITERATURE CITED

- Arnold, B.B., and F.P. Sharpe. 1967. Summary report of lake and stream investigations for 1966. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. Unpubl. mimeo. 102 pp.
- Ball, O.P. and O.B. Cope. 1961. Mortality studies on cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Lake. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Res. Rpt. 55: 62 pp.
- Benson, N.G. 1960. Factors influencing production of immature cutthroat trout in Arnica Creek, Yellowstone Park. Trans. Am. Fish. Soc. 89 (2): 158-175.
- Benson, N.G. 1961. Limnology of Yellowstone Lake in relation to the cutthroat trout. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Res. Rpt. 56: 33 pp.
- Benson, N.G. and R.V. Bulkley. 1963. Equilibrium yield and management of cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Lake. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Res. Rpt. 62: 44 pp.
- Benson, N.G., O.B. Cope, and R.V. Bulkley. 1959. Fishery management studies on the Madison River system in Yellowstone National Park. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, BSWF, Spec. Sci. Rpt. - Fisheries No. 307. 27 pp.
- Bulkley, R.V. 1961. Fluctuations in age composition and growth rate of cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Lake. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Res. Rpt. No. 54: 31 pp.
- _____. 1963. Natural variation in spotting, hyoid teeth counts and coloration of Yellowstone cutthroat trout, Salmo clarki lewisi (Girard). U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service Spec. Sci. Rpt., Fish. No. 460. 11 pp.
- Bulkley, R.V. and N.G. Benson. 1962. Predicting year-class abundance of Yellowstone Lake cutthroat trout. U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service, Res. Rpt. No. 59: 21 pp.
- Carlson, R.E. 1977. A trophic state index for lakes. Limnology and Oceanography 22 (2): 361-369.

- Chapman, Scotty. No date. Fishing and hunting notes, 1941 - 1965. Unpubl. diary. Bur. Sport Fish. and Wildlife files.
- Christiansen, R.L. 1974. Geologic Map of the West Thumb Quadrangle, Wyoming. U.S.G.S., Reston, Va.
- Christiansen, R.L. and H.R. Blank. 1974. Geologic Quadrangle Map of Old Faithful, Wyoming. U.S.G.S., Reston, Va.
- Christiansen, R.L. and H.R. Blank Jr. 1974. Geologic Map of the Madison Junction Quadrangle, Wyoming. U.S.G.S., Reston, Va.
- Christiansen, R.L. and H.R. Blank, Jr. 1975. Geologic Map of the Canyon Village Quadrangle, Wyoming. U.S.G.S., Reston, Va.
- Cochran, W.G. 1963. Sampling Techniques. 2nd edition. John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, New York.
- Cope, O.B. 1957a. Races of cutthroat trout in Yellowstone Lake. USFWS, Spec. Rpt. No. 208. pp. 74-84.
- _____. 1957b. The choice of spawning sites by cutthroat trout. UT. Acad. Sci. Proc. 34: 73-79.
- Dean, J.L. and L.E. Mills. 1970. Annual Project Report - 1969. Fishery Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. USFWS, Unpubl. mimeo. 100 p.
- Dean, J.L. and J.D. Varley. 1973. Annual Project Report - 1972. Fishery Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. USFWS. Unpubl. mimeo. 84 p.
- _____. 1974. Annual Project Report - 1973. Fishery Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. USFWS. Unpubl. mimeo. 170 p.
- Dean, J.L., J.D. Varley and R.E. Gresswell. 1975. Annual Project Report - 1974. Fishery Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. USFWS. Unpubl. mimeo. 170 p.
- Dunham, D.K. and A. Collotzi. 1975. The transect method of stream habitat inventory - guidelines and application. U.S.F.S., Intermountain Region. 39 p.

- Erman, D.C. and G.R. Leidy. 1975. Downstream movement of rainbow trout fry in a tributary of Sagehen Creek, under permanent and intermittent flow. *Trans. Amer. Fish. Soc.* 104(3): 467-473.
- Hanzel, D.A. 1960. The distribution of the cutthroat trout (*Salmo clarki*) in Montana. *Proc. Mont. Acad. Sci.* 19: 32-71.
- Hutchinson, G.E. 1967. A treatise on limnology, Vol. 2. John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, New York.
- _____. 1975a. A treatise on limnology, Vol. 1, Part 1. John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, New York.
- _____. 1975b. A treatise on limnology, Vol. 3. John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, New York.
- Hayden, F.V. 1872. Preliminary report of the United States Geological Survey of Montana and portions of adjacent territories - 1871. Government Printing Office. 538 p.
- Hem, J.D. 1970. Study and interpretation of the chemical characteristics of natural water. Second edition. Geological Survey Water - Supply Paper No. 1473. U.S. Government Printing Office. Washington, D.C.
- Jones, R.D., J.D. Varley, D.E. Jennings, S.M. Rubrecht, R.E. Gresswell. 1977. Annual Project Report - 1976. Fishery and Aquatic Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. USFWS. Unpubl. mimeo. 201 p.
- _____. 1978. Annual Project Report - 1977. Fishery and Aquatic Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. USFWS. Unpubl. mimeo. 206 p.
- Jones, R.D., J.D. Varley, R.E. Gresswell, D.E. Jennings and S.M. Rubrecht. 1979. Annual Project Report - 1978. Fishery and Aquatic Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. USFWS. Unpubl. mimeo. 311 p.
- Jordan, D.S. 1891. A reconnaissance of the streams and lakes of Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming in the interest of the U.S. Fish Commission. *Bull. U.S. Fish Comm.* 9: 42-63.
- Kimura, D.K. 1977. Statistical assessment of the age-length key. *J. Fish. Res. Bd. Can.* 34: 317-324.
- Kruse, T.E. 1959. Grayling of Grebe Lake, Yellowstone National Park, WY. USFWS, *Fishery Bulletin* 59 (149): 307-351.

- Laakso, M. and O.B. Cope. 1956. Age determination in Yellowstone cutthroat trout by the scale method. *Journal of Wildlife Mgmt.*, Vol. 20 (2): 138-153.
- Lagler, K.F. 1978. Capture, sampling and examination of fishes. Pages 7-47 in: T. Bagenal, ed. *Methods for assessment of fish production in fresh waters*. 3rd ed. IBP Handbook No. 3. Blackwell Scientific Publication Ltd., Oxford, England.
- Lanier, C.D. 1927. The random notes of Charles D. Lanier on trout fishing on Slough Creek (located in Montana and Yellowstone Park). Also his observations on August bird life. Unpubl. notes. 25 p.
- LeCren, E.D. 1951. The length-weight relationship and seasonal cycle in gonad weight and condition in the perch (Perca fluviatilis). *J. Anim. Ecol.* 20: 201-219.
- _____. 1969. Estimates of fish populations and production in small streams in England. Pages 269-280. In: H.R. MacMillan Lectures in fisheries. Symposium on salmon and trout in streams. Institute of Fisheries, the Univ. of B.C., Vancouver.
- Loudenslager, E.J. 1978. Biochemical and cytogenetic analysis of cutthroat trout populations in northwestern Wyoming. *Investigators Annual Rpt. U. of Wy. and N.P.S. Nat. Sci. Res. Center*. Unpubl. mimeo. 6 p.
- McNabb, C.P. 1960. Enumeration of fresh water phytoplankton concentrated on the membrane filter. *Limno. Ocean.* 5: 57-61.
- Mills, L.E. 1966. Environmental factors and egg mortality of cutthroat trout (Salmo clarki) in three tributaries of Yellowstone Lake. M.S. Thesis, Colorado State Univ. 65 pp.
- Mills, L.E. and F.P. Sharpe. 1967. Fishery Management Program - Pollution study on Soda Butte Creek. Unpubl. mimeo. USFWS, 16 pp.
- Mills, L.E. and F.P. Sharpe. 1967. Reconnaissance Report 1967. Fishery Management Program. Slough Creek Investigations, Yellowstone National Park, Wyoming. USFWS. 11 p.
- Pennak, R.W. 1978. *Fresh-water invertebrates of the United States*. 2nd ed. John Wiley and Sons, Inc. New York, New York.

- Pickett, F.S. and J.W. Chadwick. 1973. Studies on Soda Butte, Slough, and Iron Springs Creeks, Yellowstone National Park. MSU, a final report for Contract 2-101-0387: 54 pp.
- Prostka, H.L., H.R. Blank, Jr., R.L. Christiansen, and E.T. Ruppel. 1975. Geologic Map of the Tower Junction Quadrangle, Wyoming and Montana. U.S.G.S., Reston, Va.
- Pierce, K.L. 1974. Surficial Geologic Map of the Tower Junction Quadrangle, Wyoming and Montana. Misc. Geol. Invest. U.S.G.S., Reston, Va.
- Richmond, R.M. and K.L. Pierce. 1972. Surficial Geologic Map of the Eagle Peak Quadrangle, Yellowstone National Park, and adjoining area, Wyoming. Misc. Geol. Invest. U.S.G.S., Washington, D.C.
- Richmond, G.M. 1973. Surficial Geologic Map of the West Thumb Quadrangle, Wyoming. Misc. Geol. Invest. U.S.G.S., Washington, D.C.
- Richmond, G.M. 1977. Surficial Geologic Map of the Canyon Village Quadrangle, Wyoming. Misc. Geol. Invest. U.S.G.S., Reston, Va.
- Ricker, W.E. 1975. Computation and interpretation of biological statistics of fish populations. Fish. Res. Bd. of Canada, Bull. 191: 382 p.
- Robson, D.S. and H.A. Reiger. 1964. Sample size in Petersen mark-recapture experiments. Trans. Am. Fish. Soc. 93: 215-226.
- Ruttner, F. 1963. Fundamentals of limnology. 3rd edition. Translated by W.G. Frey and F.E.J. Fry. University of Toronto Press. Toronto, Canada.
- Ryder, R.A. 1965. A method for estimating the potential fish production of north-temperate lakes. Trans. Amer. Fish. Soc. 94(3): 314-218.
- Ryder, R.A., S.R. Kerr, K.H. Loftus and H.A. Reiger. 1974. The morphoedaphic index, a fish yield estimator - review and evaluation. J. Fish. Res. Board Can. 31 (15): 663-688.
- Sharpe, F.P. and B. B. Arnold. 1965. Summary report of the lake and stream investigations for 1964. Unpubl. mimeo., USFWS. 73 p.

- _____. 1966. Summary report of lake and stream investigations for 1965. Unpubl. mimeo., USFWS. 97 p.
- Sharpe, F.P. and W.H. Babcock. 1964. Reconnaissance Report - Fishery Management Program - Yellowstone National Park. Unpubl. mimeo., Bur. Spt. Fish. Wild. 18 p.
- Snedecor, G.W. and W.G. Cochran. 1967. Statistical Methods. 6th edition. Iowa State University Press. Ames, Iowa.
- Stumm, W. and J.J. Morgan. 1970. Aquatic chemistry: An introduction emphasizing chemical equilibria in natural waters. Wiley - Interscience. New York, New York.
- U.S. Dept. Agriculture, Forest Service/Northern Region. 1975. Stream reach inventory and channel stability evaluation. R. 1-75-002. 26 p.
- U.S. Dept. Interior, National Park Service. 1975. Administrative policies for natural areas of the National Park system. USDI, NPS, Wash., D.C. 138 p.
- U.S. Dept. Interior, Fish and Wildlife Service. 1977. The 1975 national survey of hunting, fishing and wildlife associated recreation. Wash., D.C. 96 p.
- Varley, J.D., R.E. Gresswell, S.M. Hoskins, R.B. Mathias, D.E. Jennings, M.D. Carpenter, and J. Dolan. 1976. Annual Project Report - 1975. Fishery and Aquatic Management Program, Yellowstone National Park. Unpubl. mimeo. USFWS. 48 p.
- Waldrop, H.A. and K.L. Pierce. 1975. Surficial Geologic Map of the Madison Junction Quadrangle, Wyoming. Misc. Geol. Invest., Reston, Va.
- Welch, P.S. 1952. Limnology. 2nd ed. McGraw-Hill Book Company, Inc. New York, New York.
- Welsh, J.P. 1952. A population study of Yellowstone black-spotted trout *Salmo clarki lewisi* (Girard). Ph.D. diss., Stanford Univ. 180 p.
- Westerheim, S.J. and W.E. Ricker. 1978. Bias in using an age-length key to estimate age frequency distributions. J. Fish. Res. Board Can. 35: 184-189.
- Zippen, C. 1958. The removal method of population estimation. Jour. of Wildlife Mgmt., Vol. 22 (1): 82-90.

APPENDIX A

Appendix A, Table 1. Length frequencies of landed and creeled cutthroat trout from Yellowstone Lake, 1979

Name	Section		Percentage in each length interval (inches)							Number fish	Mean size (inches)
			10	10-12	12-14	14-16	16-18	18-20	20		
Yellowstone Lake	Shore Area 1	Landed	4.1	9.0	29.7	35.5	18.1	3.6	0	1,396	15.2
		Creled	3.0	21.7	68.2	6.4	0.7	0	0	299	13.3
Yellowstone Lake	Shore Area 2	Landed	5.3	8.8	27.3	36.3	17.0	4.3	1.0	5,333	15.3
		Creled	3.6	28.9	64.6	2.2	0.7	0	0	968	13.0
Yellowstone Lake	Shore Area 3	Landed	1.8	7.3	22.1	58.5	8.6	1.2	0.4	1,638	15.3
		Creled	4.2	23.5	55.0	11.0	1.3	0	0	309	13.2
Yellowstone Lake	Shore Area 4	Landed	2.6	10.1	25.3	39.8	18.2	3.4	0.6	1,196	15.4
		Creled	5.7	30.7	55.7	7.8	0	0	0	296	13.0
Yellowstone Lake	Shore Area 5	Landed	0	6.2	11.1	45.7	37.0	0	0	81	16.3
		Creled	0	55.6	44.4	0	0	0	0	9	12.5
Yellowstone Lake	Shore Area 6	Landed	3.4	0.6	10.2	35.2	41.5	9.1	0	176	16.8
		Creled	12.5	0	62.5	0	25.0	0	0	16	14.3
Yellowstone Lake	Shore Area 7	Landed	0.6	6.9	33.5	17.3	38.7	2.3	0.6	173	15.9
		Creled	0	35.7	28.5	25.0	10.7	0	0	28	14.0
Yellowstone Lake	Boat Area 1	Landed	0.9	1.9	19.6	60.9	13.7	1.9	1.2	322	15.9
		Creled	4.8	9.7	67.7	17.7	0	0	0	62	13.7
Yellowstone Lake	Boat Area 2	Landed	3.3	13.6	26.8	41.7	11.8	1.2	1.7	3,793	15.0
		Creled	4.3	35.7	55.6	4.0	0.3	0.1	0	955	12.9
Yellowstone Lake	Boat Area 3	Landed	6.0	11.3	27.3	55.3	0	0	0	150	14.4
		Creled	0	34.4	40.6	25.0	0	0	0	32	13.5
Yellowstone Lake	Boat Area 4	Landed	3.5	13.6	29.2	37.1	14.2	1.8	0.5	3,209	14.9
		Creled	4.7	30.7	58.9	3.8	1.8	0	0.1	684	13.0
Yellowstone Lake	Boat Area 5	Landed	0.4	4.6	22.9	41.9	25.9	3.1	1.2	2,033	16.0
		Creled	1.2	25.0	61.3	11.9	0.5	0	0	168	13.4
Yellowstone Lake	Boat Area 6	Landed	0	2.7	16.8	46.8	25.7	6.8	1.1	2,447	16.4
		Creled	0	22.3	64.3	12.7	0.6	0	0	157	13.6
Yellowstone Lake	Boat Area 7	Landed	0.9	1.6	13.5	45.9	31.9	5.0	1.3	1,513	16.6
		Creled	5.2	17.4	53.9	19.1	1.7	2.6	0	115	13.8
Yellowstone Lake	All Shoreline	Landed	4.1	3.5	26.5	39.6	17.0	3.7	0.7	10,656	15.3
		Creled	3.9	26.9	62.9	5.1	1.2	0	0	2,086	13.1
Yellowstone Lake	All Boat	Landed	1.8	8.1	21.8	46.5	18.2	2.7	0.9	19,280	15.6
		Creled	3.4	29.2	59.7	6.1	0.8	0.2	0	2,970	13.1
Yellowstone Lake	Total boat/shore	Landed	2.6	8.2	23.5	44.1	17.7	3.0	0.8	29,936	15.5
		Creled	3.6	28.6	61.0	5.7	1.0	0.1	0	5,056	13.1

Appendix A
Table 2. Mean total lengths of cutthroat trout captured in the Yellowstone River, 1952-1979

Regulations	Year	Mean total length in cm (inches)			Sample size	Area	Source
		Dip net	Electrofishing	Hook and line			
5 fish bag limit, no size limit	1952 ¹⁾	368 (14.5)			382	Lellardy's Rapids	Cope 1953
	1952				330 (13.0)	Above Upper Falls	Cope 1953
3 fish bag limit, no size limit	1967		345 (13.6)		346	Excluding Hayden Valley	Unpublished data
	1967				338 (13.3)	Excluding Hayden Valley	Dean and Varley 1973
	1968		351 (13.8)		351	Excluding Hayden Valley	Unpublished data
	1968				348 (13.7)	Excluding Hayden Valley	Dean and Varley 1973
3 fish bag limit, 14 inch min. size limit	1970				43	Excluding Hayden Valley	Dean and Mills 1971
	1970			424 (16.7)	378 (14.9)	Hayden Valley	Dean 1972
	1971		447 (17.6)		309	Hayden Valley	Dean 1972
	1971		361 (14.2)		378	Fishing Bridge	Dean 1972
	1972				125	Excluding Hayden Valley	Dean and Varley 1973
	1973				2,798	Above falls, excluding Hayden Valley	Jones et al 1976
	1973				363 (14.3)	Hayden Valley	Jones et al 1976
Catch-and-release	1974 ¹⁾	362 (14.3)			463	Lellardy's Rapids	Dean et al 1975
	1974				3,763	Excluding Hayden Valley	Jones et al 1976
	1975 ¹⁾	370 (14.6)			775	Lellardy's Rapids	Varley et al 1975
	1975				10,540	Above falls, excluding Hayden Valley	Jones et al 1976
	1976 ¹⁾	375 (14.8)			964	Lellardy's Rapids	Jones et al 1976
	1976				11,062	Above falls, excluding Hayden Valley	Jones et al 1976
	1977 ¹⁾	373 (14.7)			245	Lellardy's Rapids	Jones et al 1977
	1977				10,239	Above falls, excluding Hayden Valley	Jones et al 1977
	1978 ¹⁾	376 (14.8)			759	Lellardy's Rapids	Jones et al 1978
	1978				8,950	Above falls, excluding Hayden Valley	Jones et al 1978
	1979	385 (15.2)			571	Lellardy's Rapids	Current report
1979 ¹⁾				8,495	Above falls, excluding Hayden Valley	Current report	

1) All adults only.